

hybrid
GEOTABS

Controlling the power of the ground by integration

D6.5

Industrialisation strategy

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Summary & Overview

Starting from the hybridGEOTABS modular system concept that was introduced in D6.1, this deliverable documents the industrialisation requirements for prefabrication and pre-engineering of the hybridGEOTABS (key) modules, while considering the interaction and integration of the components in the system. Example hydraulic schemes of the concept are developed and explained, as well as generic component specifications for tendering. Furthermore, the efficient integration of hybridGEOTABS in all stages of the building process is looked after: challenges and solutions are identified.

The document includes 3 main parts and three types of documents facilitating the industrialisation of hybridGEOTABS:

1. Hydraulic schemes
2. Industrialisation requirements for prefabrication and pre-engineering (describing document)
3. Integrating hybridGEOTABS efficiently into the building process (incl. generic component specifications)

The first part, **hydraulic schemes**, is used for the following purposes:

1. Guiding HVAC engineers to develop hybridGEOTABS hydraulic schemes by providing a general hydraulic scheme and examples
2. Indicating the different working modes of hybridGEOTABS, applied in different types of buildings all over the European climate zones. This part links with the work in other work packages (e.g. WP2 design)
3. Initiating hybridGEOTABS solutions for specific HVAC-objectives such as all electric heat- and cold generation, all renewable energy sources, coupling different emission systems...
4. Introduction to the next chapter, describing document of industrialization of key-components (GSHX – HP - TABS - controller). In this chapter feedback links can be used to the general hydraulic scheme to see/indicate interactions between different components.

This first part is developed by and for HVAC engineers. It can be used as a guideline or a first introduction by other industrial partners to develop a hydraulic concept for the hybridGEOTABS concept faster. Additionally, the partners of this deliverable developed **hydraulic concepts for actual and future-proof energy concepts** such as an all-electric solution or all-renewable energy solution, which are hot topics in the EU today. This exercise illustrates the flexibility of the concept towards various building types and EU climates, as well as its compliance with the energy system features of the future. This flexibility and future readiness is possible thanks to the solid base of GEOTABS as a renewable and residual energy source, and the flexibility of the secondary systems towards both traditional and renewable solutions. The here developed hydraulic schemes are made available on the project website (www.hybridgeotabs.eu/technology).

The second part of the deliverable is a describing document that focuses on the **industrialisation** aspect and its requirements towards the development of the 4 key components: the ground-source heat exchanger (GSHX), the heat pump (HP), the thermally activated building systems (TABS) and the model predictive controller (MPC). This is done for both the **prefabrication and pre-engineering stage of each component**, however realising that not all components are suitable for prefabrication and pre-engineering today. With regard to the prefabrication requirements, for the GSHX the various drilling techniques are discussed and most important parameters for the borehole thermal resistance. For the heat pumps we look at the various ranges of heat pump sizes available in the EU market for the low-temperature heating systems, and the configurations of storage tanks. For the TABS, the prefabrication options of TABS are discussed. For the MPC no prefabrication exists at this point, but requirements for speeding up the development process are identified, e.g. the required availability of measured parameters from other system components.

With regard to the pre-engineering requirements for the GSHX, the use of the Enhanced Geothermal Response Test for optimising the borehole design is explained step-by-step. For the heat pump limited pre-engineering options are listed together with the relation to BIM. For the TABS the pre-engineering aspects for prefabricated TABS are documented. For the MPC finally, the steps in the pre-engineering of MPC are listed. This chapter is mainly developed by and for industrial partners developing and selling the four main components of the hybridGEOTABS concept. For HVAC engineers it is interesting as well as it gives them an overview of actual and future developments of these components and how this development influences the global design of a hybridGEOTABS concept.

The third part of this deliverable zooms out to the **entire building process**. To increase the share of hybridGEOTABS buildings in the EU building market, the key challenges that the concept is facing, need to be identified and need to be solved or dealt with. In this part first the various stages in the building process are introduced together with their characteristics, from the viewpoint of the HVAC-designers and the RIBA process. Secondly, **generic specifications for hybridGEOTABS components** are developed to facilitate the final design and tendering process, striving for a high-quality construction. These are made available on the project website (www.hybridgeotabs.eu/technology). Finally, for each building process stage the **hybridGEOTABS challenges** are identified. It is concluded that three groups of challenges appear: challenges specific to the hybridGEOTABS concept, challenges typical for new innovations and pioneering, and challenges related to the sustainability and energy challenge our society is facing today. For each of the identified challenges, hybridGEOTABS solutions are referred to. This way, the section also summarises the **key solutions produced within the hybridGEOTABS project, as well as the remaining challenges towards the future**.

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Lists of symbols and abbreviations

AC:	Active Cooling
AHU:	Air Handling Unit
AS:	Architectural/structural party (chapter 4)
ASHP:	Air Source Heat Pump
BIM:	Building Information Modeling
BMS:	Building Management System
DAC:	Dry Air Cooler
DACH:	Germany-Austria-Switzerland
DB:	Design-Build
DBB:	Design-Bid-Build
DBFM:	Design-Build-Finance-Maintain
DBFMO:	Design-Build-Finance-Maintain-Operation
DHW:	Domestic Hot Water
EED:	Earth Energy Designer
EGRT:	Enhanced Geothermal Response Test
EHPA:	European Heat Pump Association
FCU:	Fan Coil Unit
GSHX:	Ground Source Heat Exchanger
GRT:	Geothermal Response Test
(GS)HP:	(Ground Source) Heat Pump
HT:	High Temperature
IEQ:	Indoor Environmental Quality
MPC:	Model based Predictive Control
OWN:	Owner party (chapter 4)
PCM:	Phase Change Material
PVT:	Photovoltaic Thermal hybrid solar collector
RBC:	Rule Based Control
RIBA:	Royal Institute of British Architects
SCOP:	Seasonal Coefficient of Performance
TE:	Technical party (chapter 4)
TABS:	Thermally Activated Building Systems

1. Hydraulic schemes

A general hydraulic scheme serves as an introduction to the rest of this document. This general hydraulic scheme, where different working modes are indicated, is applicable for the baseline hybridGEOTABS concept. The last paragraph of this chapter will focus on variations which were identified by the consortium as interesting to mention in the frame of future possible alternative hybridGEOTABS design variations.

The set of hydraulic schemes produced and available in the Annex 1 of this report should be regarded as an additional guidance for HVAC designers during feasibility and mostly pre-design. It enables the HVAC engineer to consider the hydraulic connexion between the basic modules and auxiliary equipment required to implement the concept. The aim is to provide the designer with practical information¹, that constitute a base which he can build on and should accelerate the start of the actual, case-specific design.

1.1. General hydraulic scheme

This scheme includes the core modules of the hybridGEOTABS concept with basic heating and cooling functions. It therefore includes the following items:

- A borefield with a ground-source heat exchanger (GSHX)
- A ground source heat pump (GSHP)
- A buffer tank for heating
- A bivalent source and system for heating: In the generic scheme a condensing boiler using gas (or biogas) is represented. However, other renewable alternatives such as wood pellet or any other low grade energy sources can be used in combination with the GSHP. This is developed in section 2.4 and illustrated in the schemes numbered A1-A3.
- General heating emission systems: TABS, combined with e.g. low temperature radiators, Fan Coil Units (FCU's) or ventilation heating coil for instance in the case of office buildings.
 - o In this generic scheme the GSHP serves only the TABS and the bivalent source/system is coupled downstream of the TABS-group, which means the second heating system serves solely the other groups (radiators, FCU's and AHU (air handling unit)). This is a preferred option if one of the emission systems is using a high temperature regime (e.g. smaller size radiator with 55°C/45°C working temperatures).), or a low temperature cooling emission system in cooling dominated projects and the passive cooling mode for the TABS is (temporarily) targeted as well.
 - o However it should be noted that all emission systems can be coupled to the buffer tank, when all heating systems are sized for low temperature regimes. (e.g. low-temperature radiators and/or FCUs).

¹ Disclaimer: The hydraulic scheme represents one way of connecting the different core modules, auxiliary equipment and other additional / optional modules together (depending on building needs and climate) from a hydraulic point of view. It is generic, connexions may vary depending on context (environmental site conditions, HVAC know-how, economic context, building services trends, etc.) and can therefore only be used as an initial guidance. Additionally, the hydraulic scheme for a specific building will vary depending on which objectives the designer is trying to achieve (e.g. maximum cost efficiency, exergy optimisation etc.).

- A buffer tank for cooling
- A bivalent source for cooling. The bivalent cooling system proposed in the generic scheme is an air cooled chiller in addition to the reversible ground source heat pump, this can be adapted to any source of cooling available for a specific project. Some alternative options are proposed in the schemes numbered A1 to A3, for instance with a reversible air source heat pump which is described in Section 2.4 of this report
- General cooling emission systems
 - o The same cooling emission systems are proposed as in heating mode (TABS, ventilation cooling coil, FCU's) and the connections follow the considerations above for the heating mode.

Figure 2-1: General hydraulic scheme - Example of bivalent heating mode

1.2. Hydraulic schemes - working modes

In a first attempt to link a design/scheme to a specific building we tried to derive 12 different schemes (one for each combination of building and climate zone (4 building typologies and 3 different EU climate regions, Brussels, Warsaw, Madrid). When it comes to designing a general scheme for the hybridGEOTABS concept, it was clear that the core modules of the GEOTABS-solution (GSHX, HP, TABS) will be found in every building and every climate region, as previously explained in D6.1 and further in D6.2. However, it was found that there is no obvious single solution for the hybrid side of the concept. First, it is difficult to recommend only one secondary production and emission system to make this concept work, as the availability of energy sources will vary depending on the local situation and specific background information for each building project. Additionally, this was found to be very static, not allowing much freedom for the designer.

Figure 2-2 to Figure 2-4 indicates the variety of applications in function of location of the building, application for the building, type of hybrid production/emission in function of location and application, renewable extras.

	Offices	Schools	Elderly Homes	Residential
Brussels				
Heating Source 1	GSHX + HP	GSHX + HP	GSHX + HP	GSHX + HP
Heating Source 2 (peak)	Biogas/-gas boiler (peaks only)	Biogas/-gas boiler (peaks only)	Biogas/-gas boiler (peaks only)	Biogas/-gas boiler (peaks only)
alternative heating source	Wood pellet, ASHP, district heating, etc.	Wood pellet, ASHP, district heating	Solar thermal, Extract Air/Water HP	Solar thermal, extract A/W HP
Cooling Source 1a	passive geo-cooling (free cooling)	passive geo-cooling (free cooling)	passive geo-cooling (free cooling)	passive geo-cooling (free cooling)
	TABS -> GSHX (no HP)	TABS -> GSHX (no HP)	TABS -> GSHX (no HP)	TABS -> GSHX (no HP)
Cooling Source 1b	active geo-cooling (rev HP)	none	none	none
	TABS -> rev HP -> GSHX			
Cooling Source 2 (peaks)	air cooled chiller (peaks only)	none	none	none
	chiller + dry coolers			
Ventilation	Central AHU, HR, htg and dfg coils	Central AHU, HR, htg coil only	Central AHU, HR, htg coil only	Central AHU, HR, htg coil only
	covers hygienic requirements (night time free cooling in peak summer)	covers hygienic requirements (+nat vent possible)	covers hygienic requirements (+nat vent possible)	covers hygienic requirements (+nat vent possible)
Heating/Cooling Emission 1	TABS	TABS	TABS	TABS
	4 pipes FCU or Ventilation	radiators	radiators	radiators
Heating Emission 2	none	none	none	none
Cooling Emission 2	none	none	none	none
Domestic Hot water	Central heat pump, fresh water station (FWS) connected to HWS tank	Central heat pump, fresh water station (FWS) connected to HWS tank	Dedicated DHW heat pump	Dedicated DHW heat pump
	low demand	low demand	high demand	high demand
DHW alternative	decentral - under sink electro boiler	decentral - under sink electro boiler	via solar / PV-T, dry coolers	via solar / PV-T, dry coolers
Regeneration boreholes	via passive / active cooling with or without dry cooler, PV-T	via passive cooling		
optional				

Figure 2-2: "Western Europe" - Oceanic Climate (mild winters, humid summers)

Warsaw	Offices				
Heating Source 1	GSHX + HP	Schools	GSHX + HP	Elderly Homes	GSHX + HP
Heating Source 2 (peak)	Biogas/- gas boiler (peaks only)	Biogas/- gas boiler (peaks only)	Biogas/- gas boiler (peaks only)	Biogas/- gas boiler (peaks only)	Biogas/- gas boiler (peaks only)
alternative heating source	Wood pellet, ASHP, district heating, etc.	Wood pellet, ASHP, district heating	Solar thermal, Extract Air/Water HP	Solar thermal, extract A/W HP	
Cooling Source 1a	passive geo-cooling (free cooling)	passive geo-cooling (free cooling)	passive geo-cooling (free cooling)	passive geo-cooling (free cooling)	passive geo-cooling (free cooling)
Cooling Source 1b	TABS -> GSHX (no HP)	TABS -> GSHX (no HP)	TABS -> GSHX (no HP)	TABS -> GSHX (no HP)	TABS -> GSHX (no HP)
Cooling Source 2 (peaks)	TABS -> rev HP -> GSHX	TABS -> rev HP -> GSHX	TABS -> rev HP -> GSHX	TABS -> rev HP -> GSHX	none
	air cooled chiller (peaks only)	none	none	none	none
	Chiller + dry cooler				
Ventilation	Central AHU, HR, htg and clg coils	Central AHU, HR, 1 coil in change over mode	Central AHU, HR, 1 coil in change over mode (can use free cooling)	Central AHU, HR, 1 coil in change over mode (can use free cooling)	Central AHU, HR, 1 coil in change over mode (can use free cooling)
	covers hygienic requirements (night time free cooling in peak summer)	covers hygienic requirements (night time free cooling in peak summer)	covers hygienic requirements (night time free cooling in peak summer)	covers hygienic requirements (+that vent possible)	covers hygienic requirements (+that vent possible)
		- air volume can be increased to serve as secondary cooling system (peak summer days)	- air volume can be increased to serve as secondary cooling system in some rooms (rest aulant, living room)	- air volume can be increased to serve as secondary cooling system in some rooms (rest aulant, living room)	
Heating/Cooling Emission 1	TABS	TABS	TABS	TABS	TABS
Heating Emission 2		radiators	radiators	radiators	radiators
Cooling Emission 2	4 pipes FCU or Ventilation	ventilation air (to a certain extent only, we cannot oversize the AHU and ducts)	ventilation air (to a certain extent only, we cannot oversize the AHU and ducts)	ventilation air (to a certain extent only, we cannot oversize the AHU and ducts)	ventilation air (to a certain extent only, we cannot oversize the AHU and ducts)
Domestic Hot water	Central heat pump, fresh water station (FWS) connected to HWS tank	Central heat pump, fresh water station (FWS) connected to HWS tank	Dedicated DHW heat pump	Dedicated DHW heat pump	Dedicated DHW heat pump
	low demand	low demand	high demand	high demand	high demand
DHW alternative	decentral - under sink electro boiler	decentral - under sink electro boiler			
Regeneration boreholes (heat storage)	via passive cooling, dry cooler, PV-T	via passive cooling, dry cooler, PV-T	via solar / PV-T	via solar / PV-T	via solar / PV-T
	depends on annual ground balance	depends on annual ground balance	depends on annual ground balance	depends on annual ground balance	depends on annual ground balance

Figure 2-3: "Central and Eastern Europe" - Cold winters and hot dry summers

Madrid	Offices	Schools	Elderly Homes	Residential
Heating Source 1	GSHX + rev HP	GSHX + rev HP	GSHX + rev. HP	GSHX + rev. HP
Heating Source 2 (peaks)	none (ground source sized on heating needs)	none (ground source sized on heating needs)	Solar (thermal or PVT) or extract air HP? for hot water demand	Solar (thermal or PVT) or extract air HP? for hot water demand
Cooling Source 1a	passive geo-cooling (free cooling) TABS -> GSHX (no HP)	passive geo-cooling (free cooling) TABS -> GSHX (no HP)	passive geo-cooling (free cooling) TABS -> GSHX (no HP)	passive geo-cooling (free cooling) TABS -> GSHX (no HP)
Cooling Source 1b	active geo-cooling (rev HP) TABS -> rev HP -> GSHX	active geo-cooling (rev HP) TABS -> rev HP -> GSHX	active geo-cooling (rev HP) TABS -> rev HP -> GSHX	active geo-cooling (rev HP) TABS -> rev HP -> GSHX
Cooling Source 2 (peaks)	air cooled chiller (peaks only) Chiller + dry cooler	none (not occupied in high summer)	air cooled chiller (peaks only) chiller + dry cooler	none
Ventilation	Central AHU, HR, htg and clg coils covers hygienic requirements (+night time cooling/ventilation)	Central AHU, HR, htg and clg coils covers hygienic requirements (night time free cooling) - air volume can be increased to serve as secondary cooling system (peak summer days)	Central AHU, HR, htg and clg coils covers hygienic requirements (+nat vent possible) - air volume can be increased to serve as secondary cooling system in some rooms (restaurant, living room)	Central AHU, HR, htg and clg coils covers hygienic requirements (+natural vent possible)
Heating/ Cooling Emission 1	TABS	TABS	TABS	TABS
Heating Emission 2	4 pipes FCU	none FCUs or ventilation air (to a certain extent only, we cannot oversize the AHU and ducts)	none FCUs or ventilation air (to a certain extent only, we cannot oversize the AHU and ducts)	none FCUs
Cooling Emission 2				
Domestic Hot water	Central heat pump, fresh water station (FWS) connected to HWS tank low demand	Central heat pump, fresh water station (FWS) connected to HWS tank low demand	Dedicated DHW heat pump high demand	Dedicated DHW heat pump high demand
DHW alternative	decentral - under sink elect ro boiler	decentral - under sink elect ro boiler		
Regeneration boreholes (heat storage)	via passive cooling and/ or dry cooler depends on annual ground balance	via passive cooling and/ or dry cooler depends on annual ground balance	via solar / PV-T depends on annual ground balance	via solar / PV-T depends on annual ground balance

Figure 2-4: "Southern Europe" - Mediterranean Climate

Consequently, a new strategy was developed, which consists of highlighting different basic operating modes for heating, cooling and production of domestic hot water. Additionally, alternative options were developed depending on the region and type of building but mainly based on the results of the pre-design split / sizing exercise completed using the project feasibility and pre-design tool, as developed in WP2 (T2.5; D2.6)

The reason to choose for this alternative method is that every building is unique and the consortium team is not prescribing a fixed design, but simply showing what can be done instead, depending on the results of WP2 (D2.6).

In section 2.3 and 2.4 we demonstrate further how the hybrid components (hybrid production and emission systems for heating and cooling) support a high level of flexibility for the designer and can untap the full potential of this concept for achieving exemplary environmental performance.

Indeed, many different options can be considered and combined with the core modules in a fully functioning hydraulic scheme depending on the building "working" modes. The different modes are more or less dominant in each climate zone and for each building typology. The designer can use these schemes as another tool from the "hybridGEOTABS toolbox" to get started with his case specific design.

Following modes are therefore identified as commonly required and are included in the general version of the scheme. Some additional variations are also proposed.

HEATING

- GEOTABS heating as only production and emission system (e.g. office in Madrid)
- Bivalent GEOTABS heating production in combination with 2nd emission system (e.g. elderly home in Brussels)

COOLING

- Natural GEOTABS cooling as standard cooling for all building (e.g. residential building in Zürich)
- Reversible active GEOTABS cooling when free cooling peak power is no longer sufficient even if the energy ground source balance is still achievable (e.g. office in Warsaw)
- Bivalent cooling with an air cooled chiller serving the secondary emission systems (e.g. office in Madrid)

DOMESTIC HOT WATER (DHW)

- DHW centrally produced by main HP using fresh water station (lower demand e.g. in offices, schools)
- DHW decoupled from GSHP with a dedicated DHW HP (high demand all year round, e.g. elderly homes)

All scenarios are highlighted on the general hydraulic scheme and explained individually in the next section.

1.3. Different working modes

The general hydraulic scheme can be seen as a pragmatic approach, with secondary heating and cooling modules, considered as the most available and implemented options, and therefore reflects current practice. Other options which may be considered more progressive are presented in the next chapter 2.4.

All different working modes of the generic scheme are displayed with colours. The combination of hydraulic circuits working together at the same time to produce the desired service (heating, cooling, DHW) is visually presented. The colours mainly represent the content (but also the purpose) of the fluid used in the hydraulic circuit. For instance, a different colour is used for glycol-water (brine water) and heated/chilled water running through the TABS or even cooling water through a condenser coil. The legend describes the type/content of each water circuit. The parts greyed-out in the scheme are not necessarily used in that particular working mode, however these modules are nevertheless required for other basic operation modes of the building.

1.3.1. Heating operation modes:

H1 – GEOTABS heating (no hybrid production/emission system)

- H1(a) – no storage tank on the primary side (borefield).

It is important to note that this scheme without buffer tank on the primary side is not compatible with a building requiring active cooling (AC). Heating and passive (free) cooling are possible.

H2 – Bivalent Heating (GEOTABS + hybrid production and emission system)

- H2(a) – no storage tank on the primary side (borefield)

The bivalent system illustrated in this example is a biogas or gas condensing boiler. It is covering the peak residual heat loads of the building and its nominal power will be given by the Feasibility and Pre-design tool developed in WP2 (D2.6). The hydraulic connexion presented is a simplified approach which can suit many buildings such as residential buildings, elderly homes and schools in the northern part of Europe. This scheme is not compatible with building requiring AC

- H2(b) – storage tank included for compatibility with active cooling purpose

In the cases of H1(a) and H2(a) the storage tank on the primary borefield side is omitted, which means the building cannot operate in active cooling mode without some modification to the hydraulic connection (position of the main pump on the return (pressure side) and pressure losses must be carefully examined). It is best used for buildings which do not require active cooling.

H2(b) presents a heating mode, with connexions which are better suited for active cooling in summer, when free cooling possibilities are exhausted.

1.3.2. Cooling operation modes:

C1 – Passive GEOTABS cooling (free cooling only)

The borefield temperature is low enough to cool the building via the free cooling heat exchanger (glycol-water/water) without any additional heat pump power. Many buildings which did not require cooling in the past (typically homes and elderly homes in northern Europe) are currently being planned with a free cooling heat exchanger, to provide a soft cooling and guarantee comfort if the temperature rises in summer. It brings additional value to a project.

C₁(a) shows the connexions required for a building which can operate in free cooling mode only. It does not require further active cooling (neither from the reversible heat pump nor from a bivalent cooling source).

C₁(b) is also highlighting passive cooling operation but in the case of a building, which will need to have all necessary equipment for active cooling of the building when free cooling is exhausted.

C₂ – Active GEOTABS cooling (reversible HP) - all heat from cooling is rejected into the borefield.

In this example all heat rejected from the heat pump in reversible mode is directed to the ground, with no heat rejection to the outside air. This concept assumes that the ground capacity is sized to balance the heating and cooling loads over a year. A dry air cooler can be added in certain cases in order to control how much heat is rejected to the ground (connexion model for the Dry Air Cooler (DAC) unit is provided in next scheme C₃).

C₃ – Bivalent Cooling with active GEOTABS cooling PLUS an additional air-cooled chiller

The air cooled chiller covers peak residual cooling loads. Its nominal power will be determined by the Feasibility and Pre-Design Sizing Tool developed in WP₂ (D_{2.6}).

1.3.3. Domestic Hot Water

DHW₁ – Central DHW production (in case of low DHW demand, e.g. offices)

The heating hot water is produced centrally by the main heat pump and feeds a second heating storage tank for DHW only. There is no dedicated HP for the DHW production. From this second heating storage tank a fresh water station (HEX) serves the DHW need as and when required. This system guarantees hygienic requirements (legionella) as well as higher efficiency for the production of domestic hot water.

DHW₂ – Decentral DHW production, typical

As opposed to the previous scheme, this scheme shows how to decouple the central heat pump and a dedicated / separate DHW heat pump which is sized on the DHW demand only. This is particularly used in buildings with a larger all year round DHW demand (residential, elderly homes). It has the advantages of not compromising the COP of the main GSHP.

DHW₃ – Decentral DHW production with booster HP.

In this variation of DHW₂, the water supply (to the evaporator side) of the decentral DHW-HP is coming from the hot storage tank which will be already heated up by the return of the TABS and other heating groups in winter. This has the effect of increasing the efficiency of the DHW HP, which is only there to “boost” the temperature to the required level for DHW (60°C).

1.4. Alternative good examples

In this chapter answers to some future questions/problems will be given. These alternatives are considered today as best practice in the integration of secondary hybrid components within the hybridGEOTABS concept.

Problem 1: The building is heating dominated and no seasonal balance is found in the underground over one year, which can, in the long term cool down the borefield in such a way that it is no longer suitable for winter operation.

Solution A1 – Exergy optimised with PVT-regeneration

The scheme includes a PVT (Photovoltaic Thermal hybrid solar collector) module. It has two outputs; first the solar thermal output of the system is used to “regenerate” the boreholes with heat. The electric output is used as regular source of green power for the building services, at times when the production and demand matches. The remaining is stored in the grid or can be stored in batteries to increase auto-consumption in the building (auxiliary electrical equipment, e-mobility on site, etc.)

The objective is to raise the temperature of the borefield back to a sustainable level at the beginning of each winter season (long term management of the ground). This is especially important in densely built residential neighbourhoods, where many of such systems may be installed close to each other, to prevent long-term exhaustion of the ground.

Solar regeneration and direct free cooling strategies are compatible, however they must be carefully examined in terms of control, in order to avoid limiting the free cooling potential.

Problem 2: EU wants to see an all-electric solution. Furthermore, a clear industrial trend of increased (optimised) self-consumption of PV-electricity is observed. HybridGEOTABS can help with the optimisation of self-consumption of on-site produced electricity.

Solution A2 – All electric bivalent heating/cooling with air-to-water HP

Adding a reversible air-to-water heat pump* (air source HP) to the general hydraulic scheme as a bivalent system will provide an all-electric solution where the PV panels (or PV-T panels) will serve the heat pumps. It increases the share of green power self-consumption.

It should be noted that in this case, it is recommended to use the air source heat pump (ASHP) (usually lower COP than GSHP) to feed the TABS, as it has a lower temperature lift than the other groups, and therefore will guarantee the efficiency of the ASHP. The GSHP will serve the other groups.

* air to air systems can also be considered, but are not interfering with the hydraulic scheme.

Problem 3: The user wants to use only renewable sources of energy for heating

Solution A3 – Bivalent Heating – Biomass (with a wood pellet/chip boiler for instance).

The most often used renewable heating system in the EU [17] is proposed in this hydraulic scheme, it highlights the fact that a wood boiler connexion as a bivalent system is not interchangeable with a typical gas/biogas boiler connexion presented in H2(a) and H2(b). Indeed, biomass combustion is not a fast-reacting heat source like gas and it has its own heat inertia. It requires a different hydraulic integration (with a necessary additional storage)

2. Industrialisation requirements of the key modules

The 4 key components are visualized on the general hydraulic scheme in Figure 2-1.

2.1. Industrialisation requirements for prefabrication

2.1.1. Ground Source Heat Exchanger (GSHX)

In this section we will take a closer look to the “prefabrication” aspects of the ground heat exchanger. It means, a review about most common type of borehole heat exchangers, analysing different drilling techniques and the most important parameters influencing the borehole thermal resistance: pipe materials, borehole configuration, glycol solutions and filling materials.

Drilling techniques

There are two frequently used drilling methods percussion and rotation. In addition to these two, new drilling techniques have been developed from the previous ones (e.g. roto-percussion, sonic drilling, horizontal directional drilling, etc).

Percussion

This method consists of inserting prefabricated thrust piles into the ground (deep foundation structures) by repetitive impact until no further penetration is possible. These piles may incorporate an exchange circuit or may have a hollow core in which a circuit is inserted. This drilling method, although it is still improving its performance, has a very slow penetration rate (approximately <10m/day, This makes it unprofitable for closed circuit systems. It is only used for:

- Open loop, construction of deep wells, with high yield ratio in unconsolidated aquifers or karst areas.
- Energy foundation; drilling in boulder zones for in situ pile construction.

This drilling method is an economic option for installing coaxial exchangers in non-consolidated formations.

Figure 3-1: Prefabricated pile introduction. Source: <https://junttan.com/>

Rotation

This drilling method is best known for oil extraction as well as for mining and hydrogeology exploration. It consists of transmitting a rotation with a rotation head to a train of threaded drill pipes with continuous sample recuperation. At the top, a drill bit is used. It can be a tricone for crunch drilling or a drill bit with continuous sample recovery. This endless screw system is the most widely used in surface drilling (<50 m), in unconsolidated materials and in foundations. With this drilling method, the excavated material is extracted with an Archimedes bolt, keeping the hole open.

The majority of the rotary methods, however, use mud as wellbore fluid and are classified as direct or inverse rotations, depending on the function of the drilling mud's flow:

- Direct circulation: The mud is pumped through the drill pipe and leaves via the bottom of the well through the nozzles located in the drill head. Once down, it returns to the surface dragging cuttings and detritus through the ring between the well and the pipe. Direct circulation methods fit well for narrow diameter boreholes, <300 mm, and in consolidated formations with compressive strength of up to 150 MPa.
- Reverse circulation: mud is pumped down the annulus and back up through the drill pipe. The pressure inside the drill pipe sinks, which permits the mud and the detritus to evacuate towards the surface where it is deposited in the decantation vessel. These systems are used in wide diameter boreholes, >300 mm, and in unconsolidated formations.

Roto-percussion (Rotary hammer)

Currently, the most commonly used methods for drilling geothermal wells are roto-percussion methods, which integrate elements of both rotation and percussion methods. To perform the drilling, a jackhammer or a hydraulic hammer is used that breaks the formation with alternative blows at frequencies between 500 and 2000 blows per minute. This hammer is activated through the drill pipe and a torque is applied to constantly change the point of impact, thus avoiding wedging the tool and facilitating the disintegration of the rock and the verticality of the well. Detritus are evacuated by means of water or compressed air.

Roto-percussion systems are categorized according to the point of impact:

- Top hammer. The striking occurs at the head of the drill pipe and is transmitted to the hammer at the base of the chain. This is a frequently used method in undep blast boreholes, <50m. It's the standard drilling method for drilling in quarry blast pits and public work as well as in tunnels and gallery drilling.
- Down the hole hammer. A piston within the hammer at the bottom of the drillstring strikes the rockface. High-pressure air is injected through the drill pipe, normally 12-30 bar, causing an alternative movement at the hammer's trigger. The trigger strikes the drill bit, pushing out the compressed air through the drill bit's nozzle completing the sweep, and transports the rock cuttings to the surface.

Figure 3-2 Top hammer and down the hole hammer technology. Source: <https://americawestdrillingsupply.com/>

Drilling fluid

Depending on the direction of the drilling fluid there are two main types: direct circulation and reverse circulation as mentioned in rotation process.

Piping, sealing materials and carrier fluids

Vertical ground heat exchanger piping configurations can be categorized based on how the heat exchange from the flow channels takes place and to their cross-sectional geometry.

U probe

In the U-pipe type geothermal probe, both the downward and the upward flow channels participate in the heat exchange with the surrounding ground.

The usual method to achieve heat exchange in a borehole is to insert one or more U-shaped loops of polyethylene tubing into the borehole. Single U-pipes are used in North-Europe and North-America, whereas double U-pipes are common in Central Europe. In South Europe both single and double U-pipes are used.

- The single U-pipe main advantages are simple design, ease of transport and simple installation compared to other alternatives. It is an industrial standard. The installation, based on proven best-practice procedures, has an almost unlimited lifetime (although manufacturers use to provide 10 years of guarantee). The main problems are leakage due to improper fusing of U-

bends and weak bottom pieces. The major disadvantage of the single U-pipe is the relatively poor heat transfer capacity, especially at non-turbulent flow conditions.

- Double, triple and multitube U-pipes are simple extensions of the single U-pipe concept. The main advantages of multitube arrangements compared with single U-tubes are the effective heat transfer area increase and the decrease of the influence of the relatively large thermal resistance of the plastic tubes. The influence of the convective heat transfer coefficient also decreases, which means that the importance of non-laminar flow at design loads is less critical.

The most commonly used U pipes are polyethylene PE100 as they are flexible and sustainable. However, the thermal resistance of the pipes is relatively high, especially with thicker walls of the SDR-11 and PN16 pipes. The pressure rating refers to a temperature of 20°C. The strength improves with lower temperatures, but reduces with higher temperatures. PE100 probes operating temperatures are between -20°C and +45°C. When working with higher operating temperatures polybutylene and PEX probes are used.

Figure 3-3: Single U geothermal probe and Single U geothermal PEX-a probe. Source: www.uponor.es

Coaxial probe

The characteristics of the coaxial (or tube-in-tube) type geothermal probe is that heat exchange occurs from either the upstream or downstream flow channel (the flow direction may also be different during injection or extraction of heat). The inner return pipe is insulated in order to avoid thermal short-circuiting between the upwards and downwards flow channels.

Figure 3-4: Coaxial probe. Source: <https://www.stuewa.de>

Figure 3-5: Differences between Double U probe and Coaxial probe. Source: <https://www.geokoax.com>

Carrier fluids

The selection of heat carrier fluids depends on the density of the fluid and its impact to the groundwater after leakage. The lower the density, the higher the energy savings for the circulation pumps of the borefield. Furthermore, fluids should be non-toxic and easily biodegradable. The ideal heat carrier would be pure water but is not possible as the design temperatures in winter typically are below 0°C. So, an antifreeze has to be added to achieve a lower freezing temperature. Most often used are: monoethylglycol, propylenglycol, ethanol and other salt brines. Different glycol solutions and water properties are shown in the following table:

	Freezing point (°C)	Viscosity (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	Density (kg m ⁻³)
Water at 5°C	0	0.00152	1000
Water at 10°C	0	0.001308	999.8
Water at 15°C	0	0.001139	999.2
Water at 20°C	0	0.001003	998.3
Water at 25°C	0	0.000891	997.2
Water at 30°C	0	0.000798	995.8
Water at 35°C	0	0.00072	994.1
30.5% Ethylene glycol at 0°C	-15	0.00438	1046
32.9% Propylene glycol at 0°C	-15	0.00812	1034
24.4% Ethanol at 0°C	-15	0.00585	972
19.9% Methanol at 0°C	-15	0.00326	973
18.8% Sodium chloride at 0°C	-15	0.00257	1146
24% Freezium™ at 0°C	-15	0.00221	1152
24.0% Potassium acetate at 0°C	-15	0.00336	1130

Figure 3-6: Glycol solutions and water properties. Source: Banks, David. 2008. *An Introduction To Thermogeology, Ground Source Heating And Cooling.* (Blackwell Publishing ed.).

Sealings

In North-Europe, the boreholes are usually filled with groundwater to a few meters below the ground surface. In the US and in Central and South Europe it is common practice to backfill the boreholes with some high conductivity mortars with better heat transfer than other sealing materials used like bentonite, concrete or quartz sand. Differences about thermal conductivity are shown in the following table:

Material	Thermal conductivity (W/m,K)
Sand, gravel – dry	0,4
Water (stagnant)	0,6
Bentonite 10 %, water	0,7
Bentonite/cement/sand, 9/9/20 %, water	0,7-0,8
Sand, moist	1,0
Bentonite 10 %, frozen	1,4
Bentonite/quartzsand, 12/50 %, water	1,5
Gravel, water-saturated	1,8
Ice	2,3
Cement/sand, 27 %/58 %, water	2,4
Quartzsand, water-saturated	2,4-2,7
ThermoCem (cement/graphite)	2,0

Figure 3-7: Thermal conductivity (W/m,K) of borehole filling materials. Source: www.geotrained.eu

2.1.2. Heat Pump (HP)

Geothermal heat pumps are often manufactured in serial production. Additionally, geothermal heat pumps used in a hybridGEOTABS concept are typically used in combination with low temperature heating e.g. TABS. As a starting point, all members the European Heat Pump Association (EHPA, <https://www.ehpa.org/about/members/>) were studied. A first selection was done based on the available nominal thermal power of the geothermal heat pumps in the product portfolio of each member (>20kW for buildings with a minimum floor surface area of 1.000m²).

Based on this list, the standard product portfolio was compared in more detail. All data of the following evaluation criteria were collected Figure 3-9:

- The name/type of the series
- The nominal thermal condenser power (kW) following European test standard EN14511 (Bo/W35)
- The use of inverter compressor technology
- The number of compressors in the machine
- The COP following European test standard EN14511 (Bo/W35)
- The minimum water supply temperature
- The ErP efficiency/SCOP for an average climate, low temperature heating (35°C) following directive n° 813/2013

Based on this overview the following conclusions are drawn:

- From all members of EHPA, a lot of manufacturers have serial production of high condenser power heat pumps (>20kW). Most manufactures are located in DACH-countries (Germany-Austria-Switzerland) and Scandinavia,
- As most manufacturers offer the possibility to make a cascade of multiple heat pumps, the available power range, even with on/off technology is quite dense. The maximal oversizing is ± 10kW. The influence of oversizing will be discussed later in this chapter.
- Most of the heat pumps still use on/off compressor technology, but with possibilities of part load operation by doubling the number of compressors.
- Three manufacturers offer inverter compressors in their heat pump serie. But, as Stiebel Eltron recently acquired Danfoss (with Thermia as main brand), only two different machines are available on the market (based on EHPA members)
- Most of the geothermal heat pumps have a COP at nominal test conditions following EN standard EN14511 of 4,4 up to 4,8. The tested Viessmann heat pump (Deliverable 6.2, chapter 3) is in line with available market efficiencies. The influence of lowering the supply water temperature to e.g. 25°C was tested in this deliverable.
- All heat pumps are able to deliver heat at a lower supply water temperature as the test conditions following EN 14511. To be able to have a more detailed comparison, the compressor working envelopes should be available. Commonly, this information was not available. Such a compressor envelope indicates the most extreme working conditions. The minimum supply water temperature is presented in function of the brine inlet temperature.
- The last column presents the SCOP and/or seasonal efficiency following the latest European directive (n° 813/2013). This directive should make a comparison between different brands easier for the end consumer. Not every manufacturer presents the efficiencies in the same way. Some choose to indicate the SCOP, others present an efficiency. There is a direct correlation between both values included in the directive. Most of the manufacturers choose to publish the Efficiency at Low-Temperature operation (35°C).

As concluded based on the market available heat pumps, the series production in the power range of this project is quite dense. Making cascades of multiple heat pumps is a common practice, so very large (>10kW) oversizing is rather rare. Guidelines are available to avoid bad functioning caused by oversizing of the heat pumps in the early design and detailed design phase.

In the hybridGEOTABS-concept a secondary production system will always be available. In the early design phase a trade-of between over-/under-sizing of the heat pump in function of the peak load can be executed. The influence of the selection of the heat pump power can be simulated with the early-design tool.

In the detailed design phase the heat pump power influences the sizing of the storage buffer tank. This topic has been discussed during the training activities of REHVA CLIMA conference in Bucharest, 2019. The storage tank is used to avoid on-off cycling of the compressors. The optimal runtime of the compressor is 1 to 2 hours, the minimum runtime is +/- 10minutes. A second goal of using a storage tank is to decouple the heat production from the heat pump towards the heat distribution in the building. If stratification is needed in the storage tank, the water speed inside the tank should be lower than 0.4m/s. In Figure 3-8 different ways to couple a storage tank are presented. This is not a complete list of all hydraulic couplings and each of them has its advantages and disadvantages. From left to right.

- A: Advantage: limited water flow through storage tank, so better stratification. Supply water temperature of heat pump is supply water temperature towards TABS in the building directly.
- A Disadvantage: extra cost of flow valve to control the primary and secondary water flows through the storage tank.

- B Advantage: Same as figure left
- B Disadvantage: Connections of storage tank should be adapted for the total water flow.

- C Advantage: Heat pump is completely decoupled from heat distribution in the building. The most robust solution
- C Disadvantage: The primary water flow should always be higher as the secondary water flow. This leads to an internal mixing point in the storage tank. Therefore the heat pump needs to produce heat at a higher supply water temperature leading to a loss of efficiency.

Figure 3-8: Different ways to couple storage tank: Left side of buffer tank: Heat pump production, Right side of buffer: secondary emission

2.1.3. TABS and PCM ceiling panels

Economic analysis of TABS and PCM ceiling panels

TABS and PCM (phase change material) panels offer benefits such as improved thermal comfort, decreased peak loads and reduced energy use [1] [2] [3]. Nevertheless, traditional all-air systems are preferred as TABS and PCM are presumed to have higher installation and operation costs. In order to be able to promote the use of both prefabricated TABS and PCM, an economic analysis is required to identify each technology's current level of competitiveness with respect to all-air systems.

For the comparison of the three technologies in terms of their economic performance, the results of a simulation study carried out by Quesada on an open-plan office for the cooling period will be used [4]. This study is of interest since it documented that PCM panels and TABS are similar with respect to energy performance, operation, heat removal characteristics and the resulting indoor thermal environment [4] [5]. Moreover, five different cases will be investigated as well, with 24, 18, 12, 6 and 3 occupants per office as in the initial study.

Data will be acquired on the lifespan of components (ceiling panels, fans, heat pumps, etc.) and their associated costs for each of the three systems, PCM, TABS and All-air. Different indicators such as global costs (initial investment, replacement operation, services and residual value) and the payback time will be determined for each technology and compared. The results will be thoroughly reported in final version of Deliverable 6.3 – usability of radiant ceiling panels with PCM.

Prefabrication of TABS

In the interest of the industrialization of TABS, manufacturers have developed different modular solutions to achieve offsite – manufacturing, onsite – assembly for construction companies and installers. The main advantages of prefabricated and standardized TABS lie in, e.g, reducing the waste of onsite construction materials, improving efficiencies of constructing TABS, as well as decreasing the need for locally trained installers/construction workers who are licenced to build TABS. However, to achieve full potentials of prefabricated TABS modules, there is a need to collaborate with local concrete and slab suppliers, given the nature that TABS-slab modules are too heavy to be transported over long distances. In situ concrete slabs are currently the most common type of floor construction for office buildings. The piping components, modules, mesh hooks and the patented ceiling lead-through elements were developed specifically for this type of slab, see Figure 3-10.below.

Figure 3-10: In situ concrete casting [8]

Another important step to increase the industrialization is to standardize the products. When TABS are designed and installed in situ in modules, standardized products make the process much faster and safer. Currently, the standardized TABS product is shown in Figure 3-11.

Figure 3-11: The standardized TABS modules [8]

Prefabrication of PCM panels

In the interest of the industrialization of prefabricated PCM ceiling panels as a renovation strategy, several requirements have been identified with respect to their construction and operation. A new PCM panel has been developed as part of this project following the identified requirements. The main improvements associated with their construction are related to leakage and corrosion problems. Moreover, the heat transfer between the PCM material and the pipes is crucial for an efficient discharge of the PCM [5] [6]. Although these problems were overcome in the prototype phase, the methods proved costly in terms of investment and time. Therefore, the construction of a prefabricated metal casing with embedded pipes following the guidelines would contribute to the reduction of the initial investment and maintenance costs. Nonetheless, fire tests under present standardization are required in order to allow the technology's market penetration.

Regarding the PCM panel operation, correct sizing of the PCM material is critical due to the sensitivity between the PCM heat capacity and the cooling load. Water circulation represents a better discharging method by increasing the solidification percentage of the PCM. Moreover, an increase in thermal conductivity and operation time combined with lower supply water temperature leads to a better thermal environment while increasing the flow rate provides only marginal benefits compared to the other parameters [5].

During the cooling season, the PCM panels behave similarly to TABS in terms of operation, heat removal, energy use and created thermal indoor environment [4]. In addition, the PCM achieves comparable results with TABS and All-air systems in terms of thermal environment with a lower energy use than All-air systems. For similar results in terms of thermal indoor environment between PCM, TABS and All-air over the heating season, a preliminary study showed that a higher energy use is required in the case of PCM systems, compared to the All-air system. However, it should be noted that this was only a preliminary result and further work is ongoing. Finally, for an all-year simulation, the thermal environment registered is worse associated with a high energy use as a consequence of the control strategy for transitioning periods between the cooling and heating season [7]. There are several possibilities to improve the performance of PCM panels in the heating season and current studies are addressing these issues. Therefore, before market ready solutions and a possible industrialization of PCM ceiling panels, clear design guidelines are required for their construction, dimensioning, control and implementation.

2.1.4. Controller

Although prefabricated MPC (Model based Predictive Control) controllers do not exist at this moment, MPC controllers can be implemented faster, when the minimum requirements (sensors, control parameters, read/write variables etc.) are determined before implementing MPC to new or existing building.

Typically, MPC controls setpoints of the emission system (main TABS system and alternative ventilation system). In the case of TABS system, MPC controls the supply water temperature setpoint, respectively the TABS power setpoint in all TABS zones. For the TABS system (for each zone of TABS) it is important to measure the following minimum set of variables:

- supply water temperature to TABS
- return water temperature to TABS
- flow rate in TABS

In case the low-level controllers (PID, RBC (Rule Based Control)) control the valves in the system to ensure the desired supply water temperature or TABS power (typically in case of existing buildings), it is not needed to measure valve openings in the system. In this case, it must be ensured that MPC can write the control signals (supply water temperature setpoints or TABS power setpoints) to the interface between Building Management System (BMS) and MPC and the low-level controllers keep the setpoints provided by MPC reliably.

However, if the MPC also controls the valves opening in the system, it is necessary to measure them. Depending on the configuration of the TABS system, all valves, which preserve control of the desired supply water temperatures need to be measured, i.e. two-way valves, three-way valves, mixing valves. Again, it must be ensured that MPC can directly control these valves through an interface with BMS.

As the ventilation system is the most often alternative low-temperature emission system within the hybridGEOTABS concept, here the minimum requirements for ventilation system variables are listed. As there are a lot of types of AHUs (draw-through, blow-through, with cooling coils only, etc.), only the most important requirements for measurement of AHUs are listed below:

necessary:

- supply air temperature to individual rooms
- return air temperature from individual rooms
- flow rate in each AHU
- speed of fan(s) in each AHU
- supply water temperature to each heating/cooling coil
- return water temperature in each heating/cooling coil

recommended:

- electricity consumption of AHU
- heat consumption of AHU

The output variables of MPC are typically supply air temperature setpoints and required flow rate in each AHU. These variables must be communicated through the interface between BMS and MPC.

The goal of the MPC is to keep the thermal comfort and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) in the building, therefore some sensors to provide a feedback to MPC are necessary:

- room temperatures
- CO₂ sensors

(ideally in all rooms, which are heated and ventilated by MPC or at least in some reference rooms)

and optional (recommended):

- solar irradiation sensors
- ambient temperature sensors
- occupancy sensors

To evaluate or compare the MPC with the existing (RBC strategy) it is also recommended to measure important quantities at the energy source side. In hybridGEOTABS concept, heat pumps are the main energy sources, therefore it is recommended to measure:

- flow rate at the primary (evaporator) side
- flow rate at the secondary (condenser) side
- inlet and outlet temperatures at the evaporator side
- inlet and outlet temperatures at the condenser side
- electricity consumption of heat pump

If the MPC also controls the setpoint temperatures in buffer tanks (heat storage tank, cold storage tank, domestic hot water tank), it is needed to measure these temperatures. Typically, temperatures are measured at different levels of heat storage tank.

2.2. Industrialization requirements for pre-engineering

2.2.1. Ground Source Heat Exchanger (GSHX)

Geothermal Response Test analysis: EGRT and GRT

Most important investigation and analysis about “ground heat exchanger pre-engineering” in this project is developed in deliverable 6.2: “The optimization of the current geothermal response test with the development of an enhanced geothermal response test”. Definitions, procedures, differences and advantages between them are going to be explained below.

When it comes to sizing the geothermal borehole field, the use of a GRT (Geothermal Response Test) is the most prevalent practice in Europe. It consists of an on-site test to determine the thermodynamic parameters of the subsoil. Besides, for installations above 30 kW it is common and recommended to perform a pilot borehole in accordance with VDI 4640 standard (VDI-Standard: VDI 4640 Blatt 2. Thermal use of the underground - Ground source heat pump systems). The borehole used for a GRT can be used afterwards as a geothermal exchanger.

A GRT is used for practical comparison of theoretical data since performing such test allows us to know the effective thermal conductivity (describes the heat transfer through conductivity in the subsoil) and the thermal resistance of the probe (indicates what should be the thermal resistance between the collector circuit and the subsoil for dissipation of power), with the aim of optimising the system and to size a field of geothermal probes. Also, when comparing the GRT with a soil samples analysis completed in a laboratory, it is observed that the measurements made of undisturbed soil conditions are not comparable with those affected by factors found in usual geothermal probe conditions like filling material, technical quality of the probe, its installation process thus as the effect of the phreatic level.

The process of a GRT is as follows:

- (1) Before the GRT is started, the undisturbed ground temperature must be determined. This can be measured by measuring the temperature of circulated water through the borehole without heating over 20 minutes. This is allowing enough time to see the temperature stabilised. In order to do so, a heat transfer fluid is circulated at a certain velocity with the aim of filling the probe circuit 1.5 times. The mean fluid temperature corresponds to the undisturbed mean temperature along the borehole.
- (2) After this initial 20-minute-long measurement, the next step is to switch on the heater and the monitoring system. During the test, the heat transfer into the ground surrounding the borehole is essentially radial and relatively constant along the borehole. The 36 to 48 hours test starts and the heat transfer fluid is gradually warmed up by circulating it through immersion heaters. Temperature data are provided by two temperature sensors at the top of the borehole and heating power applied is controlled and collected during the process. Hence, the average thermal conductivity can be obtained.

In hybridGEOTABS project, significant improvements in this process have been achieved, by executing more developed, upgraded and detailed GRTs than usual. In a traditional GRT, only flow and return temperatures at the top of the borehole are measured, while an EGRT (Enhanced Geothermal Response Test) enable us to obtain a temperature profile at all the levels of the borehole, measuring accurately how the temperature changes with depth as a function of the flow and the

thermal stress of the borehole. The interpretation of the results of an EGRT allows to calculate the effective thermal conductivity and the thermal resistance of the boreholes along the depth of the geothermal probe, centimetre per centimetre. With this data it is possible to find where the optimal areas of the sub-soil are and, even, to know the influence of the different materials or groundwater in the case that these exists.

The process of a EGRT is as follows:

- (1) Before the EGRT is started, the undisturbed ground temperature must be determined. This can be measured by measuring the temperature of water through the borehole without heating over 12 hours. To obtain this data, one sensor runs all along the length of the geothermal probe. The mean fluid temperature corresponds to the undisturbed mean temperature along the borehole.
- (2) After this initial 12-hours-long measurement, the next step is to switch on the heater and the monitoring system. The 48 hours test starts. To make a difference with respect to the traditional GRT, ten different sensors run all along the length of the geothermal probe while a 130-meter-long heating element heats the heat transfer fluid. During the EGRT, temperature of the ground was obtained, depending on the depth during the heating-controlled process. Hence, the thermal conductivity at all the levels of the subsoil can be obtained.

The required heat exchanger is longer when conductivity has been calculated from engineering guidelines than when has been determined by the GRT, due to the oversizing that used to be done for the estimation of conductivity. Similarly, the required exchanger length is higher when conductivity has been obtained from GRT than when has been determined by the EGRT because it is possible to optimize the length of the boreholes and finally the total meters to drill for the borehole field are lower.

After EGRTs executed during the project, we can affirm that pre-engineering sizing leads to a reduction of 4-10% of investment in the borehole field performing a GRT and a reduction of 14-16% performing an EGRT. That means, an EGRT has led to a 7% investment reduction compared to the GRT.

Through an EGRT, areas of high conductivity have been found along the depth, and together with the study through Earth Energy Designer (EED) software has allowed the optimization of the global geothermal system. By performing an EGRT it is possible to analyse the complete information about the subsoil and decide the best solution considering all the project conditions, always optimizing the number of meters to drill. EGRT leads to savings in investment costs, enhancing the sizing of the borehole field, increasing the security of supply and the optimum functioning of the HVAC installation.

Since low enthalpy geothermal energy (also called "shallow geothermal application" at depths less than 400 m) is an efficient and abundant renewable energy that can be found almost everywhere in the world, it is logical to investigate better methods to size the system accurately. Field studies were carried out within this project to verify the importance of the conductivity calculation along a geothermal borehole for its correct sizing and economic advantages it offers in this project.

With the conductivities obtained with an EGRT and simulations carried out with EED software, the optimal configuration of the geothermal boreholes can be decided. The EGRT allows the design team

to make an informed decision on the length of each necessary borehole and reduce the need for unnecessary meters of drilling, therefore reducing the total investment cost of the geothermal installation.

Influence of thermal balance. Influence of cooling dominated building

The starting point for information about energy behaviour of the building (kW and kWh heating and/or cooling) is the thermal load analysis or similar document carried out by a qualified professional for the site in question. This may need to be adjusted by any particular requirements of the client not covered by the exercise. For temperate and northerly latitudes, the requirement is usually dominated by heating. At lower latitudes, there will often be cooling as well as heating requirements. The basic result sought is the net annual energy (kWh/yr) to be supplied by or rejected into the geothermal collector.

Thermal imbalance is determined by the heat extracted from the soil in winter and by the heat rejected into the soil in summer and has to be evaluated from studying the building loads and geothermal heat pump operation and performance. In order to simulate the soil temperature, the design heating load, the design cooling load, and borehole number for the GSHP should be chosen based on the building loads simulated previously. Keeping the balance of cooling and heating load is of great significance for maintaining an efficient and stable operation of the heat pump and for the design of the geothermal field. If the soil thermal imbalance could be reduced, the geothermal field size could be reduced as well and COP/EER of the heat pump could be improved. So, it means a lower investment cost and a good efficiency of the heating and cooling system.

Consequences of thermal imbalance are: (1) Increasing number, spacing or depth of boreholes which increases the initial investment and occupied area. EGRT developed in D6.2 is one of the main important achievements about borefield predesign optimization; (2) Installing bivalent heat/cold energy sources that is generally applied for the peak load, while the geothermal heat pump only provides base load for heating/cooling to keep the soil temperature balanced.

The heat/cold calculation principles are presented as follows.

Cooling season. Heat rejected into the soil in summer:

- $Q_{\text{rejected}} = Q_{\text{cooling}} + P_{\text{cooling}}$

Heating season: Heat extracted into the soil in winter:

- $Q_{\text{absorbed}} = Q_{\text{heating}} - P_{\text{heating}}$

where $Q_{\text{cooling}}/Q_{\text{heating}}$ -heat supplied/removed to/from the indoor building (kW) and $P_{\text{heating}}/P_{\text{cooling}}$ - work consumed by the heat pump (kW).

It is worth noting that for the same quantity of cooling load and heating load required by the building, the heat rejected to the borefield is larger than the heat absorbed from the borefield. It means that if imbalance is a crucial aspect in heating dominated buildings, it is still more important in cooling dominated buildings with much higher heat rejection than heat extraction. In these cases, the soil

temperature increases significantly because heat rejected into the soil could easily exceed the thermal diffusion ability of the subsoil.

By designing hybrid heating/cooling production systems for buildings with the hybrid GEOTABS concept, it is possible to reduce the soil imbalance ratio effectively, to slow the decrease/increase of soil temperatures, and to mitigate the problem of soil heat/cold accumulation. As assisted heat/cold sources are applied in different kinds of buildings, we can discriminate between heating and cooling dominated buildings.

In heating dominated buildings, solar energy is used as a supplementary heat source to supply heat during daytime, and ground heat exchangers supply heat during night, which reduces the heat extracted from the soil. Even better if excess solar energy during the day is stored in the ground for heating at night. The ground temperature could remain stable with the assistance of the solar collectors, which increases the coefficient of performance of the heat pump. Also, another possibility is the use of an air-source heat compensator integrated within the geothermal heat pump. An air unit compensator works together with the geothermal heat pump unit to provide heat compensation or domestic hot water. Or it could operate directly to heat the water when the air temperature is high. Other possibilities could be a gas boiler or biomass. These variants are discussed in 2.4 of this document.

In cooling dominated buildings, the geothermal heat pump can also be integrated with the same air unit compensator, in this case for cooling compensation. Also, the integration of a cooling tower, an absorption chiller or geothermal heat pumps with heat recovery are ideal solutions too but all of them remain largely unknown, overall a real technical analysis of them is lacking: in terms of soil temperature variation, thermal imbalance ratio, and soil temperature increase. In this kind of buildings, thermal imbalance problem is inescapable due to heat accumulation after long-term operation and these solutions can contribute to the maintenance of soil thermal balance.

In a hot summer region at the South of Europe where the annual cooling load is higher than the heating load, thermal imbalance is usually a problem. The design standard of the ground heat exchanger is finally determined according to cooling loads in summer, which represents heat accumulation. In this way, the accumulation of unbalanced heat could exceed the thermal diffusion ability of soil and subsoil temperature gradually increases.

Influence on location EU of reference borehole sizing

For borehole sizing there is a set of technical standards. For shallow geothermal systems in general, technical standards exist in those countries where the market has already developed such as Austria, Germany, Sweden and Switzerland. The main administrative and licensing barriers applying to geothermal works are well covered by the overall EN standards.

- German standard VDI 4640
- Dutch standard ISSO 73
- Spanish standard UNE 100715-1
- Swiss standard SIA 384/6
- UK standard MIS 3005

- Austrian standard ÖNORM M 7753 Heat pumps with electrically driven compressors for direct expansion, ground coupled
- SE Normbrunn-07 Drilling for water wells and energy

These national standards are generally in the local language except VDI 4640 which is available in both German and English. The most advanced and comprehensive national Standard is the German document VDI 4640. This German standard focuses especially on the GSHP system as a whole (mainly in part 2), in contrast to the others that focus more on discrete elements of the system.

European countries have adopted all relevant EN standards (especially VDI 4640) into national standards and legal regulations, licensing/certification of companies and persons... are based on them. There is an important general consensus about borehole sizing in Europe.

BIM

Most important borehole sizing software programs in the market are based on parameter studies with a numerical simulation model resulting in analytical solutions of the heat flow with several combinations for the borehole pattern and geometry (g-functions). Those g-functions depend on the spacing between the boreholes at the ground surface and the borehole depth. Calculation of brine temperatures is done for monthly heat/cool loads. Databases provide the key ground parameters (thermal conductivity and specific heat) as well as properties of pipe materials and heat carrier fluids.

So, although calculation process is very complex, only monthly heat/cool loads and geological features of the ground surface are input data.

Geological features of the ground surface are fixed for the building site. But data of monthly heat/cool loads are depended of the design of the building (use, size, orientation, building envelope, heating/cooling distribution system...). So, talking about integration and collaborative work, finally, the design of the building is going to size the borefield in a BIM environment. So, any change in building design will impact the size and cost of the borefield and, in this way, it will allow to integrate this important factor in the decision tree of the total construction project analysis.

2.2.2. Heat Pump (HP)

Pre-engineering of heat pumps is possible in a limited way. As heat pumps are a mature technology and available in the market in a large power range of prefabricated units, the pre-engineering contains the following topics.

First of all, the heat pump size should be determined. To ease the decision making process a pre-design tool has been developed in WP 2 (D.2.1)

Once the heat pump power is selected, the design supply water temperature is decided. This parameter is function of the applicable circuits, with corresponding temperature levels. The heat pump can work in different heating modes:

- The heat pump is only in charge of the low TABS-baseload heating, this will lead to the highest efficiencies due to the lowest supply temperature.
- The heat pump covers all circuits, both ultra-low TABS heating, but also secondary heat emission system e.g. FCU or oversized radiators in hybridGEOTABS. In this way the energy share of the heat pump is maximised, but often with a lower efficiency.

To help engineering offices in this pre-engineering phase, chapter 2 of this deliverable includes some hydraulic concepts as a starting point for final, detailed engineering work.

Knowing the technical details of the heat pumps at supply water temperature lower than the obligated 35°C and 55°C supply temperature makes it easier for engineering offices to select the proper heat pump. This topic has been discussed in D 6.2.

Finally, since the beginning of this millennium, BIM is starting to gain interest in different phases of construction proces. In the available software packages it is possible to insert a heat pump model. The available details of the heat pump model differs from manufacture to manufacturer. The basic geometrical sizes are always available. A more detailed model includes efficiencies and thermal power are available. As there wasn't a uniform European test standard (EN14511, EN255, Eurovent,...) before the implementation of the European Directive, not all manufacturers made this information available. One stage further is the hydraulic and electric interaction from the heat pump model to the rest of the model. Finally it is possible to add maintenance guidelines available in the model.

For the processing of BIM it was intended to use the German VDI 3805 in the past. In the future, the international standard ISO 16757 will be used for worldwide exchange of product data. ISO 16757 replaces the German VDI 3805. Both standards contain the following components:

- 3 LOG (Level of graphic)
- approx. 150 properties / product classes

This standard will include all above mentioned topics, not only geometrical sizes, but also efficiencies and maintenance guidelines.

2.2.3. TABS

Pre-engineering of TABS for prefabricated solutions commonly consider the structure, property and the most suitable construction methods. This applies to modularized TABS particularly. Given the industrialization experiences, the following solutions have been developed and are available [8]:

(a). The installation of modules in precast concrete structures is a widely used method. The modular design enables the concrete element manufacturer to supply the precast parts with fully integrated concrete core activation to the site on time.

(b). Another precast floor construction is the hollow core slab. This type of precast slab constructed from pre-stressed concrete comes with voids of tubular shape along the full length of the slab. This characteristic of hollow core slab makes it lighter than the typical slab construction, thus providing advantages of reduced material and transportation costs, as well as fast installation, see Figure 3-12

Figure 3-12: Precast hollow core slab, equipped TABS [8]

Other solutions for pre-engineering also considers different concrete and floor types:

(a). In order to overcome the natural weakness that concrete has in relation to tension, post-tension slab can be used for the length of the floor. This method is called pre-stressing and means that the slab has been pre-stressed to increase its strength, see Figure 3-13

Figure 3-13: TABS are installed in the center of the floor [8]

[b]. Pre-designed TABS modules are also suitable for installation in filigree slab floors as they allow for fast installation. In this case, the mesh carriers, which normally serve as spacers for the upper reinforcement layer, are shortened so that they can carry the medium reinforcement layer and the TABS modules, see Figure 3-14.

Figure 3-14: TABS modules placed on mesh carriers [8]

2.2.4. Controller

The development of white-box models for MPC purpose takes the most time of the whole MPC implementation. Therefore, in the case of new buildings, it is required to develop the white-box models already during the design phase of the building.

During the design phase of the building, the models allow to investigate possible limits of the energy system, respectively MPC controllers and provide feedback to designers in order to change some design values of TABS and ventilation system.

The interface between BMS and MPC must be agreed upon during the design phase of the building. The following issues must be confirmed with the BMS engineers during the design phase:

- server/local based MPC
- communication interface (Modbus, OPC server, web API, etc.)
- read/write variables (the list of minimum read/write signals is stated in Controller3.1.4

The models are refined and adapted to design changes during the construction phase of the building. Therefore, a lot of simulations need to be performed in this phase, which allow to:

- set suitable MPC parameters (temperature comfort bands, cost-function, hard-constraints, solver etc.)
- investigate situations where MPC fails (not enough power, too high desired temperature, etc.)
- estimate operational costs and potential MPC savings

3. Integrating hybridGEOTABS efficiently into the building process

3.1. Description of the building process steps

Context:

Work Stages in a building project are defined in this section first in detail from the consortium designer and HVAC designer's point of view, and secondly on a higher level following the RIBA (Royal Institute of British Architects) Plan of Work. We will use this information to determine how and when the hybridGEOTABS solution can speed up the different studies and processes involved and tackle some challenges encountered by the project team members, whether it is a design or construction or a commissioning and handover issue.

Consortium designers' point of view:

The classical approach to a new construction project (called DBB for Design_Bid_Build), still most frequently applied, makes a clear distinction between the concept and design phase in order to translate the design in a clearly defined set of tender documents. The tender documents then tend to define what is needed in the project in a brand-neutral manner, in order to create a fair level market competition. After the tender stage, the contractors are assigned that take the responsibility to build the project and detail the design where needed according to the real equipment and material characteristics that are approved to be integrated into the project after compliance check with the tender files. This classical² early design phase of a project, integrating the technical energy and sustainability approach involves several key partners:

- Investor
- User (if the investor is not developing for the market but for a dedicated user)
- Architects
- Consultants/engineers (structural, MEPH, building physics), these can be design or concept oriented, or both). These parties are in some cases subcontracted by the architect, in others they are independent advisors/designers directly contracted by the investor or user.

In this classical approach we would like to simplify the configuration by assigning energy and technical related domains to a party called **TE**, architectural and structural responsibilities to **AS** and investor and user position to a party called **OWN** (owner).

The split incentive (capex/opex) is not neglected, but is more and more merged by the impact of the operational and LCC aspects on the value of the asset, and as such affects the goals and KPIs of the investment. The degree of importance of the operational energy and environmental costs is mainly determined by policy makers, who can change the regulatory framework, but also energy prices and taxes to shift towards clean solutions, and raise awareness towards the end users of the buildings. The typical phases in this process, once **OWN** has established a program definition, can be classified as follows:

² In more recent procedures the construction and operational partners might be involved earlier in the process (eg DB (design and build, similar to turnkey), DBM (design, build and maintain), DBFM (design, build, finance and maintain) DBFMO (the operation is included as well). In the latter case the energy operating cost is rarely included, since the user behaviour has a major impact on it.

- Concept & feasibility (link WP2)
- pre-design (link WP2)
- final-design (also called detailed design)
- tender
- sale
- construction (incl detailed construction design) (link WP3)
- hand over
- commissioning (link WP3)
- maintenance & operation (link WP3)

Figure 4-1: Building process stages: consortium designers' stages grouped into the RIBA stages

The RIBA Plan of Work:

Next to this experience-based Work stages' classification, it is worth describing a new construction project with a higher level and mostly theoretical approach, based on the RIBA plan of work. First developed in 1963, for half a century the RIBA Plan of Work has been the definitive UK model for the building design and construction process, also exercising significant influence on an international stage.

In this description the classic RIBA Plan of Work, as shown on the left hand side in Figure 4-1, revisited and updated in 2013 to take into account modern design and construction processes is followed. This Plan of Work is generally accepted and used around Europe, with some variation or adaption per country. It is used here to describe all the different stages the project team must go through before the building is in operation.

RIBA Stage 0 – Strategic definition

This stage strategically appraises and defines the project before a detailed design brief is created, for example in the context of sustainability, performing a refurbishment and/or extension may be more appropriate than a new build. It serves to identify client's Business Case. A strategic brief including core project requirements is produced.

RIBA Stage 1 - Preparation and Brief

This typically includes feasibility studies, surveys of the existing site or building and initial cost appraisals. It includes quality objectives and desired project outcomes, sustainability aspirations, a budget for the project as well as other parameters or constraints

The client will develop an Initial Project Brief and commission a Feasibility Studies as well as necessary Site Information studies/assessment (geological survey, etc.)

It also involves the 'preparation tasks' such as assembling the project team and defining each party's roles and responsibilities.

RIBA Stage 2 – Concept Design

This stage is also commonly called "pre-design".

Here, the initial concept design is produced in line with the Initial Project Brief established in stage 1, and presented to the client. It is the first time the Client will see what the architect is proposing.

During this stage, the design team is required to prepare a Concept Design which include outline proposals for structural design, building services systems, outline specifications and preliminary cost Information (not detailed, a ball park figure per trade for instance heating, cooling, plumbing, electrical etc. It should be ca. 15% to 25% accurate).

A Final Project Brief is also ideally issued by the Owner.

RIBA Stage 3 – Developed Design

This stage is also commonly called "detailed design".

The concept design from stage 2 is further developed to meet the client's requirements in terms of liveability and how they propose to use the spaces. Once completed, the planning drawings and documents will be drafted and submitted to the local authority for approval.

Once approved, the building services and structural engineers design will begin development and enable a closer cost and project budget analysis.

RIBA Stage 4 Technical Design

This phase includes the Tendering (bid) process. Traditionally the construction industry was following the Design-Bid-Build (DBB) Process, clearly separating the design and construction duties and teams with a bidding process in the middle. However, the trend in the industry is to use a Design and Build or Design-Build (DB) procurement route, with the project being run under one single contract. The budget is defined from an earlier stage. The main contractor is involved from the start of the project to manage the design as well as the construction, this can lead to a more integrative and faster (therefore more cost efficient) process particularly on large commercial projects.

During technical design, the structural and building services packages are further refined allowing for any specialist sub-contractor design to be carried out, such as renewable energies.

The specification documents are produced. This package is best thought of as a strict guidance for how the building goes together, and will contain every essential information to enable the contractor/builder to build the required proposed design.

In the case of a Design-Bid-Build procurement, at the end of this stage, traditionally, the project will be issued to the chosen group of contractors/builders for tender (normally a four to six-week period).

RIBA Stage 5 Construction

It involves offsite manufacturing (for instance prefabricated TABS / pre-tense slabs) and onsite construction in accordance with the construction programme. Design queries as they arise from site (subcontractors) must be resolved by the design team.

During this stage the building is constructed in line with the drawings and information produced in the previous stages, and as described here will often be administered by the architect, helping to ensure a smooth construction process.

The “as-built” drawings and system manual information are produced.

RIBA Stage 6 Handover and Close-out

Commissioning work occurs during this stage. This stage facilitates the successful handover of the newly completed building, and involves the inspection of the completed works and the resolution of any defects witnessed during commissioning performance tests.

During close-out the “as-built” drawings are updated (also called revision drawings)

RIBA Stage 7 In Use

The building goes under several checks and fine-tuning of the systems in the first months and maybe first year of being in operation. It involves a post-occupancy evaluation, covering the projects performance, outcomes and development, additional commissioning duties such as seasonal commissioning of the systems (for instance when the building is first occupied in the middle of the summer, the heating plant must be commissioned in winter again). It is essentially an aftercare service and the opportunities to optimise the potential (in terms of running hours, system efficiency, etc.) of the systems installed.

Alignment:

Logically, the two approaches show similarities as the descriptions focus on the same process. However RIBA was intended to focus more on the architects responsibilities as the principal designer, and therefore further refining towards the hybridGEOTABS challenge is less obvious, but it is good to understand how the two classification approaches fit in together.

Stage 0 and 1 (Strategic definition, Preparation and Brief) are content wise related to the definition and preparation stage of a project, often delivered by OWN and consulting architectural planners, not necessarily the architects that engage into the real design process. It refers to the elaboration of what is further called the project program. This program is used as a kick off document for the conceptual and operational designers mission, through a competition or a contract specification.

RIBA Stage 2 – Concept Design is merging the concept & feasibility, in a pre-design phase as mentioned in the first classification. Whereas for the lead designer this merge is plausible, for the designers of the underlying disciplines it is clarifying more at what moment the intermediate decision to further elaborate an innovative and integrated energy concept is launched, and all concerned designers (AS & TE) are aware of this exercise. In fact too often it is seen that the structural engineer, as well as the architect, did not absorb the design impact of geothermal source planned near or under the building as well as the TABS in the concrete on their discipline in order to interact accordingly.

RIBA Stage 3 developed design and 4 technical design are describing the final design and the (sub)tender phase from the first classification.

The sales phase is not specifically mentioned in RIBA, since it tries to create one description for the design-bid-build as well as the design-build procedure. However, for clear understanding of the hybridGEOTABS related component industries, this is practically the sales starting moment for these suppliers, as in general from this moment on the HVAC subcontractors are appointed, and the business partner for the aforementioned industries has a clear identity.

The stages Construction and Handover are similar, however the commissioning mentioned in RIBA is content wise rather an in-depth compliance check prior to handover.

The consortium designers perceive commissioning duties to be a series of third party checks of all delivered installations, plans, operational aspects in the first year of use. The third party (commissioner) is independent from the designer and simply has to check coherence of files and reality and report any flagged issues to the Owner, without any performance improvement measures or of adapting the HVAC systems towards better operation, since that responsibility is allocated to the designers and the contractors.

The in-use stage of RIBA accords more to the so called commissioning in the first year of operation and the maintenance & operation phase.

Concept & feasibility:

In this first stage, AS and TE elaborate the project program of the OWN towards a layout and geometry of the building. In an integrated approach they start together from a white sheet, discuss the translation of the OWN ambitions and functionalities within their disciplines, add their experiences and look at the potential of the location in different aspects and merge them to a first conceptual design. The integrated approach is the most enhanced creative collaboration in the design field, it requires an intensive collaboration and cross-disciplinary discussions and meetings, but delivers tailor made solutions to the site, expectations, architectural multi-domain criteria and budgets. For this purpose, this upfront work requires the most experienced, dedicated and collaborative open mind profiles of the different design experts. They will include innovative, state of the art and feasible aspects in the project that for sure need to be further evaluated, defined and assessed in the course of the project.

In practice there is still a tendency to weaken this approach to a leading idea of the AS, the 'master' concept on building level, and integrate the knowledge of TE, 'the slave' to find a suiting energy and technical solution for the given AS idea. The AS concept constrains the TE concept, often disregarding the weight factors put forward in the project program. This suboptimal integration is found in projects where the upfront expert capacity is not available and TE steps in the process when the buildings main features are already consolidated. Changing these is then logically regarded as a step back.

Integrated approach or not, at the end of this phase AS and TE should deliver in most practice environments:

- AS sketches and floor layouts, positioning of the building in the neighbourhood, and possible variations to regard in the further process. Attached or integrated are the first structural principles, consequences and constraints. The note motivates the direction and choices at the core of the project and how this complies to the program of OWN.
- A technical and energy approach note and first sketches, putting forward what systems can be applied, motivating a TE designer's order of preference, and attaching a short SWOT to each of the variations. This is often illustrated to a degree that OWN understands the basic principles of the proposals. The concept of TE should be a feasible combination with the AS concept, OWN needs to be convinced that AS and TE deliver an integrated or compatible concept.
- A budget estimation for the main concept and the variations suggested. These are merely based on lump sum and typical cost/m² calculations (feedback from AS and TE references or market study, built examples, or more detailed bottom up studied quantification if none of above is available, eg for highly innovative approaches).
- A first draft of a design and construction work schedule is produced.

It is important to stress that this early phase could be pre-contractual, e.g. in architectural design terms belongs to the competitions³ phase, meaning that this work is delivered with a (partly or fully) financial risk to the designers, which tends to limit the invested efforts.

³ Competition, or rather a purchase or tender procedure for DB, DBM, DBFM, DBFMO is applied as well, in public and private markets. In this case the AS and TE can negotiate about fee arrangements for the pre-contractual efforts, but still too often a no cure no pay settlement applies. It is obvious that this situation often leads to proven 'off the shelf' solutions, that minimise design effort instead of maximising project performance (unless the purchase or tender documents clearly state a weighted criteria procedure, judged by renowned expert panels, which is often not the case).

If this phase is post-contractual, the AS (and TE) have regular meetings with OWN to align, give more explanation of the concept and the progress and consolidate common ground. In this case the deliverables are mainly a synthesis, enabling the high level decision of OWN to give green light for the further stages.

The feasibility elaboration of a concept in this phase for TE focuses mainly on:

- Can the concept meet the performance criteria put forward by OWN and TE in terms of environmental objectives, comfort,...
- Can the concept be integrated in the architectural layout, is it achievable? This is further verified in the pre-design stage.
- Does the budget (capex/opex) allow this concept? Is there room for integrated (AS & TE) cost optimization? This is further verified in the pre-design stage.

In this exercise, as mentioned, the preferred concept is compared with competing or varying concepts.

At the end of this phase, OWN should be able to decide to continue elaboration of this project/concept proposal in the pre-design stage.

Pre-design:

In this second stage, AS and TE elaborate the practical design integration, as in the feasibility stage (former project feedback) assumptions were applied and need to be verified. The pre-design focuses on the sizing and the spatial integration (technical spaces, shafts, practical barriers (e.g. ground source limitations)) in the project. Also the budget is verified on the basis of the preliminary sizing. In this stage there is still interaction (room for improvement) between AS and TE in order to adapt their respective designs, e.g. insulation level and glazing characteristics, technical space and distribution allocation, intensity of sun shading, principles of interior integration details.

A room by room assessment towards final design occurs at the end of this stage, when the above mentioned interaction is nearing completion.

Also to finalise this stage, an update on the feasibility study is often provided, especially when important derivations to the concept assumptions have occurred in this process.

Deliverables of this phase provided by TE consist of:

- Synthesis of the concept variations and the preferred concept put forward.
- Note illustrating and commenting on all supply, distribution and emission systems
- Floor by floor elaboration plans of the integration of the TE concept, sizing of spaces and shafts, distribution pathways, indication of interior and exterior impact, one or more typical rooms elaborated with technical features, typical detailing of integration issues.
- More detailed investment cost estimation, based on equipment chapter approach.
- If relevant, an update on performance criteria assessment (updated feasibility).
- Short risk analysis of cost, timing, ...

Deliverables of the AS are focused on further elaboration of the plans and the cost estimation.

In this stage AS and/or TE or an external consultant also provide first assessments of sustainability/energy performance certification schemes if applicable (BREEAM, LEED, Minergie, HQE, DGNB, EPB, PH assessment...).

At the end of this stage the coordinated verification of the different design disciplines, the verification of budgets, of targeted performance is achieved. This enables the OWN to decide to start the final design.

Final-design (also called detailed design):

The final design phase focuses on detailing the former stages to plans and files that enable contractors and all their suppliers to elaborate accurate quotes in the tender stage. As these quotes are preferably consolidated and only subject to minor changes in the following processes the plans have to be very accurate detailed coordinated plans, detailed calculations and sizing (AS & TE). Also the detailed investment cost estimation, based on a bill of quantities, is finalized with an accuracy that is targeting a maximum deviation of the purchase cost of 5%. Only if serious deviations from the pre-design budget is noticed the design needs to be reviewed or adapted.

Deliverables of this phase provided by TE consist of:

- Detailed coordinated plans, floor by floor and sizing based on calculation results
- Bill of quantities, detailed cost estimation
- Hydronic and aerolic schemes, basic control schemes
- Elevations and details illustrating the integration (in case no detailed 3D plans are completed in this phase (depending on the TE firm))
- Floor by floor elaboration plans of the integration of the TE concept, sizing of spaces

These are based on AS plans that achieve the same level of detail.

Remark:

In some markets (and in DB configurations) where performance contracting is more common, the detailed design of HVAC is often assigned to the HVAC contractor, and TE limits the work to the conceptual design or the pre-design. It leads to minimising the investment cost (or maximising the profit for the contractor) and, if not specified in the performances, leads to less attention to the operational aspects. This different incentives can lead to continuous confrontation between the supervising TE and the elaborating HVAC, that endangers the compliance of the delivered project with the early stage ambitions.

Tender:

The tender phase translates the final design in to market purchase documents. Technical quality descriptions, guidelines for construction, points of attention and constraints, timing and planning and juridical and administrative clauses are added as well as responsibilities during construction until final handover. These tender documents are afterwards used as contractual document to comply with, and added to the (sub)contractors final contract. The bids and offers are asked for a specified date, compared and advice is reported to the OWN in order to purchase the best offer, be it with or without further commercial negotiations in the sales phase.

Also the purchase criteria and their weighted impact are specified, since other criteria than the investment cost can be implemented depending on the public or private character of the project, and the purchase procedure decided upon between OWN, AS and TE. This can make added or innovative value of materials, post construction services, lifespan or maintenance characteristics, ... relevant in the sales stage.

Thus this is a stage to create relevance to concept-elaboration that show clear advantages not integrated in the investment cost.

Deliverables of this tender phase provided by TE consist of:

- Final design deliverables as mentioned above
- Extensive (brand-neutral) specifications of components, materials, and their expected performances (see also section 4.2)
- Administrative and legal obligations of the contract
- Purchase criteria, and if needed selection criteria for the contractor to comply with
- Detailed bill of quantities, enabling clear, detailed and comparative pricing by the competing companies
- Draft time planning of the global project
- After tendering, a complete comparative analysis of all the quotes received, according to the purchase criteria, dealing with the remarks and corrections of the competitors, with advice for further steps

Deliverables of this tender phase provided by competing HVAC contractors:

- Answers to all required information by the tender documents
- Remarks or corrections revealed by their offer study of the tender files

Sales:

The sales stage in this timeline is the moment of the finalization of the HVAC contract content. Independent of the followed procedure (DB or DBB) and even if the preferred contractor HVAC (further called HVAC) has already been predefined in a private procedure, the financial consequences of the design are now checked and consolidated. There is often a competition between contractors still running (DBB and in some cases DB), those competitors either are backed up by a purchase amongst suppliers and subcontractors or rely on their own experience and former project feedback. The latter procedure will count on later purchase of suppliers and subcontractors.

For this reason this should be the moment for the TE to ask and check material compliance, as this contract stage enables consolidation of choices.

If not, discussion on what material is compliant to the neutral descriptions and what is not remains a fundamental and recurring discussion throughout the construction process, disturbing it often and thus introducing errors and affecting the project planning. For example, not having closed the compliance discussion on borehole materials and execution procedures for a borehole field under the building have been witnessed to be a blocking issue to a degree that project planning pressure did lead to a change of thermal supply in the construction stage, disregarding the whole concept and design stage that has led to it.

The more detail specified in the sales stage and the (sub)contract, the smoother the control of timeplanning and quality during the construction, so parties should not hesitate to use the pre contractual sales stage to name components explicitly with brands and main features within the contract.

Deliverables of this sales phase provided by TE consist of:

- Contract annexes providing in the ideal case a list of agreed materials, subcontractors, adjustments related to remarks and suggestions of contractors in the tender phase, break-down of the final offer in quantities and unit prices, tender documents, ...

Deliverables of this sales phase provided by HVAC consist of:

- Final offer
- Signed contract incl annexes

Deliverables of this sales phase provided by OWN consist of:

- Signed contract incl annexes

Construction (including detailed construction design)

The construction stage starts with the detailed construction design of the HVAC installer, further detailing planning, material selection within the contract specification and tender documents, elaborating detailed and integrated plans based on these, detailed calculations if needed and submitting these for approval to TE and AS. They should work literally bottom up, to facilitate the progress of the integrated construction and anticipate on any coordination issues well in time. Specifically for hybridGEOTABS buildings, the integration of TABS and the borehole field are major points of focus.

Therefore hybridGEOTABS buildings need a HVAC contractor in the early stage of the construction, or at least the contractors that take the borehole field and the TABS in their mission.

The HVAC installer usually takes the lead, in close coordination with the building construction company, and is supervised by AS and TE. Preferably all interacting contractors (electrical, plumbing, interior, ...) should be known from now on to coordinate correctly, and decisions of OWN towards the effective use of the building that might interact should be identified and consolidated in parallel.

Meetings should primarily handle construction detailed design and coordination issues, construction quality issues and time planning issues.

Detailed elaboration of the HVAC control, and all interaction within the building management system (even if they should be predefined by the tender documents in the design stage) is needed ultimately 6 months before inhousing of the project. It can start however as soon as the detailed material selection has taken place. In most situations the control company is subcontracted by the HVAC contractor.

Although this is often disregarded, and the building control is rather initialized in a 'default' manner, control anticipation guarantees a better user satisfaction in the inhousing stage. No discussion that this anticipating approach is advantageous to all parties involved.

Hand over:

The hand over is the moment that OWN accepts the building as is, be it with a list of shortcomings or finalizations that are acceptable to be handled with in a defined further timeframe. The list should be taken very seriously, and is made by AS and TE after intensive control of the building. OWN should take time to add or in case remove remarks, since the hand over is contractual between OWN and contractors. The designers have an advisory role.

Specific attention is drawn on the fact that in most EU countries occupying the building is equal to accepting the building, so hand over should be handled explicitly beforehand. If parts of the work are postponed this should clearly be stated in documents between parties.

User interaction will affect the operation of the building from this moment on, which makes it more difficult to judge on responsibilities when problems are detected. For control installations, often a longer period of responsibility, or 'ownership' is defined (ideally already noted in the tender or sales stage). hybridGEOTABS buildings often need this agreement, since evaluation and finetuning of the control settings need different real operation modes.

AS and TE however inspect and detect all points of action that can be discovered in the handover phase. Legally, all faults that reasonably could not have been detected through visual and normal operational inspection remain the responsibility of the contractors.

Commissioning:

Commissioning focuses on facts and files.

It checks all occurring discrepancies between files, notes, contracts and the further elaboration, realization of the project towards what is really delivered and handed over to the OWN. The independent commissioning expert (third party) is appointed by the OWN, ideally much earlier in the project (end of detailed design) and has already been involved in the review of tenders, detailed construction documents, so he or she has a QA role also during the implementation of hybridGEOTABS systems for the OWN....LEED, BREEAM, DGNB guidance are all requesting a well prepared and through commissioning process. It has become very popular in the past decade, since performance assessments post of the occupancy phase have unveiled many differences between design and practice, disabling qualitative performance in operation and the assessment of it. Commissioning verifies the presence and announced standard compliance of calculations, pumps, valves, supply and emission components and their attributes. It also verifies if the targeted IEQ criteria are met in design conditions (if feasible).

Therefore it interacts with the post hand over fine tuning of the hybridGEOTABS control. Indeed, TE is still evaluating performances and control finetuning together with the control subcontractor, while the third party is performing compliance checks, also interfering in this post hand over process. As this third party for the HVAC commissioning is often a TE competitor, the interference can be a thin line of preventing knowledge transfer and profiling towards the OWN.

HybridGEOTABS buildings actually still require a one or two year follow up of the comfort and efficiency performance (energy use, borefield balance, ...) for the RBC control. This often reveals the necessity of adjustment or correction of sensor-, valve-, pump-, control-...settings or positioning for better operation. Often the concept is not thoroughly enough understood by the actors present, still default settings (e.g. by RBC programmers or TE project leaders) are noticed and adapted.

It is logic that the simultaneous presence of the third party can be a challenge in this finetuning process.

Maintenance:

The maintenance in most cases is handled by the contractor until the hand over is completed, and all the listed points have been dealt with. After this a maintenance contractor becomes involved, sometimes having a pure maintenance mission, sometimes also being responsible for the operation management to a certain degree. From this moment on, also this company faces a learning curve in hybridGEOTABS operational management. If adequate expertise is missing, often the actions after complaints of users, whatever the cause may be, are translated by adapting the operation maximally to the secondary system, since the staff of the maintenance company is well acquainted with this more conventional system. As a result, the risk appears that comfort is weighted far more heavy than clean energy performance on a yearly base, ground balance, energy use...

Only periodical expert audits, OWN awareness, or in-use commissioning can in these cases 'refresh' the fine-tuned operation of the building...under the condition that the involved experts master the knowledge of hybridGEOTABS dynamics.

In a renovation context the same stepwise approach is noticed. Some differences are observed however:

- As part of the building is integrated in the resulting renovated building, the integration feasibility has a higher weight in the early design process.
- Often the leading building renovation contractor subcontracts all other involved companies.
- TABS are mainly achieved by integrating pipes in the screed (if replaced or added) or in the ceilings. Boreholes can be drilled in the immediate neighbourhood of the building, in some cases they have been drilled through the existing floor slabs.

Going through the description of the whole process, it becomes clear that many different management, design and construction parties are involved. All of these are interacting somewhere in the design, construction or the use phase of the building. Therefore instructions and information needs to be provided in time, comprehensive to the receivers of it (thus differentiated) and clearly stating the interaction with each ones core activities.

3.2. Specification of key system components

Specifications constitute, besides plans and bills of quantities, the most important document of the final design phase in the most commonly applied building process (Design Bid Build). Specifications are usually annexed to the contract between the contracting authority (investor) and the contractor. As such, they become legally binding for both contracting parties. Therefore, it is understood that the quality of specifications can have a significant impact on the development of the construction phase of the build process.

In order to facilitate the writing of specifications, the consortium has prepared a set of generic specification templates of key system components of a hybridGEOTABS building. These specifications can be found in **Annex 2** of this report.

The prepared generic specification templates have been prepared for the following key system component groups:

- 01 Heat pumps and chillers
- 02 Dry coolers
- 03 Ground (geothermal) heat exchangers
- 04 Plate heat exchangers
- 05 Thermally activated building structures (TABS)
- 06 Fan coils
- 07 Electronic variable air volume (VAV) controllers
- 08 Buried horizontal geothermal pipes
- 09 Solar thermal collectors
- 10 Control and automation system
- 11 Energy meters

In each group, a series of individual specification templates has been prepared for system components that are characteristic for hybridGEOTABS buildings. Common components such as pumps, pipes, valves, etc. have not been included because they are widely specified in conventional buildings; hence, a typical design office shall normally be in a possession of necessary specification templates.

The group 01 heat pumps and chillers includes a broad range of different equipment types, ranging from air/water to water/water units. Apart from chillers and heating only heat pumps, reversible heat pumps and multifunctional units (for simultaneous production of heated and chilled water) are also included.

The group 02 on dry coolers includes the description of the most commonly encountered type of a dry cooler - table type.

The group 03 on geothermal heat exchangers includes specification templates of a vertical U-tube geothermal heat exchanger, prefabricated manifold chambers and geothermal response tests.

The group 04 on plate heat exchangers includes specification templates for brazed and gasketed plate heat exchangers.

The group 05 on thermally activated buildings structures includes a specification types for two most common types of embedded pipe systems of a thermally activated concrete core, i.e. system with in situ installed pipes and system with prefabricated TABS pipe modules composed or pipes attached to wire mesh plates. A specification template of a TABS manifold is also included.

The group 06 on fan coils includes specification templates of some of the most commonly encountered fan coils, as well as a template of a fan-assisted radiator.

The group 07 on electronic variable air volume (VAV) controllers includes a specification template for round and rectangular VAV controller, eventually supplemented with a sound attenuator.

The group 08 on buried horizontal geothermal pipes includes a template of PE flexible pipes normally used to link manifolds with vertical geothermal heat exchangers and the building installation.

The group 09 on solar thermal collectors includes specification templates of flat plate and evacuated tube solar thermal collectors.

The group 10 discusses control and automation systems. The first part provides templates for imposing quality control of the building process with the goal of bridging the quality gap between design intent and measured system performance. The second part concerns rule-based control (RBC) and provides templates for the specification of the control sequence of pump in the primary ground source heat exchanger loop and the control of a TABS manifold serving a thermally activated concrete core zone. The third part concerns model predictive control (MPC) and provides a template for a model predictive control of a TABS manifold serving a thermally activated concrete core zone. Additionally, a template for a building automation controller is also provided.

The group 11 on energy meters includes a specification template for heat meters.

3.3. The building process: challenges and solutions for hybridGEOTABS

To increase the share of hybridGEOTABS buildings in the EU building market, the key challenges of concept need to be solved or dealt with. In this section the challenges encountered today in the various stages of the building process, are identified. They are organised in Table 1 according to the 10 *building process stages* as identified by the consortium designers (see Figure 4-1). For each challenge, the *key actor(s)* are mentioned, that are the people who are dealing with this challenge, and are thus the people that should be aware of the challenge and the possible solution(s). For each challenge a level of *importance* is estimated, that is 'how important is this challenge in the realisation of hybridGEOTABS', from level 1 (minor), via level 2 (average) to level 3 (major). The *solutions* developed in this project to deal with some of these challenges, and to speed up the various studies and processes in a building process, are also summarised.

During the conceptual stage, the challenges are related to the 'new' or 'innovative' character of this concept. hybridGEOTABS is not widely known and applied yet, so its qualities and benefits need to be validated, assessed and documented. Via promotion activities building owners, investors, architects and HVAC-designers discover the concept, see the benefits it may bring them, and consider to use it in their projects. To enable the actors to gain confidence in the concept, demonstration activities and testimonies are important solutions.

In the feasibility and pre-design stages, the hybridity of the concept risks to become a barrier, because: how should a designer come to an assessment of the roles of the GEOTABS and secondary systems, which is needed to come to a cost-effective, comfortable and energy-efficient design? And even more, how to make this assessment without increasing the engineering costs already in this early stage, and loose the competition with more traditional HVAC-solutions on beforehand? It is in this stage that the newly developed hybridGEOTABS feasibility and pre-design tool and manual play the crucial role of providing a fair chance for hybridGEOTABS within the range of possible HVAC-design options.

To further guide the designers in the (detailed) design stage, example hydraulic schemes of hybridGEOTABS solutions are available, as well as guidelines for the good practice design and integration of the key components in the system. Also in this stage, the enhanced geothermal response test allows to further optimise the design of the geothermal borefield, which is the most expensive component of the hybridGEOTABS concept. The major challenge is the design of the MPC, the controller that will optimise the operation of the building. The set-up of this type of controllers (which is rather new in buildings) is not common practice today and experienced control designers are required for this task. In this project and parallel-running projects, a semi-automated toolchain is developed to allow for a more straightforward controller development to reduce the overall engineering costs going with the development of the MPC.

From the design stage onwards, 'integration' becomes even more key in order to realise the performance of hybridGEOTABS. The integration of the building features and key HVAC-components already studied in pre-design stage, is now taken further to an extensive integration up to the level of individual valves and pumps, hydraulic configurations and user interaction elements, to create degrees of freedom for the MPC to optimally control the building, and robustness to entrust the MPC with the vital task of providing thermal comfort in the building. This extensive integration of the

system also brings along a more intensive collaboration between various actors involved in the building process from the design, via the tendering, sale and construction to the operation and commissioning stage: HVAC-designers have to deal with implications of the control and therefore control companies (that often make the design and contracting of the control) are preferably involved from the design stage; contractors/installers and suppliers need to be accurate on even the 'small' HVAC-components they provide; the construction of the hybrid system requires an overall coordination and assigning of responsibilities; the operator and maintainer need to be familiar with the concept and control in order to keep its performance high. Clear and comprehensive information-exchange and interaction between the actors is therefore crucial, as well as a basic knowledge of hybridGEOTABS for every actor involved. Also more integrated project delivery systems may provide a suitable framework for constructing hybridGEOTABS buildings.

In the commissioning, operation and maintenance stage, the MPC provides the advantage of a time-efficient and effective commissioning, especially when compared to the high commissioning efforts observed with traditional controllers in hybrid systems today. During the installation of MPC many issues are already solved, because MPC does not allow 'faults'. And since the MPC interacts with many HVAC-components, it may (now or in the future) facilitate the quick detection of defects, faults and degeneration of components and thus assist in the achievement of high building performance on the long term. Finally, the hybridGEOTABS building is prepared for some challenges that will occur throughout its lifetime, such as dealing with interior renovations and reorganisations thanks to the free floor plans provided by TABS, and smart-grid readiness thanks to the MPC.

In summary, this section provides an overview of the challenges the hybridGEOTABS concept may encounter throughout the various stages of the building process. For some of them solutions are developed in this project, others remain future challenges for the knowledge centre and business development. One class of challenges are related to the inherent properties of the hybridGEOTABS concept, such as hybridity, MPC and integration, and for many of the most important challenges this project is providing solutions to a higher degree of readiness. Other challenges are related to the concept being rather new and innovative, i.e. challenges every concept encounters when going from a pioneer to a widespread solution. Finally, some challenges and solutions, such as BIM- and smart-grid readiness, correspond to the future challenges of the building sector as a whole in its transition to a more sustainable built environment.

Table 1: Challenges and solutions for hybridGEOTABS in the building process

Actor(s)	Challenge	Importance	Solution
CONCEPT			
Architect, HVAC designer, owner, investor	Actors are not aware about the existence of the hybridGEOTABS concept	3	The hybridGEOTABS knowledge centre promotes the concept (demonstration, dissemination, communication, training etc.) (WP7)
Architect, HVAC designer, owner, investor	Actors do not 'trust' the hybridGEOTABS concept is 'possible' or do not understand/believe its potential, including energy-efficiency and environmental potential.	3	The concept is demonstrated and validated in real-life buildings (WP4); the visibility of these buildings and results is increased (WP7)
Architect, HVAC designer, owner, investor	Actors are not aware of the architectural benefits of the hybridGEOTABS concept (reduced floor height, free rooftop, free and adaptable floor plans...)	2	The concept is demonstrated and validated in real-life buildings (WP4); the visibility of these buildings and results is increased (WP7, knowledge centre)
Architect, HVAC designer, owner, investor	Actors are hesitant about the high thermal comfort, IEQ and user acceptance achieved in TABS-buildings (e.g. due to misinformation, previous bad experiences)	3	The IEQ and effects on productivity/health are demonstrated and validated in real-life buildings and scientific research (WP4-5); results are disseminated (WP7)
Architect, owner, investor	Actors believe that embedded systems such as TABS have a higher life-cycle environmental impact and lower circularity character than other concepts.	2	Demonstrate the environmental impact of TABS (partially done in WP5); create a fair level of comparison e.g. include TABS in LCA-tools
Architect, HVAC-designer, owner, investor, maintainer	Actors believe that a hybrid solution leads to increased overall costs (engineering, investment, maintenance...) and only consider well-established solutions.	3	Demonstration buildings and examples of detailed cost documentation and testimonies are disseminated (WP4-7).
HVAC designer, architect, supplier/industry	Heavy-weight TABS is hard to realise in refurbishments and light-weight building structures	2	Development of PCM-integrated ceiling panels to replace the TABS (WP6)
FEASIBILITY			
HVAC designer, architect, owner, investor	Actors consider the feasibility study for hybridGEOTABS too complex (time consuming, expert knowledge) and thus too expensive, and only consider well-established solutions.	3	hybridGEOTABS feasibility and pre-design tool and manual are developed and disseminated: straightforward and easy-to-use (WP2)
HVAC designer, architect, owner, investor	Actors do not believe hybridGEOTABS is a suitable solution for their building (e.g. typology, climate...)	2	hybridGEOTABS feasibility and pre-design tool allows to assess the feasibility for many types of buildings in the building stock (WP2)

HVAC designer, architect, owner, investor	Actors believe that hybridGEOTABS leads to increased costs (e.g. design, investment, maintenance)	3	Cost-estimations and comparison of costs with traditional solutions are included in the hybridGEOTABS feasibility and pre-design tool and manual (WP2); focus on long term benefits in terms of LCC and payback periods Awareness raising, training to sell the hybridGEOTABS concept as one complete solution, where integration is key to achieve the performance. Continued development and market-pushing of the MPC to make the entire concept available.
HVAC designer, architect, owner, investor	Actors choose for a part of the hybridGEOTABS solution and risk to receive suboptimal performance in operational stage.	3	

PRE-DESIGN

HVAC designer, architect	The architectural implications of hybridGEOTABS were not foreseen in the architectural concept (e.g. acoustics, finishing materials...)	1	Dissemination / design manual (WP7)
HVAC designer, architect, owner, investor	The sizing of the key components is complex. Oversizing of the geothermal system leads to higher investment costs.	3	hybridGEOTABS feasibility and pre-design tool and manual allow optimal sizing of the key components, the hybrid solution prevents oversizing of geothermal system (WP2)
HVAC designer, architect, owner, investor	The actors do not believe in the importance and potential of MPC to control hybridGEOTABS		The feasibility and saving potential of MPC are demonstrated (WP3-4) and disseminated (WP7)

DESIGN

HVAC designer	The integration of components and optimisation of the detailed hydraulic design is more complex in hybrid systems.	2	Example hydraulic schemes help the designer to get started (WP6).
HVAC designer, investor, owner	Oversizing of the geothermal borefield leads to increased investment costs.	2	An Enhanced Geothermal Response Test (EGRT) that allows more accurate sizing of the GSHX is developed and validated (WP4-6).
HVAC designer, architect, assessor	The energy and environmental benefits of GEOTABS are not recognised or valued in the assessment schemes (e.g. EPBD, LCA-tools etc.)	1	Recommendations are included in the policy report (WP5). Knowledge centre follows-up and lobbies.
HVAC designer	The HVAC-designer is not used to deal with the effect and implications of the (MPC) control on his/her design, and to interact with the control designer/contractor in the design stage.	3	Awareness of the interactions is raised in the pre-design phase (WP2 tools). Control designers/contractors are engaged in the design phase, e.g. using more integrated design and build procedures. Knowledge centre (WP7) plays the role to increase the

Control designer/contractor	Design and set-up of MPC is complicated, resulting in high engineering costs.	3	knowledge of HVAC designers in the detailed design (e.g. certification or experience sheets of experienced HVAC-designers). Development of an MPC toolchain for design of the MPC reduces the engineering costs (WP3-4).
Control designer/contractor, HVAC designer, commissioner	The systems that are not controlled by the MPC require additional control systems and/or are controlled sub-optimally.	1	Solutions for controlling other systems (e.g. solar shading, ventilation) also by MPC can be developed. As BIM and its requirements are developing, like for other technologies, also the solutions for hybridGEOTABS will need to be developed. The modelling required for MPC can be assisted by BIM.
HVAC designer, architect, contractor, control designer/contractor	Linking of the system and MPC to BIM is challenging.	1	
TENDER			
HVAC designer, supplier, contractor	The tendering documents need to be detailed and complete to allow a high-quality offer	2	Good design and tender document examples help the designer to get started (WP6)
HVAC designer, owner, architect, contractors	The system integration aspect, important for realising the optimal performance, requires the actors to collaborate more intensively throughout the project stages and disciplines involved.	1-2	More integrated building contracting procedures such as DB, DBM etc. may provide a better framework for achieving the optimal performance.
SALE			
Supplier, contractor	Lack of knowledge of the system leads to suboptimal acquisition.	2	Knowledge centre (WP7) may work on awareness raising for salesmen and purchasers about the complexity of system integration and experience sheets for installers, suppliers. The contractor has to provide detailed information as required in the tender and the HVAC-designer performs compliance checking.
HVAC designer	Lack of material details and compliance checking in sales stage leads to recurring discussions and inadequate materials installed.	2	
CONSTRUCTION			
Contractor, HVAC designer, architect	The contractor is not familiar with installing the hybridGEOTABS concept.	1	Pre-engineered and pre-fabricated components make the installation easier and create confidence (WP6).
Contractor, control designer/contractor	The installed HVAC-hardware (pumps, valves, radiator valves...) may be sub-optimal for using MPC.	2	The control company providing the MPC should be involved in the design phase.
Control designer/contractor	The HVAC and/or control contractors/installers are not familiar with the concept and apply default / inappropriate settings.	1	Experienced control designer/contractors are involved from the design phase (see also 'design phase').

Contractors, suppliers, architect and designers	The borders of responsibility between several suppliers and contractors collaborating are unclear and lead to arguments and suboptimal results.	1/2	Knowledge centre (WP7) plays the role to increase the knowledge (e.g. certification or experience sheets). More integrated building contracting procedures such as DB, DBM etc. may provide a better framework to allow to tackle legal responsibility questions.
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COMMISSIONING

Control designer/contractor, commissioner	In today's practice, errors and defects in the HVAC-system (introduced during the construction and first operation) often occur but are difficult to detect.	2	During the installation of MPC in the construction phase, a detailed model of the HVAC is set-up and many faults and defects in the HVAC-system are detected, thus making the commissioning phase very time-efficient and effective (WP3-4). MPC (white box) can enable pre-occupancy assessment of the operation, to prevent early malfunctioning in the stage of first operation and occupancy.
Control designer/contractor	Traditional controllers (RBC) require important case-by-case efforts to realise comfort and energy-efficiency, by tuning the settings or positioning of sensors, valves, pumps, controllers increasing commissioning costs	3	Promote MPC for controlling hybridGEOTABS (WP7); Development of an MPC-toolchain, robust and adaptive MPC to make commissioning easier (WP3);

OPERATION and MAINTENANCE

Owner, operator	Traditional controllers (RBC) cannot harvest the full potential of hybridGEOTABS and even may jeopardise the performance if not well-designed	3	MPC allows optimised HVAC control (e.g. comfort, energy efficiency, cost efficiency) (WP3)
Operator, maintainer	Actors are not familiar with maintaining hybridGEOTABS(-MPC) buildings and increase the use of the secondary system, thus risking to decrease the real energy and environmental performance	2	In-use commissioning or periodical audits by hybridGEOTABS experts or maintainers with expertise. Maintenance use cases become available.
Commissioner, maintainer, operator	Detection of defects and reduced performance of the HVAC-system during its operational lifetime are often not or lately detected.	2	The MPC includes a detailed model and measurements of the HVAC system, allowing to follow-up on the performance of the system and detection of faults (WP3). MPC also has potential for predictive maintenance.
Owner, operator, maintainer, control designer/contractor	The geothermal borefield is not in balance in the long term, and is depleted prematurely.	3	The MPC, installed in construction phase and designed in design phase, controls the long-term balance of the borefield (WP3).

Operator, maintainer	Water based systems in buildings may be better in the future compared to refrigerant solutions in buildings (type VRF/VRV) used in heat pumps today (e.g. F-gas regulation, GWP of refrigerants, periodic maintenance, replacement)	1	Environmentally friendly refrigerants are under development (WP6).
Maintainer, operator	When smart grids are/become operational, buildings or HVAC-systems are not ready to deal with it.	2	hybridGEOTABS with MPC is a smart grid ready solution: the MPC is ready to include interaction with the grids in its objective function (WP3).
Maintainer, operator, owner, designer	When the function or internal organisation of the building changes, the HVAC needs to be adapted.	2	TABS offer a free and flexible floor plan, making the building more adaptable (WP5).
Maintainer, owner, designer	The deconstruction and end-of-life (EOL) of TABS may be challenging.	1	Possibilities for a useful EOL treatment of TABS are/become available (WP5).

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Annex 1: Hydraulic schemes

hybrid GEO TABS
09.12.2019/ MSt
Lemon Consult AG

H1(a) GEOTABS (only) heating mode

Labeling layer	
Heating	
—	heat, supply
- - -	heat, return
—	brine/water, supply
- - -	brine/water, return
Cooling	
—	free-cooling, supply
- - -	free-cooling, return
—	cooling water, supply
- - -	cooling water, return
—	chilled water, supply
- - -	chilled water, return
Sanitary	
—	hot water
- - -	cold water

Labeling symbols	
	2 way valve
	3 way valve
	on to valve
	non-return valve
	pump
	temperature sensor
	flow sensor

NOTES:

- No storage on the primary side (borefield): Therefore it is important to note that this scheme is not compatible with a building requiring active cooling.
- Passive (free) cooling is possible.

primary energy source
borefield

heat pump

storage hot

heating/ cooling group TABS
temperature <30°C

secondary heating
biogas/ gas

heating/ cooling group AHU
temperature <50°C

heating/ cooling group
temperature <50°C

cooling HEX

central DHW fresh water station
temperature <65°C

Controlling the power of the ground by integration

hybrid GEO TABS
09.12.2019/ MSt
Lemon Consult AG

H2(a) - Bivalent heating mode

Labeling layer	
Heating	
	heat, supply
	heat, return
	brine/water, supply
	brine/water, return
Cooling	
	free-cooling, supply
	free-cooling, return
	cooling water, supply
	cooling water, return
	chilled water, supply
	chilled water, return
Sanitary	
	hot water
	cold water

Labeling symbols	
	2 way valve
	3 way valve
	on to valve
	non-return valve
	pump
	temperature sensor
	flow sensor

NOTES:

- No storage on the primary side (borefield):
Therefore it is important to note that this scheme is not compatible with a building requiring active cooling.
- The bivalent system is either a biogas or gas condensing boiler.

primary energy source borefield heat pump storage hot heating/ cooling group TABS temperature <30°C secondary heating biogas/ gas heating/ cooling group AHU temperature <50°C heating/ cooling group temperature <50°C cooling HEX central DHW fresh water station temperature <65°C

Controlling the power of the ground by integration

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C1(a) – Passive GEOTABS cooling (free cooling only)

Labeling layer

Heating	
—	heat, supply
- - -	heat, return
—	brine/water, supply
- - -	brine/water, return
Cooling	
—	free-cooling, supply
- - -	free-cooling, return
—	cooling water, supply
- - -	cooling water, return
—	chilled water, supply
- - -	chilled water, return
Sanitary	
—	hot water
- - -	cold water

Labeling symbols

	2 way valve
	3 way valve
	on to valve
	non-return valve
	pump
	temperature sensor
	flow sensor

NOTES:

- This example shows the connexions required for a building which can only operate in free cooling mode.
- For schemes compatible with also active cooling mode, refer to C1(b), C2, C3.

primary energy source borefield heat pump storage hot heating/ cooling group TABS temperature <math>< 30^{\circ}\text{C}</math> secondary heating biogas/ gas heating/ cooling group AHU temperature <math>< 50^{\circ}\text{C}</math> heating/ cooling group temperature <math>< 50^{\circ}\text{C}</math> cooling HEX central DHW fresh water station temperature <math>< 65^{\circ}\text{C}</math>

hybrid GEO TABS
21.11.2019/ MST
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C1(b) – Passive GEOTABS cooling mode (with storage on primary side)

Labeling layer

Heating	Heat, supply
	Heat, return
Cooling	brine/water, supply
	brine/water, return
	free-cooling, supply
	free-cooling, return
	cooling water, supply
	cooling water, return
	chilled water, supply
	chilled water, return
Sanitary	hot water
	cold water

Labeling symbols

	2 way valve
	3 way valve
	on to valve
	non-return valve
	pump
	temperature sensor
	flow sensor

NOTES:

- C1(b) shows like C1(a) passive cooling operation but in the case of a building, which has all necessary equipment for active cooling operation.
- Use of a stratified storage on primary side is optional but recommended: the buffer tank is optimised with differentiated thermal layers and enable to alternate the extraction of either hot or cold(er) water at different temperature. It increases the capacity of the tank to store heat and deliver it at the desired temperature.

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C2 – Active GEOTABS cooling (reversible HP) - option with no dry cooler

Labeling layer	
Heating	
—	heat, supply
—	heat, return
Cooling	
—	brine/water, supply
—	brine/water, return
—	free-cooling, supply
—	free-cooling, return
—	cooling water, supply
—	cooling water, return
—	chilled water, supply
—	chilled water, return
Sanitary	
—	hot water
—	cold water

Labeling symbols	
	2 way valve
	3 way valve
	on to valve
	non-return valve
	pump
	temperature sensor
	flow sensor

NOTES:
- The heat pump works in reversible mode and 100% of the heat rejection is done via the boreholes. No heat rejection to the outside air.
- For connexion with a DAC unit, refer to hydraulic scheme C3.

Controlling the power of the ground by integration

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DHW1 – Central DHW Production

Labeling layer	
Heating	
—	heat, supply
—	heat, return
—	brine/water, supply
—	brine/water, return
Cooling	
—	free-cooling, supply
—	free-cooling, return
—	cooling water, supply
—	cooling water, return
—	chilled water, supply
—	chilled water, return
Sanitary	
—	hot water
—	cold water

Labeling symbols	
	2 way valve
	3 way valve
	on to valve
	non-return valve
	pump
	temperature sensor
	flow sensor

NOTES:

- The heating hot water is produced centrally by the main heat pump and feeds a second heating storage tank for DHW only.
- There is no dedicated HP for the DHW production. The use of FWS (fresh water station) as DHW system guarantees hygienic requirements as well as higher efficiency for the production of domestic hot water.

recovery borefield HEX primary energy source borefield storage cold air-cooled chiller reversible heat pump storage hot heating/ cooling group TABS temperature <30°C secondary heating biogas/ gas heating/ cooling group AHU temperature <50°C heating/ cooling group temperature <50°C cooling HEX central DHW fresh water station temperature <65°C decentral DHW heat pump temperature <65°C

Controlling the power of the ground by integration

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A1 - Exergy optimised with hybrid solar (PV-T) regeneration

Labeling layer

Heating

- heat, supply
- heat, return
- brine/water, supply
- brine/water, return
- brine/water hybrid solar, supply
- brine/water hybrid solar, return

Cooling

- free-cooling, supply
- free-cooling, return
- cooling water, supply
- cooling water, return
- chilled water, supply
- chilled water, return

Sanitary

- hot water
- cold water

Labeling symbols

- 2 way valve
- 3 way valve
- on to valve
- non-return valve
- pump
- temperature sensor
- flow sensor

- NOTES:**
- This scheme includes a PV-T (hybrid solar) module as a solution to reduce seasonal imbalance of the ground.
 - The solar thermal output of the system is used to "regenerate" the boreholes with heat.
 - The electric output provide a green power source for the building services.

hybrid solar primary energy source borefield heat pump storage hot heating/cooling group TABS temperature <math><30^{\circ}\text{C}</math> secondary heating biogas/ gas heating/cooling group AHU temperature <math><50^{\circ}\text{C}</math> heating/cooling group temperature <math><50^{\circ}\text{C}</math> cooling HEX central DHW fresh water station temperature <math><65^{\circ}\text{C}</math>

Controlling the power of the ground by integration

Annex 2: Generic specifications of key system components

A.1 Introduction

Specifications constitute, besides plans and bills of quantities, the most important document of the final design phase in the most commonly applied building process (Design Bid Build). Specifications are usually annexed to the contract between the contracting authority (investor) and the contractor. As such, they become legally binding for both contracting parties. Therefore, it is understood that the quality of specifications can have a significant impact on the development of the construction phase of the build process.

Like any contract, specifications shall express the designer's intent in a clear, precise and concise manner. Moreover, such specifications are easy to maintain and can quickly be adapted to reflect the technological advances in the concerned field or to fit a particular project's needs. Verbose specifications, on the other hand, are usually difficult to maintain, especially if they contain multiple interlaced dependencies at various parts of the specification. Designers often tend to write verbose specifications thinking that specifications that are more extensive are more likely to hide the eventual shortcomings. At some point, such practice can backfire, especially if the verbosity has led to contradictions or requirements that are incompatible with the specific requirements of a given project. Therefore, the specification writer shall try to find just the right balance between being too verbose and too concise. At the same time, the specifications shall be clear and precise.

In Europe, the specification styles vary from one country to another, and very often from one company to another. One can find specifications ranging from a rather verbose novel-like style on one hand to a bullet list-like style on the other one. Moreover, the specification sometimes acts as a separate document from the bill of quantities or both can be merged into one integrated document.

The format proposed in this annex follows the bullet list style and tends to be as concise as possible. If needed, the person using these texts can still expand it into a novel-like structure or, alternatively, make it even more concise. At the same time, the applied format has been selected such that it can also be used in styles where articles represent one bill of quantity unit. Such style can easily be transformed into a pure specification not linked to a bill of quantities, as it will be explained below.

In any case, the person using these generic specification texts shall adapt them in order to suit the exact project needs. In order to be applicable in the entire EU, national standards are not referenced in the following specifications. If such standards or any other locally recognized guidelines are considered as the state of the art in the country of interest, the specification writer shall adapt the content accordingly.

A.2 Structure

This section explains how the specifications presented in this document are structured.

Sections

Each specification article is divided into several sections used to group the related technical content. Sections are only added to the specification if necessary.

The following sections are used:

- Products
- Labor
- Submittals
- Certification
- Specifications
- Operation
- Execution

Products

The purpose of this section is to provide a succinct way of defining the entire scope of products covered by the article.

The products considered included in the scope of the article if a quantity is used are listed. This way, anyone reading the specification (e.g. the contractor submitting the price offer) immediately gets an idea what products are included in the article's scope. This is especially useful for auxiliary items that are usually not specified in details, e.g. fastening material.

It is definitely not the meaning of this section to describe the construction of some equipment (i.e. the way some product is assembled). Only the list of individual equipment items that clearly form a complete functional entity can be given. The following list gives some examples of complete functional entities: heat pump, boiler, buffer tank, valve, etc.

The list shall not contain individual components of one functional entity. These shall be described, if needed, under the specification section. For example, a heat pump compressor is just a component of a heat pump functional entity that is a heat pump. It shall therefore not be listed under this section, because it is automatically included in the heat pump. The same goes for components such as an impeller that is just a component of a pump functional entity.

Labor

In analogy to the section 'Products' which gives an overview of products included in the specification article, this section gives an overview of labor comprised in the described article. It is used in specification writing styles where a specification article is bound to an item in the bill of quantities.

The labor considered included in the scope of the article if a quantity is used are listed. Most commonly, this will be the supply and installation of the material, but in the case of certain products, other labor shall also be included. For example, in case of complex machines such as heat pumps, commissioning shall also be included if not specified in its own article.

Submittals

This section is used to specify the list of documents and samples that the contractor shall submit during construction. In analogy to the sections 'Products' and 'Work', this section only lists the submittal types and not their full content. In most cases, it is sufficient. However, if it is necessary to provide more information regarding one type of submittal, this is done under the section 'Specifications'.

A special type of submittals that is required in most cases are technical data sheets. The list only mentions that technical data sheets shall be submitted, but at the same time it refers to the 'Specifications' for the precision of which sheets precisely are needed.

By default, it is not specified when during the construction phase the required submittals shall be submitted. If some submittals need to be submitted earlier or later than required, this can be explicitly prescribed in this section.

Certification

This section can be used to specify the necessary approvals and certificates of the equipment. The approvals and certificates can be requested either for a specific functional unit or for all the equipment described in the article, depending on the context.

Specifications

This section defines all the necessary requirements for the specified product or system. If detailed product or system descriptions are necessary then they shall be provided here.

Any description given in this section tries to be succinct. Only important information is given without the unnecessary prescriptive overhead. For example, when describing a circulator pump, it is not specified that it contains an electric motor and an impeller because this is implicitly required in order to comply with the performance requirements.

The requirements provided in this section are performance based as much as possible. Prescriptive requirements are avoided if possible.

If a technical data sheet shall be submitted for some equipment (because it typically is of great interest to the designer) this is specified using the '@' symbol followed by the word 'data sheet'. The '@' symbol is used to make this requirement stand out from the rest of the text and to make it searchable in a pdf document. The data sheet requirement shall always be the first line following the subsection delimiter.

The 'Specifications' section is divided into separate subsections for every functional unit. If needed, there can also be one general section ('General') at the beginning that lists the general requirements applicable to all functional units.

The structure of this section is rather flexible and is not fixed. The description is split into logical groups, avoiding several layers if possible. Large and complex functional units (e.g. heat pumps) require separate subsections to describe individual components of functional units.

Operation

This section is used to explain the working principle of a product or system. It is most commonly used to describe the operation of an equipment that is based on some sort of automation control, although the control can also be mechanical. This section is only used if the description of the operation sequence or principle is necessary. For example, one does not describe the principles of operation of a scroll compressor because such principles are generally well known and understood.

Execution

This section provides specific instructions for execution work, i.e. how the work shall be performed and what result shall be achieved. It shall not be confused with the 'Work' which is a listing of work to be performed.

Customization

Specifications have to be adapted in order to suit the exact needs of each project. Parts of specification texts that need to be adapted or filled in by the specifier taking into account specific project requirements have been indicated with **blue** color.

A.3 Liability and trademarks

Disclaimer of liability: the authors of the specification texts provided in this document shall be not hold responsible for any damage that may arise from the use of these texts. Anyone using these specification texts solely bears the full responsibility for the legal consequences that may arise from their use.

Claims to third-party names: this report does not make any claims to third-party names:

BACnet® is a trademark of the American Society of Heating, Refrigeration and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE).

The BTL logo (BACnet Testing Laboratory) is a trademark of BACnet International (BI), earlier BACnet Manufacturers Association (BMA).

Text may contain specific trademarks to clearly describe the design intention. This cannot be interpreted as a recommendation by the report authors. At the same time, mentioning a trademark does not mean that that particular product is best suited for the related application.

A.4 Specifications

01 Heat pumps and chillers

Heat pumps and chillers

Work:

always included

Selection

Supply and installation

Commissioning

Submittals:

always included

Product data sheet

Declaration of performance

Unit selection sheet

Vibration dampers selection sheet

Shop drawing

Operating, maintenance and safety instructions, in particular:

- Instruction for safe use under operating and maintenance conditions
- Instruction for switching on and off the equipment
- Instructions for equipment and control instruments, periodic inspections, frequency recommends for these inspections
- Description of the normal operation of the device, the instructions concerning the protection and control equipment, the instructions for troubleshooting
- Instructions for maintenance and cleaning, with diagrams

Specifications:

> Submittals

The calculation of performance in the actual operating state shall be determined using calculation software certified by Eurovent or an equivalent certification body

The declaration of performance transmitted shall comply with the requirements of the relevant EU regulations, in particular:

- Regulation (EU) 206/2012
- Regulation (EU) 813/2013
- Regulation (EU) 2016/2281

The coefficient of performance (COP, EER, COP_{rated}, EER_{rated}, SCOP, SEER) mentioned on the documentation submitted by the contractor shall be established in accordance with EN 14511 (all parts)

> Definitions

Nominal heat output (Q_n): cooling or heating output supplied by the appliance at nominal operating conditions

Monobloc version: all elements are mounted in a single frame

Split version: condenser and evaporator are mounted in separate frames and connected by means of pipes

> Performances

All performance factors shall always be determined in accordance with EN 14511 (all parts)

The following conditions apply to the coefficients of performance mentioned in these specifications:

- COP and/or EER: nominal operating conditions (defined separately for each device specified in the article of the device itself)
- COP_{rated} or EER_{rated}: test conditions (defined separately for each device specified in the article of the device itself)
- SCOP and / or SEER: average standard climate

> General

Devices shall be fully assembled and tested at the factory

All the components of a device shall be designed and produced so that they resist the corrosion classes according to EN ISO 9223 specified below in these specifications

If a coating shall be provided on the heat exchangers to meet the requirements for protection against corrosion, the selection of components shall take into account the additional heat transfer resistance

> Compressors

>> Authorized types

Unless expressly stated otherwise in the specification, the following types of compressors are allowed:

- Rotary compressors: up to 50 kW Q_n
- Piston compressors: up to 300 kW Q_n
- Scroll compressors: up to 300 kW Q_n
- Screw compressors: without restrictions
- Centrifugal compressors: without restrictions

>> Modes of execution

The following modes of execution are authorized:

- Hermetic: up to 50 kW of Q_n (exception: scroll compressors: without restrictions)
- Semi-hermetic: without restrictions
- Open execution: not authorized

>> Lubrication

Lubrication of compressor, bearings and any speed multipliers is carried out under pressure

The necessary oil pressure is supplied either by an oil pump or by the compressor itself (if the oil pan is on the high-pressure side)

For semi-hermetic compressors there is also a removable oil filter, an oil pressure switch and an oil level sight glass

Oil shall be compatible with the refrigerant

The oil pan contains an electrical resistance, which keeps the oil at the necessary temperature when the compressor is not running

>> Compressor cooling

The compressor and the drive motor of the hermetic and semi-hermetic compressors are cooled by the refrigerant and possibly by oil

The oil is also cooled by the refrigerant

>> Number of compressors

A device can contain a maximum of four compressors

>> Special requirements: piston compressors and scroll compressors

A piston compressor has at least two cylinders

The heat output of the device is adjustable at least as follows:

- Q_n less than 30 kW: on / off

- Q_n between 30 and 100 kW: min. 2 stages (lower stage: max. 50% of Q_n)
- Q_n between 100 and 200 kW: min. 3 stages (lower stage: max. 33% of Q_n)
- Q_n between 200 and 300 kW: min. 4 stages (lower stage: max. 25% of Q_n)

The heat output shall be adjusted either by the use of several compressors, or by an adjustable power compressor; in the latter case, three methods are allowed:

- A bypass between the suction side and the discharge side of one or more cylinders / spirals
- Lifting the suction valve of one or more cylinders / spirals
- Variation of the rotation speed of the drive motor

>> Special requirements: screw compressors

The sealing between screws as well as between screws and body is ensured by the oil of the lubrication system

The heat output shall be able to be continuously adjustable between 10 and 100% of Q_n ; the following methods of adjustment are permitted:

- A bypass between the suction side and the discharge side
- Variation of the rotation speed of the drive motor

>> Special requirements: centrifugal compressors

Centrifugal compressors are of the single or multi-stage type

The heat output shall be able to be continuously adjustable between 10 and 100% of Q_n ; the following methods of adjustment are permitted:

- Adjustable blades mounted on the suction
- Variation of the rotation speed of the drive motor

> Electric drive motor

>> Features

The following types of electric motors are authorized:

- Three-phase asynchronous motor according to EN 60034-1
- Three-phase synchronous motors with permanent magnets

Min. protection index: IP 54

Insulation class min.:

- Standard: class B (130 to 155 °C)
- Motors powered by frequency regulators: class F (155 to 180 °C)

Efficiency class min.: IE3 according to EN 60034-30-1
A temperature sensor is placed in the motor windings

>> Motor starting

Direct starting of motors is allowed insofar as there are no harmful consequences for the drive system and for the functioning of the electrical installation
In any case, it is prohibited to directly start motors with a power greater than 20 kVA

In general, the maximum inrush current is limited to the following values according to the nominal power of the motor:

- $P_n \leq 3 \text{ kVA}$: $4 \times I_n$
- $3 \text{ kVA} < P_n \leq 5 \text{ kVA}$: $3 \times I_n$
- $5 \text{ kVA} < P_n \leq 10 \text{ kVA}$: $2 \times I_n$
- $10 \text{ kVA} < P_n$: $1.5 \times I_n$

In order to satisfy the requirements concerning the inrush current, the following solutions can be used:

- Variable speed drives
- Star-delta starters with contactors according to EN 60947-4-1
- Starters with semiconductors (soft-starter) according to EN 60947-4-2 (in this case, the starter can also fulfill the function of contactor); start time and torque or current shall be adjustable

It is necessary to take all the necessary precautions so that during the switching of the poles, or of the star-delta passage, the axis of the motor does not undergo too violent shocks likely to damage the transmission or the load driven or shorten its lifespan

The starting current limiting devices shall be installed in the control panel of the device itself or in the electrical panel, which supplies the device
During start-up, the device always works at the lowest power level

>> Speed control

The speed control of the drive motors is optional with compressors (unless expressly indicated) and compulsory with fans and circulator pumps
Variable speed drives shall be of the electronic frequency converter type (possibly as part of a synchronous motor with permanent magnets)
Drives that are not part of the motor shall be installed in the electric panel of the device

> Expansion valve

Only the electronic type expansion valve is authorized

> Water cooled/heated condenser/evaporator

if applicable

Compliance: EN 14276

The following construction types are authorized:

- Coaxial (Q_n : max. 50 kW): the pipes are made of copper
- With plates (Q_n : max. 300 kW): the plates are made of stainless steel (material 1.4401 or 1.4404) and welded or brazed
- With tube bundle (without restrictions): the tubes are made of copper, the envelope of steel

Equipped with a drain valve and a water side air purge

Pressure drop (water side): max. 50 kPa (for delta T indicated below in the specification)

Operating pressure: at least 6 bar

Fouling factor: the device selection shall take into account the following fouling factor:

- Evaporator: 0.018 (m^2K) / kW
- Condenser: 0.035 (m^2K) / kW

If a heat exchanger is used as an evaporator and condenser, the selection shall be made taking into account the most unfavorable value

> Air cooled/heated condenser/evaporator or free cooling heat exchanger

if applicable

Compliance: EN 14276

The following constructions are authorized:

- Fin-and-tube: copper tubes, aluminum fins
- Micro-channels: entirely in aluminum

The air flow through the exchanger is ensured by one or more fans which are part of the device itself

Coating (only applicable if specified in the article of the specified device itself): the surface of the heat exchangers shall also be protected by a coating system in accordance with EN ISO 12944-5 (durability class H: more than 15 years) although the uncoated material may already meet the required corrosion environment class

The corrosion environment class is defined below in the item of the specified device itself

> Fans

if applicable

The following constructions are authorized:

- Centrifugal type with backward curved blades
- Axial type

The impeller is mounted directly on the motor shaft

Any contact between different metals shall be avoided

Impellers are mounted on self-aligning bearings and greased for life

Bearings shall be dimensioned for a minimum service life (L₁₀ according to ISO 281-1) of 40,000 hours of operation at maximum speed

The fan motor unit shall be statically and dynamically balanced in accordance with ISO 14694 and ISO 1940-1, class G: 2.5

The impeller and the blades are made of:

- Aluminum
- Fiber reinforced material

Reaction to fire class of plastics: min. B-s1,do

> Thermal insulation

All elements of the hydraulic and refrigeration circuit in the appliance shall be thermally insulated in the factory

Insulation material:

- Flexible elastomer closed cell foam
- Compliance: EN 14304
- Does not contain CFC or HCFC
- Reaction to fire class: min. B(L)-s3,do
- Declared thermal conductivity (at +10 ° C): ≤ 0.040 W/(mK)
- Coefficient of resistance to water vapor diffusion: $\geq 10,000$

The minimum thickness of thermal insulation allowed is 20 mm

> Frame

>> General

All components are mounted on a solid frame made of steel profiles or on a self-supporting construction in which the different elements are fixed to each other

In the case of outside installation, the motor-compressor assembly and accessories are placed in a compartment composed of removable metal panels

>> Anti-vibration measures

Devices with rotating elements shall always be installed on a raised base:

- Either on a concrete base with a minimum thickness of 8 cm, the edge of which is protected by an angle profile 50 x 50 x 5 mm
- Either on a metallic structure in stainless steel (min. EN 1.4301)

- Either on a wall support made of powder-coated sheet steel profiles (exceptionally for direct expansion devices whose nominal electrical power does not exceed 5 kW)

Anti-vibration elements shall be placed between the base and the device; their characteristics shall meet the acoustic requirements

>> Noise reduction

When the acoustic conditions require it, the device shall be fitted with a soundproof box

The box is either made of removable metal panels, coated inside with sound absorption material or is double-walled

All control and signaling devices shall remain visible and freely accessible

The non-combustible sound absorption material in the box, in the noise attenuators and in the screens (class A2 according to EN 13501-1) shall be durable, rot-proof and vermin-resistant; it is also provided with the necessary means of protection to prevent it from eroding and becoming wet in the event of rain

The panels shall be removable while the hydraulic and electrical connections are operational

> Control panel

Compliance: EN 61439 (series)

The panel is completely wired, connected to the compressor and its accessories and tested in the manufacturer's factory

The 24 V DC control transformer in the panel shall have a power reserve of at least 1 A

> Controls

The device is equipped with microprocessor control unit

The control unit is installed in the control panel of the device

Each device shall be fitted with a potential-free contact, which, by means of an external signal, can prevent the device from operating

In the case of several devices connected in parallel, the control system shall be able to operate in cascade; the regulation of at least one device shall be configured as master, or the contractor shall provide an additional master regulator

A dip in the mains voltage causes an ordered shutdown of the device and, when the mains voltage returns, an automatic start-up

> Human-machine interface

A control unit with a screen and a keyboard shall be provided

> BMS interface

The control unit is provided by default with a BACnet (IP or SC) or Modbus interface

> Nameplate

The device is equipped with a nameplate in durable material and whose inscriptions are indelible

The plate is securely spun in an easily accessible and visible place

It bears at least the following indications:

- Name of manufacturer
- Model and serial number
- Year of manufacture
- Type and quantity of refrigerant
- Thermal/cooling capacity for nominal conditions
- Temperatures at nominal conditions
- Nominal voltage
- Maximum current

> Temperature range

When stopped, the device shall be able to withstand without adverse consequences, all the temperatures that could result from the nature of the installation and the indoor and outdoor climatic conditions

- Outside: -15 to +40 °C
- Indoors (underground or in an isolated room): +10 to +40 °C
- Indoors (in a non-isolated room): -5 to +40 °C

The contractor shall take all the necessary measures for this purpose

Without prejudice to the more specific prescriptions below, any device shall be able to operate when the temperatures are as follows:

>> Chilled water units

Air condenser:

- Air temperature: between -10 and +40 °C

Water condenser:

- Inlet water temperature: between +20 and +30 °C
- Difference in water temperature between the inlet and outlet of the condenser: between 4 and 8 K

Air evaporator: not applicable

Water evaporator:

- Outlet water temperature: between +5 and +15 °C

- Difference in water temperature between the inlet and outlet of the evaporator: between 4 and 8 K

>> Heat pumps

Air condenser: not applicable

Water condenser:

- Outlet water temperature (flow temperature):
 - Standard application: between +25 and +55 °C
 - High temperature (HT) application: between +25 and +70 °C
- Difference in water temperature between the inlet and the outlet of the condenser: between 4 and 8 K

Air evaporator:

- Inlet air temperature: between -15 and +30 °C

Water or brine evaporator:

- Inlet water temperature
 - Water/water type heat pump: between +7 and +25 °C
 - Soil/water type heat pump: between -5 and +25 °C
- Difference in temperature of water or brine between the inlet and outlet of the evaporator: between 4 and 8 K

>> Reversible heat pumps and multipurpose machines

The requirements for chillers, as well as for heat pumps apply

> Restart interval

In the event of a total power supply interruption (compressor and control unit power supply), the device shall be fully operational within an interval defined below after the return of the mains voltage (according to the specifications in the article of the device itself):

- Standard variant: 10 minutes
- Data center variant: 2 minutes

The device shall be factory fitted with all the necessary devices in order to guarantee this interval

If the variant applied in the specifications is omitted, the standard variant applies

> Frost protection

if applicable

All the elements of the hydraulic circuit in the device shall be equipped with a protection against freezing of the system fluid in the event of negative temperatures down to -20 °C

The protection shall be carried out by means of electrical tracing fitted in the factory under thermal insulation

Execution:

> Access area

An access area for maintenance shall be provided

The width of the access area shall be at least equal to that prescribed by the device manufacturer

Overlap: it is accepted that the access area of a device overlaps the access area of an adjacent device without, however, overlapping the horizontal projection of this other device

> Water content

Before choosing a compressor technology, the contractor shall verify that the water content in the proposed installation is sufficient; if it turns out that the content is not sufficient for the proposed technology, the contractor shall include in his offer all the measures necessary to increase the water content (e.g. installation of a buffer tank)

Notes:

The meaning of the word water in this article and the following articles in this chapter may vary depending on the context and may mean either water or brine

Hydraulic modules

Work:

always included
selection
supply and installation
commissioning

Submittals:

always included
product data sheet

device selection note
workshop drawing

Specifications:

> Hydraulic module

Construction :

- Connections to the hydraulic circuit
- Filter
- Buffer tank (if applicable - see device article)
- Expansion tank
- Safety valve
- Purge valve
- Air vent
- Circulator pump
- Pressure gauge
- Thermometer (flow and return)
- Flow switch
- Frost protection (if specified in the device article)

All the elements of the hydraulic module shall be integrated into the chassis of the device which they supplement

The dimensions are not specifically indicated in the specifications; the dimensions of the device in which the module is integrated apply

01.01 Chillers

01.01.01 Chiller - air/water

Material:

Chiller

[Hydraulic module](#)

Specifications:

> General

Layout: [indoor / outdoor](#)

Corrosion environment according to EN ISO 9223: [C3](#)

> Chiller

>> General

Type: water / water

Construction: monobloc

Operating mode: cooling

Configuration: 2 pipes (monovalent)

Restart interval variant: [standard / data center](#)

System fluid:

- Primary: [water](#)
- Secondary: [water](#)

Approximate dimensions:

- Length: [___ mm](#)
- Width: [___ mm](#)
- Height: [___ mm](#)

Refrigerant: [\[optional\]](#)

Min. refrigerant circuits: [\[optional\]](#)

Min. compressors per circuit: [\[optional\]](#)

>> Performance at nominal service conditions

Nominal service conditions (cooling):

- Condenser (inlet / outlet): [25/30 °C](#)
- Evaporator (inlet / outlet): [15/10 °C](#)

Nominal useful cooling capacity: [___ kW](#)

Max current (according to nameplate): [___ A](#)

Max sound power : [___ dB\(A\)](#)

>> Performance under test conditions

Test conditions (for EER_{test}):

- Condenser (inlet/outlet): 30/35 °C
- Rvaporator (inlet/outlet): 12/7 °C

EER_{test} : min. ____

SEER: min. ____

> Hydraulic module

Number of pumps: 1

Buffer tank: yes

Volume of the buffer tank: ____ L

01.01.02 Chiller - air/water

Material:

Chiller

Hydraulic module

Specifications:

> General

Layout: indoor / outdoor

Corrosion environment according to EN ISO 9223: C₃

> Chiller

>> General

Type: air/water

Construction: monobloc

Operating mode: cooling

Configuration: 2 pipes (monovalent)

Restart interval variant: [standard / data center](#)

System fluid: [water](#)

Approximate dimensions:

- Length: [___ mm](#)
- Width: [___ mm](#)
- Height: [___ mm](#)

Frost protection: [yes](#)

Refrigerant: [\[optional\]](#)

Min. refrigerant circuits: [\[optional\]](#)

Min. compressors per circuit: [\[optional\]](#)

Coating on the air/refrigerant heat exchanger: [yes](#)

>> Performance at nominal service conditions

Nominal operating conditions (cooling):

- Condenser (inlet: dry bulb): [32 °C](#)
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): [15/10 °C](#)

Nominal useful cooling capacity: [___ kW](#)

Max current (according to nameplate): [___ A](#)

Max sound power : [___ dB\(A\)](#)

>> Performance under test conditions

Test conditions (for EER_{test}):

- Condenser (inlet: dry bulb): [35 °C](#)
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): [12/7 °C](#)

EER_{test} : [min. ___](#)

SEER: [min. ___](#)

> Hydraulic module

Number of pumps: [1](#)

Frost protection: [yes](#)

Buffer tank: yes

Volume of the buffer tank: ___ L

01.01.03 Chiller - air/water (with heat recuperation)

Material:

Chiller

Hydraulic module

Specifications:

> Heat recovery

The term heat recovery implies an additional double wall heat exchanger in the vapour compression cycle, upstream of the condenser and downstream of the compressor

The heat exchanger for heat recovery has connections for an additional hydraulic circuit; this circuit is hydraulically separated from the chilled water circuit coming from the evaporator

There are two possible versions of heat pumps with heat recovery which are distinguished by the type of outlet temperature control on the secondary side of the heat exchanger and the extent of heat recovery (total/partial recovery)

>> Partial heat recovery

The additional heat exchanger is dimensioned to be able to recover part of the rejected heat

The power of this exchanger and the outlet temperature are not controlled and vary according to The requested cooling capacity

>> Total heat recovery

The additional heat exchanger is sized to be able to recover the same power as the condenser

The regulation of the device keeps the outlet temperature on the secondary side of the exchanger constant by adapting the compressor power and the condensing pressure

The chilled water flow temperature is not the primary set point of the control loop if the heat recovery mode is active

The chilled water flow temperature is the primary set point of the control loop if the heat recovery mode is not active

> General

Layout: [indoor/outdoor](#)

Corrosion environment according to EN ISO 9223: [C3](#)

> Chiller

>> General

Type: air/water

Construction: monobloc

Operating mode: cooling and heat recuperation

Configuration: 4 pipes

Type of heat recuperation: [partial](#)

Restart interval variant: [standard / data centre](#)

System fluid:

- Cooling: [propylene glycol 25%](#)
- Heat recuperation: [water](#)

Approximate dimensions:

- Length: [___ mm](#)
- Width: [___ mm](#)
- Height: [___ mm](#)

Frost protection: [yes](#)

Refrigerant: [\[optional\]](#)

Min. refrigerant circuits: [\[optional\]](#)

Min. compressors per circuit: [\[optional\]](#)

Coating on the air/refrigerant heat exchanger: [yes](#)

>> Performance at nominal service conditions

Nominal operating conditions (cooling):

- Condenser (inlet: dry bulb): [32 °C](#)
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): [15/10 °C](#)

Nominal operating conditions (heat recuperation):

- Condenser (inlet/outlet): [50/45 °C](#)

Nominal useful cooling capacity: ___ kW

Nominal recuperated heating capacity: ___ kW

Max current (according to nameplate): ___ A

Max sound power : ___ dB(A)

>> Performance under test conditions

Test conditions (for EER_{test}):

- condenser (inlet: dry bulb): 35 ° C
- evaporator (inlet / outlet): 12/7 ° C

EER_{test} : min. ___

SEER: min. ___

> Hydraulic module

Number of pumps: 1

Frost protection: yes

Buffer tank: yes

Volume of the buffer tank: ___ L

01.01.04 Chiller - air/water (with free cooling)

Material:

Chiller

Hydraulic module

Specifications:

> General

Layout: indoor/outdoor

Corrosion environment according to EN ISO 9223: C₃

> Chiller

> Free cooling

the air/water chiller is equipped with an additional heat exchanger cooled by outside air

the additional exchanger cools the system liquid when the dry bulb temperature of the outside air is lower than the return temperature of the cooled system liquid

free cooling is of the indirect type, that is to say that the system fluid never comes into contact with air

free cooling shall be activated automatically by chiller's control system if the gain in electrical power due to free cooling is greater than the additional energy consumption of fans and pumps

under conditions when free cooling alone is not able to provide 100% of the required cooling capacity, the free cooling and mechanical cooling modes with compressors shall be able to operate in parallel; free cooling always takes priority

at a sufficient temperature difference between the outside air and the system liquid (defined in the article of the appliance itself), the appliance shall be able to supply 100% of the required cooling capacity without compressor operation

>> General

Type: air/water

Construction: monobloc

Operating mode: cooling and/or free cooling

Configuration: 2 pipes (monovalent)

Type of heat recuperation: [partial](#)

Restart interval variant: [standard / data centre](#)

System fluid: [propylene glycol 25%](#)

Approximate dimensions:

- Length: [___ mm](#)
- Width: [___ mm](#)
- Height: [___ mm](#)

Frost protection: [yes](#)

Refrigerant: [\[optional\]](#)

Min. refrigerant circuits: [\[optional\]](#)

Min. compressors per circuit: [\[optional\]](#)

Coating on the air/refrigerant heat exchanger: [yes](#)

>> Performance at nominal service conditions

Nominal operating conditions (cooling):

- Condenser (inlet: dry bulb): 32 °C
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): 15/10 °C

Nominal useful cooling capacity: ___ kW

free cooling shall be capable of delivering 100% of the nominal cooling capacity under the following operating conditions:

- System return temperature (Tr): +15 °C
- Dry bulb outside air temperature: Tr - 13 K

Max current (according to nameplate): ___ A

Max sound power : ___ dB(A)

>> Performance under test conditions

Test conditions (for EER_{test}):

- condenser (inlet: dry bulb): 35 °C
- evaporator (inlet / outlet): 12/7 °C

EER_{test}: min. ___

SEER: min. ___

> Hydraulic module

Number of pumps: 1

Frost protection: yes

Buffer tank: yes

Volume of the buffer tank: ___ L

01.02 Heat pumps (heating only)

01.02.01 Heat pump (heating only) - water/water or ground/water

Material:

Heat pump

Hydraulic module

Specifications:

> General

Layout: indoor

Corrosion environment according to EN ISO 9223: C₃

> Heat pump

>> General

Type: water/water or ground/water

Construction: monobloc

Operating mode: heating

Configuration: 2 pipes (monovalent)

Application (heating flow temperature): standard/high temperature

System fluid:

- primary side: water/propylene glycol 25%
- secondary side: water

Approximate dimensions:

- Length: ___ mm
- Width: ___ mm
- Height: ___ mm

Refrigerant: [optional]

Min. refrigerant circuits: [optional]

Min. compressors per circuit: [optional]

>> Performance at nominal service conditions

Nominal operating conditions (heating):

- Condenser (inlet/outlet): 30/35 °C
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): 10/5 °C [water/water] or 5/0 °C [ground/water]

Nominal useful heating capacity: ___ kW

Max current (according to nameplate): ___ A

Max sound power : ___ dB(A)

>> Performance under test conditions

Test conditions (for COP_{test}):

- condenser (inlet/outlet): 30/35 °C
- evaporator (inlet/outlet): 10/7 °C [water/water] or 0/-3 °C [ground/water]

COP_{test}: min. ___

SCOP (at 35/55 °C): min. ___

> Hydraulic module

Number of pumps: 1

Buffer tank: yes

Volume of the buffer tank: ___ L

01.02.02 Heat pump (heating only) - air/water

Material:

Heat pump

Hydraulic module

Specifications:

> General

Layout: indoor/outdoor

Corrosion environment according to EN ISO 9223: C₃

> Heat pump

>> General

Type: air/water

Construction: monobloc

Operating mode: heating

Configuration: 2 pipes (monovalent)

Application (heating flow temperature): [standard/high temperature](#)

System fluid: [propylene glycol 25%](#)

Approximate dimensions:

- Length: [___ mm](#)
- Width: [___ mm](#)
- Height: [___ mm](#)

Frost protection: [yes \[if outdoor\]](#)

Refrigerant: [\[optional\]](#)

Min. refrigerant circuits: [\[optional\]](#)

Min. compressors per circuit: [\[optional\]](#)

Coating on the air/refrigerant heat exchanger: [yes](#)

>> Performance at nominal service conditions

Nominal operating conditions (heating):

- Condenser (inlet/outlet): [30/35 °C](#)
- Evaporator (inlet: dry bulb): [-10 °C](#)

Nominal useful heating capacity: [___ kW](#)

Max current (according to nameplate): [___ A](#)

Max sound power : [___ dB\(A\)](#)

>> Performance under test conditions

Test conditions (for COP_{test}):

- Condenser (outlet): [35 °C](#)
- Evaporator (inlet: dry bulb/wet bulb): [2/1 °C](#)

COP_{test}: [min. ___](#)

SCOP (at [35/55 °C](#)): [min. ___](#)

> Hydraulic module

Number of pumps: 1
Frost protection: yes [if outdoor]
Buffer tank: yes
Volume of the buffer tank: ___ L

01.03 Heat pumps (reversible)

01.03.01 Heat pump (reversible) - water/water or ground/water

Material:

Heat pump

Hydraulic module

Specifications:

> Reversible water/water or ground/water heat pump

There are two possible versions of reversible heat pumps which are distinguished by the way in which the operating mode is reversed (cooling/heating)
The device operating mode is inverted either manually from the man-machine interface or remotely via the BMS interface

>> Water-side inversion

The evaporator and condenser function is not reversible

In heating mode, the control system maintains the desired flow temperature at the condenser outlet

In cooling mode, the control system maintains the desired flow temperature at the evaporator outlet

The control system is capable of controlling 4 external reversing valves which ensure the reversal on the water side; the control unit has the contacts and intelligence necessary to control at least 4 motorized reversing valves depending on the operating mode of the device

>> Refrigerant-side inversion

The evaporator and condenser function is reversible by means of a reversing valve in the vapour compression cycle circuit

In heating mode, the heat exchanger on the secondary side operates as a condenser and the heat exchanger on the primary side as an evaporator

In cooling mode the functions of the heat exchangers on the primary and secondary side are reversed

The control system always maintains the desired temperature setpoint on the secondary side

> General

Layout: indoor

Corrosion environment according to EN ISO 9223: C₃

> Heat pump

>> General

Type: water/water or ground/water

Construction: monobloc

Operating mode: heating or cooling

Configuration: 2 pipes (reversible on the water/refrigerant side)

Application (heating flow temperature): standard/high temperature

System fluid:

- primary side: water/propylene glycol 25%
- secondary side: water

Approximate dimensions:

- Length: ___ mm
- Width: ___ mm
- Height: ___ mm

Refrigerant: [optional]

Min. refrigerant circuits: [optional]

Min. compressors per circuit: [optional]

>> Performance at nominal service conditions

Nominal operating conditions (heating):

- Condenser (inlet/outlet): 30/35 °C
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): 10/5 °C [water/water] or 5/0 °C [ground/water]

Nominal operating conditions (cooling):

- Condenser (inlet/outlet): 20/25 °C
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): 15/10 °C

Nominal useful heating capacity: ___ kW
Nominal useful cooling capacity: ___ kW
Max current (according to nameplate): ___ A
Max sound power : ___ dB(A)

>> Performance under test conditions

Test conditions (for COP_{test}):

- condenser (inlet/outlet): 30/35 ° C
- evaporator (inlet/outlet): 10/7 ° C [water/water] or 0/-3 ° C [ground/water]

Test conditions (for EER_{test}):

- condenser (inlet/outlet): 30/35 ° C
- evaporator (inlet/outlet): 12/7 ° C

COP_{test}: min. ___

EER_{test}: min. ___

SCOP (at 35/55 °C): min. ___

SEER: min. ___

> Hydraulic module

Number of pumps: 1

Buffer tank: yes

Volume of the buffer tank: ___ L

01.03.02 Heat pump (reversible) - air/water

Material:

Heat pump

Hydraulic module

Specifications:

> Reversible air/water heat pump

The device operating mode is inverted either manually from the man-machine interface or remotely via the BMS interface
The evaporator and condenser function is reversible by means of a reversing valve in the vapor compression cycle circuit
In heating mode, the heat exchanger on the secondary side operates as a condenser and the heat exchanger on the primary side as an evaporator
In cooling mode the functions of the heat exchangers on the primary and secondary side are reversed
The control system always maintains the desired temperature setpoint on the secondary side (building side)

> General

Layout: indoor/outdoor

Corrosion environment according to EN ISO 9223: C3

> Heat pump

>> General

Type: air/water

Construction: monobloc

Operating mode: heating

Configuration: 2 pipes (reversible on the refrigerant side)

Application (heating flow temperature): standard/high temperature

System fluid: propylene glycol 25%

Approximate dimensions:

- Length: ___ mm
- Width: ___ mm
- Height: ___ mm

Frost protection: yes [if outdoor]

Refrigerant: [optional]

Min. refrigerant circuits: [optional]

Min. compressors per circuit: [optional]

Coating on the air/refrigerant heat exchanger: yes

>> Performance at nominal service conditions

Nominal operating conditions (heating):

- Condenser (inlet/outlet): 30/35 °C
- Evaporator (inlet: dry bulb): -10 °C

Nominal operating conditions (cooling):

- Condenser (inlet: dry bulb): 32 °C
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): 15/10 °C

Nominal useful heating capacity: ___ kW

Nominal useful cooling capacity: ___ kW

Max current (according to nameplate): ___ A

Max sound power : ___ dB(A)

>> Performance under test conditions

Test conditions (for COP_{test}):

- Condenser (outlet): 35 °C
- Evaporator (inlet: dry bulb/wet bulb): 2/1 °C

Test conditions (for EER_{test}):

- Condenser (inlet: dry bulb/wet bulb): 35 °C
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): 12/7 °C

COP_{test}: min. ___

EER_{test}: min. ___

SCOP (at 35/55 °C): min. ___

SEER: min. ___

> Hydraulic module

Number of pumps: 1

Frost protection: yes [if outdoor]

Buffer tank: yes

Volume of the buffer tank: ___ L

01.04 Multifunctional units

Specifications:

> Multifunctional water/water or air/water unit

The primary side has 2 hydraulic connections for the primary hydraulic circuit [**only applicable to water/water units**]

The secondary side has 4 hydraulic connections for two independent hydraulic circuits: 1x heating + 1x cooling

The reversal of the vapor compression cycle is performed automatically by the integrated control system according to the power requested from the secondary hydraulic circuits

The integrated control system maintains the desired flow temperature for each secondary hydraulic circuit simultaneously and independently

During simultaneous heating and cooling the heat rejected from one process is recovered internally by the other and vice versa; the deficit or surplus comes from the compressor and/or the primary side

01.04.01 Multifunctional unit - water/water

Material:

Heat pump

Hydraulic module

Specifications:

> General

Layout: indoor

Corrosion environment according to EN ISO 9223: C₃

> Heat pump

>> General

Type: water/water

Construction: monobloc

Operating mode: heating and cooling

Configuration: 4 pipes (2x heating + 2x cooling)

Application (heating flow temperature): **standard/high temperature**

System fluid:

- primary side: water/propylene glycol 25%
- secondary side: water

Approximate dimensions:

- Length: ___ mm
- Width: ___ mm
- Height: ___ mm

Refrigerant: [optional]

Min. refrigerant circuits: [optional]

Min. compressors per circuit: [optional]

>> Performance at nominal service conditions

Nominal operating conditions (heating):

- Condenser (inlet/outlet): 30/35 °C
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): 10/5 °C

Nominal operating conditions (cooling):

- Condenser (inlet/outlet): 25/30 °C
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): 15/10 °C

Nominal useful heating capacity: ___ kW

Nominal useful cooling capacity: ___ kW

Max current (according to nameplate): ___ A

Max sound power : ___ dB(A)

>> Performance under test conditions

Test conditions (for COP_{test}):

- Condenser (inlet/outlet): 30/35 °C
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): 10/7 °C

Test conditions (for EER_{test}):

- Condenser (inlet/outlet): 30/35 °C
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): 12/7 °C

COP_{test}: min. ___

EER_{test}: min. ___

SCOP (at 35/55 °C): min. ____

SEER: min. ____

> Hydraulic module

Number of pumps: 1

Buffer tank: yes

Volume of the buffer tank: ____ L

01.04.02 Multifunctional unit - air/water

Material:

Heat pump

Hydraulic module

Specifications:

> General

Layout: outdoor

Corrosion environment according to EN ISO 9223: C₃

> Heat pump

>> General

Type: air/water

Construction: monobloc

Operating mode: heating and cooling

Configuration: 4 pipes (2x heating + 2x cooling)

Application (heating flow temperature): standard/high temperature

System fluid:

- secondary side - heating: water/propylene glycol 25%
- secondary side - cooling: water/propylene glycol 25%

Approximate dimensions:

- Length: ___ mm
- Width: ___ mm
- Height: ___ mm

Frost protection: yes [if outdoor]

Refrigerant: [optional]

Min. refrigerant circuits: [optional]

Min. compressors per circuit: [optional]

Coating on the air/refrigerant heat exchanger: yes

>> Performance at nominal service conditions

Nominal operating conditions (heating):

- Condenser (inlet/outlet): 30/35 °C
- Evaporator (inlet: dry bulb): -10 °C

Nominal operating conditions (cooling):

- Condenser (inlet: dry bulb): 32 °C
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): 15/10 °C

Nominal useful heating capacity: ___ kW

Nominal useful cooling capacity: ___ kW

Max current (according to nameplate): ___ A

Max sound power : ___ dB(A)

>> Performance under test conditions

Test conditions (for COP_{test}):

- Condenser (outlet): 35 °C
- Evaporator (inlet: dry bulb/wet bulb): 2/1 °C

Test conditions (for EER_{test}):

- Condenser (inlet: dry bulb): 35 °C
- Evaporator (inlet/outlet): 12/7 °C

COP_{test}: min. ___

EER_{test}: min. ___

SCOP (at 35/55 °C): min. ____

SEER: min. ____

> Hydraulic module

Number of pumps: 1

Frost protection: yes

Buffer tank: yes

Volume of the buffer tank: ____ L

Controlling the power of the ground by integration

02 Dry coolers

02.01 Dry cooler - table model

Work:

Selection
Supply and installation
Commissioning

Submittals:

Product data sheet
Unit selection sheet
Vibration dampers selection sheet
Shop drawing

Specifications:

> Submittals

The calculation of performance in the actual operating state shall be determined using calculation software certified by Eurovent or an equivalent certification body

> General

Devices shall be fully assembled and tested at the factory

All the components of a device shall be designed and produced so that they resist the corrosion classes according to EN ISO 9223 specified below in these specifications

If a coating shall be provided on the heat exchangers to meet the requirements for protection against corrosion, the selection of components shall take into account the additional heat transfer resistance

> Electric drive motor

The motor is of the permanent magnet type

Min. protection index : IP 54

Efficiency class min. : IE₄ according to EN 60034-30-1

A temperature sensor is placed in the motor windings

The motor is equipped with a device for limiting the starting current; during startup, the device always operates at the lowest power level

Continuous speed regulation of motors is compulsory

Variable speed drives shall be of the electronic frequency converter type (possibly as part of a permanent magnet motor)

Drives that are not part of the motor shall be installed in the control panel of the device

> Fans

The following constructions are authorized:

- Centrifugal type with backward curved blades
- Axial type

The impeller is mounted directly on the motor shaft

Any contact between different metals shall be avoided

Impellers are mounted on self-aligning bearings and greased for life

Bearings shall be dimensioned for a minimum service life (L₁₀ according to ISO 281-1) of 40,000 hours of operation at maximum speed

The fan motor unit shall be statically and dynamically balanced in accordance with ISO 14694 and ISO 1940-1, class G: 2.5

The impeller and the blades are made of:

- Aluminum
- Fiber reinforced material

Reaction to fire class of plastics: min. B-s1,do

> Air cooled heat exchanger

Compliance: EN 14276

The following constructions are authorized:

- Fin-and-tube: copper tubes, aluminum fins
- Micro-channels: entirely in aluminum

The air flow through the exchanger is ensured by one or more fans which are part of the device itself

Coating (only applicable if specified in the article of the specified device itself): the surface of the heat exchangers shall also be protected by a coating system in accordance with EN ISO 12944-5 (durability class H: more than 15 years) although the uncoated material may already meet the required corrosion environment class

The corrosion environment class is defined below in the item of the specified device itself

The heat exchanger shall be able to be drained

> Frame

>> General

All components are mounted on a solid frame made of steel profiles or on a self-supporting construction in which the different elements are fixed to each other

>> Anti-vibration measures

Devices with rotating elements shall always be installed on a raised base:

- Either on a concrete base with a minimum thickness of 8 cm, the edge of which is protected by an angle profile 50 x 50 x 5 mm
- Either on a metallic structure in stainless steel (min. EN 1.4301)

Anti-vibration elements shall be placed between the base and the device; their characteristics shall meet the acoustic requirements

>> Noise reduction

When the acoustic conditions require it, the device shall be fitted with a soundproof box

The box is either made of removable metal panels, coated inside with sound absorption material or is double-walled

All control and signaling devices shall remain visible and freely accessible

The non-combustible sound absorption material in the box, in the noise attenuators and in the screens (class A2 according to EN 13501-1) shall be durable, rot-proof and vermin-resistant; it is also provided with the necessary means of protection to prevent it from eroding and becoming wet in the event of rain

The panels shall be removable while the hydraulic and electrical connections are operational

> Control panel

Compliance: EN 61439 (series)

The panel is completely wired, connected to the compressor and its accessories and tested in the manufacturer's factory

Components:

- A switch-disconnector with padlock acting as an emergency stop
- Short circuit protection
- Overload protection

> Controls

The device is equipped with microprocessor control unit

The control unit is installed in the control panel of the device

Each device shall be fitted with a potential-free contact, which, by means of an external signal, can prevent the device from operating

In the case of several devices connected in parallel, the control system shall be able to operate in cascade; the regulation of at least one device shall be configured as master, or the contractor shall provide an additional master regulator

A dip in the mains voltage causes an ordered shutdown of the device and, when the mains voltage returns, an automatic start-up

Components:

- Electronic control unit
- Fluid temperature sensor (outlet/return)

Functions:

- Fan speed regulation as a function of the measured outlet temperature
- Control of operating parameters
- Alarm signaling

> BMS interface

The control unit is provided by default with a BACnet (IP or SC) or Modbus interface

> Nameplate

The device is equipped with a nameplate in durable material and whose inscriptions are indelible

The plate is securely spun in an easily accessible and visible place

It bears at least the following indications:

- Name of manufacturer
- Model and serial number
- Year of manufacture
- Type and quantity of refrigerant
- Thermal capacity for nominal conditions
- Temperatures at nominal conditions
- Nominal voltage
- Maximum current

> Performance criteria

Corrosion environment according to EN ISO 9223: C₃

System fluid: propylene glycol 25%

Min. number of heat exchangers (coils): [optional]

Min. number of circuits: [optional]

Approximate dimensions:

- Length: ___ mm
- Width: ___ mm
- Height: ___ mm

Nominal operating conditions:

- Outdoor air (inlet/outlet): 35 °C
- System fluid (inlet/outlet): 45/40 °C

Nominal useful heat exchange capacity: ___ kW

Max current (according to nameplate): ___ A

Max sound power : ___ dB(A)

Execution:

> Access area

An access area for maintenance shall be provided

The width of the access area shall be at least equal to that prescribed by the device manufacturer

Overlap: it is accepted that the access area of a device overlaps the access area of an adjacent device without, however, overlapping the horizontal projection of this other device

> Hydraulic connections

The hydraulic connections are made:

- Either by means of Victaulic couplings
- Either by means of flange connections
- Either by means of 3-piece threaded fittings (up to DN 40 max.)

03 Ground (geothermal) heat exchangers

Specifications:

The pressure drop between the vertical geothermal heat exchanger and the collector shall not exceed 0.2 bar

Execution:

The connections between the vertical geothermal heat exchangers and the collector shall be made by means of PE pipes having the same characteristics as the pipes in the exchangers

All flow and return piping from vertical geothermal heat exchangers will be collected in 2 collector chambers where they will be connected to the collector

The pipes are installed with the slope towards the collector

03.01 U-tube heat exchangers

03.01.01 U-tube heat exchanger

Note:

The depth of a vertical geothermal heat exchanger is defined as the distance between the foot and the head of the probe; this only takes into account the part of the probe which is in contact with the grout

Material:

Geothermal probes

Grout

Spacers

Work:

Realization of vertical boreholes

Installation of piping

Pressure test with report

Rinsing

Grout injection

Disposal of drill cuttings

Removal of the surface finishing layer

Submittals:

Before execution:

- Technical data sheet: see specifications
- Certificate of the filling material used (grout)

After execution:

- Tightness and resistance test report
- Flow test report
- Drilling report

Specifications:

> *General*

Compliance: EN ISO 17628 chapter 5

Type: **single/double** vertical U-loop (2/4 vertical pipes per probe)

Space between boreholes: see plans

Configuration (layout): see plans

Hydraulic connection of vertical geothermal heat exchangers on collectors:

- EITHER all vertical geothermal heat exchangers are connected in parallel on the collector
- EITHER (up to) X vertical exchangers in a group are connected in series with each other; the groups are connected in parallel on the collector
- EITHER according to plans/schematics

> *Boreholes*

Borehole diameter: 130 mm

Borehole depth: depending on quantity

Number of boreholes: according to quantity

Drilling technique to be used:

- EITHER hydraulic drilling
- EITHER downhole hammer drilling
- EITHER to be defined by the contractor according to the geological profile

Sampling:

- EITHER required
- EITHER if required by the local regulations

> Geothermal probes

@ Data sheet

[Option: PN16 standard pipes]

>> Pipes

Concerns: the vertical piping of the exchanger (probes)

Conformity :

- Pipes in general: EN 12201-2
- PE100-RC pipes: [NBN T 42-116 or equivalent](#)

Material: PE100-RC

Dimensions: d32 x 2.9 mm (SDR11)

Service pressure: 16 bar (safety factor 1.25)

Service temperature: -20 to +40 ° C

Lifespan: 50 years

[Option: PN35 high pressure pipes]

>> Pipes

Concerns: the vertical piping of the exchanger (probes)

Conformity :

- pipes in general: NBN EN 12201-2
- PE100-RC pipes: [NBN T 42-116 or equivalent](#)

Material and construction (interior to exterior):

- PE100-RC layer
- Metal layer
- PE100-RC layer

Dimensions: d42 x 3.5 mm

Service pressure: 16 bar (safety factor 1.25)

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Service temperature: -20 to +40 °C

Lifespan: 50 years

>> Foot

The pipes are factory-welded to the foot

Designed to be able to support ballasting

Provided with a dirt retention volume

>> Ballast

Material: structural steel S235JR / S355J or equivalent

Weight: to be defined by the contractor

> Grout

@ Data sheet

Type: frost resistant cement grout

Thermal conductivity: min. 2.0 W/(mK)

Permeability: max. 10E-09 m/s

Execution:

> General

Compliance: EN ISO 17628 chapter 5

The contractor is himself responsible for the supply of water and energy necessary to be able to carry out the work

A water connection is available at the construction site

> Realization of vertical wells

The underground conditions are considered to be known by the contractor and cannot give rise to any additional cost

Drilling work may not start before the delivery of vertical heat exchanger piping to the site, because the piping shall be installed no later than 24 hours after drilling

Throughout the execution of the work, the contractor shall provide protection to avoid damaging the boreholes and preventing the intrusion of foreign matter

- The driller shall take all the necessary precautions to prevent contamination of the groundwater by runoff, unwanted water from another groundwater layer, gasoline or other contaminant
- The driller shall take all the necessary precautions to channel the water extracted from the boreholes in order to prevent the blocking of sumps and sewers, or the contamination of water bodies; it shall create a temporary settling tank from which surface water is pumped
- A continuous protection of the location of boreholes shall be ensured so as to prevent future activities from affecting the performance of the well, both quantitatively and qualitatively
- The contractor shall ensure the verticality of the drilling over its entire depth: the borehole shall be sufficiently straight and vertical (89.5° to 90.5°) so as not to interfere with the installation of the probe and future filling
- The contractor shall seal the head of boreholes with a tight flanged cover fitted with a gasket

> Installation of piping

- During storage, pipes and accessories may not be exposed to direct solar radiation
- The ends of the pipes shall be sealed with a plug until the moment of installation
- Apart from the pipe joints at the bottom and top of the vertical probes, no joints are allowed

> Pressure test

- The pressure test of the vertical heat exchanger probes shall be carried out before the installation into the boreholes
- Each vertical probe shall be tested separately
- The piping shall be filled with water, tested under pressure to check its integrity and tightness, then sealed

> Grout injection

- Sufficient storage capacity shall be provided to minimize or avoid injection in sequences

03.02 Manifold chambers

03.02.01 Prefabricated PE manifold chamber

Material:

Prefabricated manifold chambers

Work:

Supply and installation

Submittals:

Technical data sheet: see specifications

Specifications:

> Prefabricated manifold chamber

>> General

@ Data sheet

The manifold chamber is made up of a PE housing, manifolds and connection fittings on the outside of the chamber, ready to be connected to the distribution circuits to the vertical geothermal heat exchangers and the building

The casing of the manifold chamber as well as the connections passing through its wall are made in a completely waterproof manner

Outside the manifold chamber, a sufficient length of pipe is provided per connection to make the connection to the distribution pipes by means of electrofusion sleeves

The chamber is fully equipped at the factory with all necessary regulating and shut-off valves

Manifolds are installed and pressure tested, including external connections for piping

The chamber is equipped with a manhole with waterproof cover

An access ladder shall be provided if the depth exceeds 0.80 m

The exact position of the fitting outlet for the piping shall be defined by the contractor

The manifold chamber is large enough to be accessible for maintenance of the manifold elements (min. 0.6 x 0.8 m)

Max. working pressure : 6 bar

Operating temperature: -20 to +50 °C

Number of connections per manifold: [specify](#)

>> Housing

Material and construction:

- Housing: PE-HD
- Cover: round, d600 mm, in PE-HD

Cover class according to EN 124: [A15 \(1500 kg\)](#)

>> Manifolds

Material and construction:

- 1 stop valve per supply connection
- 1 stop and balancing valve per return connection
- 1 pressure gauge per manifold
- 1 drain valve per manifold
- 1 stop valve per manifold
- 1 purge and rinse valve per manifold

Spacing between connections: min. 130 mm

Execution:

The manifold chamber shall represent the highest point of the geothermal installation (at least with regard to the part outside the building)

The manifold chamber is installed so that it does not rise in the event of a rise in the water table

The level of the cover shall be at the same level as the ground level

The installation shall be carried out according to the manufacturer's instructions

The chamber shall be installed on solid and flat ground

03.03 Thermal response tests (TRT)

03.03.01 Conventional thermal response test (TRT)

Work:

Thermal response test (TRT)

Submittals:

After execution:

- Test report

Specifications:

> Test report

Compliance: EN ISO 17628

Measurement data shall also be transferred electronically in CSV or Excel format

Execution:

> Thermal response test (TRT)

Compliance: EN ISO 17628

The test will be carried out on a vertical geothermal heat exchanger already carried out on the site (depth ___ m)

Result: the test shall lead to the determination of the following properties:

- Average thermal conductivity of the soil (W/(mK))
- Thermal resistance of the average borehole ((mK)/W)
- Average undisturbed soil temperature (°C)

The average volumetric thermal capacity of the soil necessary for the determination of the drilling resistance shall be estimated by the driller according to the soil samples that will be taken during the drilling

03.03.02 Distributed thermal response test (DTRT)

Work:

Thermal response test (TRT)

Submittals:

After execution:

- Test report

Specifications:

> Test report

Compliance: EN ISO 17628

Measurement data shall also be transferred electronically in CSV or Excel format

Execution:

> *Distributed thermal response test (DTRT)*

Compliance: the test installation is based in principle on that described in EN ISO 17628; however, the temperature shall be measured across the entire depth of the vertical heat exchanger by means of a distributed temperature sensor comprising an optical cable and a central measurement and data processing unit

Result: the test shall lead to the determination of the following properties:

- The vertical profile of the thermal conductivity of the ground (W/(mK)) for each vertical meter of the geothermal heat exchanger (resolution min. 1 m)
- The average thermal resistance of the borehole ((mK)/W)
- Vertical profile of undisturbed soil temperature (°C)

The average volumetric thermal capacity of the soil necessary for the determination of the drilling resistance shall be estimated by the driller according to the soil samples that were taken during the drilling

The test will be carried out on a vertical geothermal heat exchanger already carried out on the site (depth ___ m)

The theoretical context of the test is described in the following scientific article (see section 2.1 - Distributed thermal response test (DTRT)): Wilke S., et al.

Advanced thermal response tests: A review. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews 119, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.109575>

Any approach described in the abovementioned article can be used provided the test yields the required properties

04 Plate heat exchangers

04.01 Brazed plate heat exchangers

Material:

Brazed plate heat exchanger

Removable insulating shell

Base support

Work:

Supply and installation

Submittals:

Technical data sheets: see specifications

Selection note

Specifications:

> Brazed plate heat exchanger

@ Data sheet

Type: counter-current, single pass, [single/double-wall](#)

Material :

- Plates: stainless steel EN 1.4401
- Brazing: copper

Service pressure: min. 16 bar

Service temperature : min. -10 °C to + 95 °C

Transfer capacity reserve: min. 10%

Heat transfer capacity: ___ kW

Warm side:

- Fluid: [water/glycol __%](#)
- Temperature (inlet / outlet): [_/_](#) °C
- Maximum pressure drop: [0.2](#) bar

Cold side:

- Fluid: [water/glycol __%](#)
- Temperature (inlet/outlet): [_/_](#) °C
- Maximum pressure drop: [0.2](#) bar

> Base support

Material: powder-coated galvanized steel sheet

04.02 Gasketed plate heat exchanger

Material:

Gasketed plate heat exchanger

Removable insulating shell

Floor mounting feet

Work:

Supply and installation

Submittals:

Technical data sheets: see specifications

Selection note

Specifications:

> Gasketed plate heat exchanger

@ Data sheet

Type: counter-current, single pass, [single/double](#)-wall

Material :

- Plates: stainless steel EN 1.4401
- Frame: powder-coated galvanized steel sheet

Service pressure: min. 16 bar

Service temperature : min. -10 °C to + 95 °C

Transfer capacity reserve: min. 10%

Heat transfer capacity: ___ kW

Warm side:

- Fluid: [water/glycol ___%](#)
- Temperature (inlet / outlet): [_/_](#) °C
- Maximum pressure drop: [0.2](#) bar

Cold side:

- Fluid: [water/glycol ___%](#)
- Temperature (inlet/outlet): [_/_](#) °C
- Maximum pressure drop: [0.2](#) bar

> Floor mounting feet

Material: powder-coated galvanized steel sheet

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05 Thermally activated building structures (TABS)

05.01 TABS pipes and modules

Specifications:

> General

A heating and/or cooling system by means of pipes installed in the core of concrete slabs in accordance with EN ISO 11855

All system elements shall come from a single manufacturer

> Sizing

The sizing of the system is carried out by the contractor according to the material offered

The sizing shall comply with EN ISO 11855-4

The following criteria apply:

- Max pressure drop of a circuit: 20 kPa
- Max speed in pipes: 0.5 m/s
- Flow temperatures:
 - Heating: ___ °C
 - Cooling: ___ °C

> Guarantee certificate

Concerns: execution and material

Duration: 10 years from provisional acceptance

The warranty certificate shall include a written declaration from the manufacturer or his representative in which he declares that the installation has been carried out entirely in accordance with the installation instructions and the rules of good practice

Execution:

Before execution, submit calculations and construction drawings with:

- Indication of pipe diameter and spacing
- Pipe layout in view
- Total length per area

- Flow rate, temperature differential and pressure drop per circuit

The execution shall comply with the manufacturer's installation instructions and EN ISO 11855-5

Pipes are installed in the concrete slab at regular distances

Pouring of the slab can only take place after the successful completion of the pressure test

During the pouring and drying of the slab pipes shall be permanently under a pressure of 2 bar

At the crossings of the expansion joints and the connections to the manifolds, pipes shall be protected by protection hoses

The contractor is advised to carry out the pressure test and keep the pipes under pressure during and after the pouring of the tiles with compressed air instead of water in order to avoid possible damage caused by frozen water at negative outside temperatures

05.01.01 In situ installed pipes

Material:

Multilayer PE pipes

Fastening material

Protection hoses (expansion joints traversal)

Ceiling lead-through elements

Work:

Supply and installation

Pressure test with report

Rinsing

Photographing of pipe layout traces

Submittals:

Before execution:

- Technical data sheets: see specifications

After execution:

- Warranty certificate
- Leak test report
- Pictures

Specifications:

> Multilayer PE pipes

@ Data sheet

Compliance: EN ISO 21003-2

Material and construction (interior to exterior):

- PE-X layer
- Aluminum layer, min. 0.2mm or EVOH membrane
- PE-X layer

Application class (temperature): class 4 according to EN ISO 21003-2

Oxygen diffusion class: min. class 4 according to EN ISO 15875

Service pressure: 10 bar

Pipe diameter: ____ mm

[To be included if applicable]

> Wire mesh

@ Data sheet

Construction :

- Steel wire mesh
- Plastic pipe fixing clips

Steel wire: zinc galvanized

Possible installation spacing: 5 to 35 cm

Steel wire thickness: min. 3 mm

05.01.02 Prefabricated TABS pipe modules

Material:

Prefabricated TABS pipe modules

Fastening material

Protection hoses (expansion joints traversal)

Ceiling lead-through elements

Work:

Supply and installation
Pressure test with report
Rinsing
Photographing of pipe layout traces

Submittals:

Before execution:

- Technical data sheets: see specifications

After execution:

- Warranty certificate
- Leak test report
- Pictures

Specifications:

> Prefabricated TABS pipe modules

@ Data sheet

>> Multilayer PE pipes

Compliance: EN ISO 21003-2

Material and construction (interior to exterior):

- PE-X layer
- Aluminum layer, min. 0.2mm or EVOH membrane
- PE-X layer

Application class (temperature): class 4 according to EN ISO 21003-2

Oxygen diffusion class: min. class 4 according to EN ISO 15875

Service pressure: 10 bar

Pipe diameter: ___ mm

>> Wire mesh

@ Data sheet

Construction :

- Steel wire mesh
- Plastic pipe fixing clips

Steel wire: zinc galvanized

Possible installation spacing: 5 to 35 cm

Steel wire thickness: min. 3 mm

>> Fittings

Compliance: EN ISO 21003-3

Material: synthetic material or metal

Equipped with a bad press control system

05.02 TABS manifolds

05.02.01 TABS manifold

Material:

Always included in a set of manifolds:

- Supply and return manifold
- Couple of wall supports with fixing material
- Two ball valves at the head of the manifolds
- **Manifold cabinet**

Work:

Supply and installation

Circuit balancing

Submittals:

Before execution:

- Technical data sheet: see specifications

After execution:

- Balancing report

Specifications:

> General

@ Data sheet

Max. service pressure : 10 bar

Service temperature: +5 to +95 °C

> Supply and return manifold

Authorized materials: brass, bronze, stainless steel

Number of connections per manifold: 2 to 12

Diameter:

- manifold: 1"
- connections: 3/4"

Connection spacing: 50 mm

Every connection of the supply manifold is equipped with a flow meter and a balancing valve

Every connection of the return manifold is equipped with shut-off valve that can be fitted with an electro-thermic actuator

A connector for connecting plastic pipes (PE-X or multilayer) per connection

A supply and drain valve per manifold

A manual lockable air vent per manifold

Marking to distinguish the supply and return manifold

Number of connections per collector: [to be defined](#)

> Wall supports with fixing material

Material: galvanized sheet steel

For mounting on the wall or in a cabinet

Noise isolation: according to [DIN 4109 or equivalent](#)

> Ball valves

Compliance: EN 13828

Material and construction:

- Brass or bronze body
- Brass or chrome-plated bronze ball
- O-ring in EPDM or FKM
- PTFE ball seals

Noise (EN ISO 3822): group I

> Manifold cabinet

Material: sheet steel, powder coated, min. 1.5mm

White color

With door and cylinder lock

Execution: recessed / surface-mounted [choose]

Dimensions: to be defined

Execution:

> Connections

The connections to manifolds of the distribution piping shall always be installed in the direction of the piping layout

Each circuit is connected to its own manifold connection

> Balancing report

The contractor shall carry out a detailed calculation of pressure losses in the network; this calculation shall lead to a value of the differential pressure available at nominal service conditions at the point of the system where the manifold is installed

The calculation shall be made for each manifold individually

The contractor shall determine for each branch the setting of the balancing valve; he shall take into account the available differential pressure, the desired flow and the diameter and length of the pipes

Important: if the contractor chooses manifolds with pressure independent balancing valves, the detailed calculation does not have to be performed; in this case it is sufficient to determine the adjustment position of the valve of each connection according to the required flow using the diagram available in the installation instructions of the balancing valve

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06 Fan coils

Specification:

> General

Compliance: EN 16430 part 1 to 3

All fan coil units of one type shall come from the same manufacturer; all components are factory compatible

Operating pressure of all system components: min. 10 bar

All fan coil units are designed for a two-pipe system

> Heating and cooling capacity

Compliance: EN 1397

The calorific values indicated in the tender documents correspond to the power supplied at the project design conditions

The equipment proposed by the contractor shall be capable of supplying the required heat capacity (cooling and/or heating) at the middle fan speed (max. 6 V in the case of EC motors)

> Dimensions

The contractor shall check in advance the possibility of installation on site and take into account any changes to the tender documents

Unless explicitly stated otherwise, the lengths indicated in the project are indicative; however, the accepted deviations are limited to the following values provided that all the relevant rules of good practice are observed:

- Length or width:
 - Up to and including 1000 mm: 5%
 - From 1000 mm: 10%
- Depth or height: 5%

As regards larger deviations, the contracting authority reserves the right to refuse them without justification

In any case, the installation of the devices is not authorized without prior approval of the dimensions by the contracting authority

The contractor shall submit to the contracting authority a complete list of fan coil units; this list shall include at least the following information (per device):

- Room number
- Room name
- Heat loss and/or gain
- Fan coil dimensions according to the tender documents

- Fan coil power according to the tender documents
- Fan coil dimensions according to the construction documents
- Fan coil power according to the construction documents
- Difference in dimensions between tender and construction (yes, no)

> Fan coil units

>> Fin and tube heat exchangers

Material: copper tubes and aluminum fins

Test pressure: min. 25 bar

Screw connections

>> Motors

Type: only EC type motors (single-phase synchronous motor with permanent magnets) with ball bearings are authorized

Speed regulation: continuous via an external 0 to 10 V signal

Insulation class min.: class B (130 to 155 °C)

Efficiency: min. IE4 according to EN 60034-30-1

In case of motor failure (e.g. overheating), the fan will stop automatically

Execution:

> Supply

Fan coil units for surface installation are supplied in a wear-resistant package (one per device); they are kept in this packaging until provisional acceptance; they shall be intact at this time

The replacement of damaged units is carried out at the expense of the contractor after contradictory expertise

> Installation

The installation of units shall always be coordinated with the equipment other trades; the coordination shall be performed on plans; these plans shall be submitted to the contracting authority for approval

After installation, the fastening of the unit shall no longer be visible

Units suspended from ceiling are fitted with at least 4 suspension points

All costs relating to the supply and installation of units, fasteners, supports, etc. shall be included in the unit price of the device
A modification of the location of devices in relation to the location indicated on the plans within a radius of 2 meters, due to the proximity of obstacles (e.g. lights), cannot give rise to an additional cost
Each possible gap shall be completely masked by the grill of the unit or the finish of the wall, floor or ceiling

> Connection pipes

The connection of devices by means of flexible EPDM (or equivalent) hoses reinforced with stainless steel braid is prohibited
The price for the connecting pipes shall be included in the price of the piping

> Fittings (wall units without feet)

The connection shall always be made from the wall; there shall be no visible pipe parts

> Visible fixing parts

The exposed fasteners shall be painted in the same color and quality (as regards heat resistance, color quality and degree of finish) as the painting of the fan coil unit

> Installation openings

Before installation, all the necessary information shall be collected by the contractor in order to cut openings in the wall, floor and ceiling structures, or to modify them, in order to obtain a system in working order
The contractor takes into account in his price offer the making of openings for the installation of units

06.01 Fan coil unit for concealed installation

Material:

Fan coil
Installation material

Work:

Supply and installation

Documents:

Technical data sheet: see specifications

Specifications:

> *Fan coil*

@ Data sheet

Description: fan coil without casing for concealed installation in construction voids

Material and construction:

- Mounting frame made of galvanized sheet steel, insulated against surface condensation
- Fin and tube tubular heat exchanger
- Air purge and drain valve per heat exchanger
- Centrifugal or tangential fans
- Condensate tray in rust resistant material
- Removable and washable filter

Electrical connection: 1 x 230 V, 50 Hz

Max. working pressure: 10 bar

Max. installation depth: ___ mm

No. of heat exchangers: ___

BMS interface:

- 1x AI: fan speed

Performance - heating:

- Water temperature regime (flow/return): ___ °C
- Room temperature: ___ °C
- Sensible heating capacity: ___ W

Performance - cooling:

- water temperature regime (flow/return): ___ °C
- room temperature: ___ °C
- relative humidity: ___%
- Total cooling capacity: ___ W
- Sensible cooling capacity: ___ W

06.02 Fan coil unit with metal casing for exposed installation

Material:

Fan coil

Installation material

Work:

Supply and installation

Documents:

Technical data sheet: see specifications

Specifications:

> Fan coil

@ Data sheet

Description: fan coil with metal casing for exposed installation

Material and construction:

- Rectangular shaped casing composed of:
 - Flat finishing panel on the front side
 - Closed flat finish panels on the lateral sides
 - A fitting aluminum grille on top
 - Panels and grille forming a whole with the fan coil
 - Entirely powder coated in the same color
 - Folded galvanized sheet steel panels, min. 1.25mm
- Mounting frame made of galvanized sheet steel
- Fin and tube heat exchanger
- Air purge and drain valve per heat exchanger
- Centrifugal or tangential fans
- Condensate tray in rust resistant material
- Removable and washable filter

- Concealed wall connections
- Integrated electronic control thermostat

Paint (casing): primer paint + powder coating finish

Color: RAL 9010 or RAL 9016 (white)

Finish: satin look, finely structured

Electrical connection: 1 x 230 V, 50 Hz

Max. working pressure: 10 bar

Max. installation depth: ___ mm

No. of heat exchangers: ___

BMS interface:

- 1x AI: fan speed

Performance - heating:

- Water temperature regime (flow/return): ___ °C
- Room temperature: ___ °C
- Sensible heating capacity: ___ W

Performance - cooling:

- water temperature regime (flow/return): ___ °C
- room temperature: ___ °C
- relative humidity: ___%
- Total cooling capacity: ___ W
- Sensible cooling capacity: ___ W

06.03 Fan-assisted radiator for exposed installation

Material:

Fan-assisted radiator

Installation material

Work:

Supply and installation

Documents:

Technical data sheet: see specifications

Specifications:

> Fan-assisted radiator

@ Data sheet

Description: hybrid radiator with forced convection by means of axial fans for horizontal wall installation (vertical air supply)

Compliance: EN 442-1

Material and construction:

- Water conducting panels with concealed convection fins
- Battery of axial fans in horizontal plane above the convection fins
- Fans are installed on a bogie and can be pulled-out laterally for maintenance after removing a side panel
- Flat cover plate on the front side
- Fully welded construction, with no visible welds
- Without convection fins on the outside
- Flat closed finish panels on the lateral sides
- A fitting grille on top
- panels and grid forming a whole with the radiator
- Fully powder coated in the same color
- Integrated electronic control thermostat
- Motorized control valve with preset kv value

Hydraulic connections: 2x at the base of the radiator, centered

Paint: primer paint + powder coat finish

Color: RAL 9010 or RAL 9016 (white)

Electrical connection: 1 x 230 V, 50 Hz

Max. working pressure : 10 bar

Value of exponent n (at maximum speed): min 1.1

Performance - heating:

- Water temperature regime (flow/return): ___ °C
- Room temperature: ___ °C

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- Sensible heating capacity: ___ W

Performance - cooling:

- water temperature regime (flow/return): ___ °C
- room temperature: ___ °C
- Sensible cooling capacity: ___ W

07 Electronic variable air volume (VAV) controllers

07.01 Round/rectangular electronic VAV controller

Material:

Round/rectangular electronic VAV controller

Round/rectangular noise attenuator

Work:

Supply and installation

Flow adjustment at the control unit

Setting of the actual site altitude

Submittals:

Technical data sheet: according to specifications

Selection note

Specifications:

> Electronic VAV controller

@ Data sheet

>> Casing with flow rate sensor and control damper

Material :

- Casing: galvanized sheet steel
- Damper: galvanized sheet steel or aluminum
- Differential pressure sensor: aluminum
- Insulation: min. 50 mm mineral wool, reaction to fire: min. A₂(L) -s₁; do

Measuring range: 1.0 to 6.0 m/s

Max pressure drop at design flow (with open damper): 10 Pa

Dynamic control range (minimum/design flow rate): min. 1/3

Casing air leakage according to EN 1751:

- Rectangular casing: class B
- Round casing: class C

Blade air leakage according to EN 1751:

- Rectangular casing: class 3
- Round casing:
 - Class 2: d80 to 100 mm
 - Class 3: d125 to 160 mm
 - Class 4: d200 and above

Maximum straight duct length required:

- Upstream: 3 x equivalent diameter
- Downstream: 1.5 x equivalent diameter

Measurement accuracy:

- Min. 20% at minimum adjustable flow
- Min. 10% at maximum adjustable flow

Operating temperature: +10 to +50 ° C

Adjustment of the flow rate setpoint on the outside of the casing

Adjustment remains accessible from the outer side of the casing after mounting and insulation (up to 50 mm of insulation thickness)

Connection to ducts:

- Rectangular ducts according to EN 1505: with flanges
- Round ducts according to EN 1506: with EPDM gasket

Meets hygienic requirements according to [VDI 6022 or equivalent](#)

Factory tested

Independent of mounting position

Maintenance free

Max. differential operating pressure : [500 Pa](#)

>> [Control unit with servomotor](#)

@ [Data sheet](#)

Control and diagnostic functions:

- Choice between constant or variable flow regulation

- Min. and max. flow rate setting
- Display of actual flow rate
- Command: damper closed/open position
- Command: damper at max./min. position

Operating principle:

- Flow measurement: via differential pressure or ultrasonic sensor
- Constant flow rate control regardless of pressure variations in the duct

Aluminum casing

Connection cable 1 m

Mechanical position display

Manual control possible

Conditions of service:

- Temperature: 5 to +40 °C
- Relative humidity: 10 to 90% (non-condensing)

Maintenance free

Supply voltage: 24 V AC/DC

Protection index: min. IP54

Protection class: III

Running time: max. 300 s

BMS interface:

- Control signal: 0/2-10 V (adjustable: flow rate, damper position, pressure differential)
- Return signal: 0/2-10 V (adjustable: flow rate, damper position, pressure difference)

> Sound attenuator

>> General

@ Data sheet

Absorption material:

- Material: mineral wool
- Reaction to fire: min. A2 (L) -s1; do

Attenuation at 6.0 m/s (Lw): min. 10 dB (A) at 250 Hz

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Insulation thickness: 50 mm

Casing air leakage according to EN 1751: min. class B

Max. working pressure: 600 Pa

>> For connection to round units

Casing and perforated inner sheath: galvanized sheet steel

Connection to ducts: according to EN 1506 with gasket

> For connection to rectangular units

Type: with splitters

Casing and splitter frame: galvanized sheet steel

Connection to ducts: according to EN 1505 with flanges

Execution:

An inspection hatch shall be installed in the immediate vicinity of the air flow controller

08 Buried horizontal geothermal pipes

Specifications:

> General

The system as a whole shall offer, after completion, total protection against humidity, water infiltration, mechanical, chemical and electrical actions

> Connections

Pipe connections between pipes and fittings have to be :

- Waterproof
- Able to withstand the axial forces generated by the axial movements of the pipes in the ground
- Able to resist radial forces and bending movements
- Able to withstand the effects of temperature and temperature fluctuations

Execution:

> General

Pipes shall be in one piece; buried connections are prohibited when the length does not exceed 80 m

> Penetrations

Penetration of piping through the walls of buildings and inspection chambers is carried out according to the manufacturer's instructions using parts and special seals in order to obtain a watertight assembly

> Laying of pipes

>> Laying in trenches

Pipes are laid on a bed of sand at least 10 cm thick

The trench is backfilled with sand up to a height of 15 cm above the upper edge of the pipe

A warning tape is placed above the pipes

08.01 Pressure test

Work:

pressure test

Submittals:

report

Execution:

> General

Carry out a pressure test on the entire network of buried pipes (refer to section "plastic piping test procedure")

The test shall be carried out before carrying out the backfilling of the trenches

During the test, the buried piping system shall be isolated from the rest of the hydraulic installations

The test can be carried out in phases

> Preparatory work

Before carrying out the tests, the pressurization pump and the pipes are rinsed with potable water and the pipes are completely filled with potable water and purged

Connections and ends of the circuit are closed with plugs

Accessories of the piping system and the other elements of the installation which do not resist the pressure to be applied during the tests shall be disconnected or isolated beforehand

> Test conditions

The installation is subjected to hydraulic pressure p_{test} for a minimum duration of two hours

During the test, no leakage or resistance fault may appear

The pressure is equal to 3 times the maximum operating pressure with a maximum of 10 bar

The test is carried out at room temperature, that is to say without heating or cooling the heat transfer fluid

> Pressurization

The pressure is applied statically; in the case of use of a hand pump, all precautions are taken to avoid the production of water hammer, in particular, by the placement of a device intended to dampen vibrations on the discharge pipe of the pump

The test pressure is read by a pressure gauge connected to the lowest point of the installation's piping

The pressure gauge shall allow a reading with an accuracy of 0.1 bar and have a sufficient measurement range

> Plastic piping test procedure

The test procedure is based on method B of § 10.2.3 of standard CEN/TR 12108

If the loss between p_{t30} and p_{t60} or between p_{t60} and p_{t180} is greater than the authorized value, it is necessary to identify the cause of the leakage of the installation and remedy it, then repeat the procedure from the beginning

08.02 Flexible PE pipes

Material:

Pipes

Fittings for electro-welding

Warning tape

Work:

Supply and installation

Layout of pipes (or pipe placement) according to drawings from manufacturer

Submittals:

Technical data sheets: see specifications

Certification:

10 year warranty

Specifications:

> General

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Operating pressure: 8 bar

Operating temperature: -20 to +30 °C

> Pipes

@ Data sheet

Compliance: EN 12201-2

Material: min. PE80 SDR17

> Electro-welding fittings

@ Data sheet

Compliance: EN 12201-3

09 Solar thermal collectors

09.01 Flat plate solar thermal collectors

Material:

Flat plate solar thermal collectors
Roof mounting structure
Fastening material

Work:

Supply and installation
Hydraulic connection to hot water storage tank

Documents:

Technical data sheet: see specifications
[Keymark certificate + annex \(test report\)](#)

Certification:

[Keymark certification](#)
10 year warranty certificate

Specifications:

> Flat plate solar thermal collectors

@ Data sheet

Compliance: EN 12975-1

Testing method: EN ISO 9806 or EN 12975-2

Material and construction:

- Housing made of corrosion resistant material
- Low iron tempered glass cover plate

- Aluminum or copper absorber with high selectivity coating
- Meandered copper tubes
- Thermal insulation on the rear and side of the absorber

Black color

Connection of collectors in series possible through using internal connectors

Min. number of collector panels that can be connected in one module:

- Connection on one side: ___
- Connection on two sides: ___

Max operating pressure: 6 bar

Max stagnation temperature: ___ °C

Collector efficiency (η_{col}) in accordance with ErP: min. 60 %

Approximate gross dimensions (length x height): ___ x ___ mm

Thermal output ($G = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2$, $T_m - T_a = 30 \text{ K}$): ___ W

Execution:

Installation on a sloping roof by means of rails and anchor rafters or chevron hooks

Recessed into a sloping roof by means of a recessed frame

Installed on a flat roof by means of a supporting structure and necessary ballast

09.02 Evacuated tube solar thermal collectors

Material:

Evacuated tube solar thermal collectors

Mounting material

Fastening material

Work:

Supply and installation

Hydraulic connection to hot water storage tank

Documents:

Technical data sheet: see specifications
[Keymark certificate + annex \(test report\)](#)

Certification:

[Keymark certification](#)

10 year warranty certificate

Specifications:

> Evacuated tube solar thermal collectors

@ Data sheet

Compliance: EN 12975-1

Testing method: EN ISO 9806 or EN 12975-2

Material and construction:

- Vacuum tube
- Heat pipe
- Absorber
- Condenser
- Heat exchanger

Connection of collectors in series possible through using internal connectors

Min. number of collector panels that can be connected in one module: ____

Max operating pressure: 6 bar

Max stagnation temperature: ____ °C

Collector efficiency (η_{col}) in accordance with ErP: [min. 60 %](#)

Approximate gross dimensions (length x height): ____ x ____ mm

Number of tubes per collector: ____

Thermal output ($G = 1000 \text{ W/m}^2, T_m - T_a = 30 \text{ K}$): ____ W

Execution:

[Installation on a sloping roof by means of rails and anchor rafters or chevron hooks](#)

[Recessed into a sloping roof by means of a recessed frame](#)

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Installed on a flat roof by means of a supporting structure and necessary ballast

10 Control and automation systems

10.1 General

Note:

A hybridGEOTABS building is a building with advanced technical systems. Such systems add an additional layer of complexity to control and automation systems. Without proper quality control management, a performance gap between the design intent and measured energy use is very likely to appear. Usually, the largest share of responsibility for the performance gap stems from the problems with the control and automation system.

In order to avoid the quality gap, the contractor shall be contractually obliged to participate in the quality control process as this usually involves additional labor to be provided by the latter. In the absence of the contractual obligation, it cannot be realistically expected that the contractor will participate in the process on a voluntary basis. Since specifications represent a contractual obligation, it is important that they include all the necessary provisions that bound the contractor to the full participation in the process.

The following template of the specification text outlines some clauses that can be added to the specification in order to assure full participation of the contractor in the quality management process. They can also be used even if no strictly defined quality management process is followed. It is important to adapt the template to suit the local legislation and building practice. Some deliverables that are supposed to be submitted by the contractor according to the proposed specification may in fact be part of the services that shall be provided by the designer. It is important to understand that in some EU member states, execution design is performed by the contractor and not by the design office. This specification was written supposing such local practice. If needed, requirements that are part of the services provided by the design office can simply be removed.

10.1.1 Direct Digital Control (DDC) system

The contractor shall supply and install a complete Direct Digital Control (DDC) Building Automation System (BAS) as required to accomplish the sequences of control for heating, ventilating, air-conditioning and other building-level equipment and systems as described herein.

The BAC contractor is responsible for quality assurance for all materials and workmanship provided under this specification.

10.1.2 Project sequence

The control system work shall proceed in the following order:

- Submit and receive approval on submittals
- Install the control system hardware, including all checkouts and tuning
- Submit and receive approval of the commissioning plan
- Perform the commissioning testing
- Submit and receive approval on the commissioning report
- Perform the trial operation
- Receive approval of the trial operation
- Submit and receive approval on the follow-up surveillance plan
- Engage in the follow-up surveillance
- Receive approval of the follow-up surveillance

10.1.3 Submittals

Pre-submittal meeting:

- The contractor shall convene a pre-submittal meeting with the engineer within one month of the notice to proceed.
- The purpose of this meeting is to review sequences of operation, outline where the proposed system deviates from the specified sequence of operation, and identify potential problems with the specified sequence.
- Once the sequences of operation are agreed to by all parties, the contractor shall proceed with the formal controls submittal process.

The contractor shall submit the following documents:

- A complete bill of materials of all equipment to be provided and/or used. For every piece of equipment, a unique identifier, manufacturer name and model number shall be provided.
- A riser diagram for each segment of the building technical communication network. The diagram shall outline execution and details of all communication and structural data cabling. The following information shall be included:
 - All DDC hardware with controller number, unique identifier or tag, location, equipment and service
 - All network hardware (routers, switches, etc.) with equipment number, unique identifier, location and service
 - Network cabling configuration and execution specification
 - Location of all cabling termination points and end-of-line terminations
 - Location of all network interface jacks
- A separate equipment data sheet for every piece of equipment being installed. Data sheets shall provide all the information necessary for the engineer to verify their compliance with specifications. At least the following information shall be included:
 - Name and address of the manufacturer

- Shop drawing of the equipment
- List of reference standards
- Mechanical and electrical characteristics
- Dimensions and operational mass
- Details concerning assembly or adjustment
- Wiring diagram and connection schematics
- A control schematics and wiring diagram for every piece of equipment being controlled by and/or associated with the building automation system. At least the following information shall be included:
 - Control schematic flow diagram of each system being controlled showing actual physical configuration and relative location of all control devices and sensors of controlled equipment (e.g. fans, coils, dampers, valves, pumps, heat exchangers, etc.).
 - Controller termination details showing every controller point termination, type and mnemonic.
 - Wiring Diagrams of all packaged equipment, motor starters, relay wiring, equipment interlock, safety circuits, etc. clearly indicating all interconnecting wiring and termination of all conductors and cables including labels of all cables and point mnemonics.
 - Control Enclosure details for every enclosure including panel identifier, location, physical layout, dimensions, instrumentation, labels, etc. Detail wiring (I/O, network and power) and power source for each panel, transformer and controller shall also be included.
- A sequence of operation and state graph and/or table for every piece of equipment being controlled by and/or associated with the building automation system. At least the following information shall be included:
 - Functional control operation. Sequences of operation shall be described in a functional control operation description. The submitted description shall refer to equipment identifiers and tags. The use of generic tags is not permitted. Do not merely provide a copy of the sequence of operation specified in the contract documents, as the engineer will refuse it. The description shall include control sequence operation under normal and failure conditions. All default failback values used by the control sequence under failure conditions shall also be defined.
 - State graph or table is a graphical representation of states, their transitions, transition conditions and actions. System parts using complex logic interlocks involving more than three states shall be treated as finite state machines represented by means of state transfer graphs. An accompanying assignment table listing the state (value) of all associated data points also be provided for clarity if required.

10.1.4 Commissioning

The commissioning shall demonstrate compliance of the control system work with the contract requirements; it shall be performed by the contractor and witnessed and approved by the engineer

The contractor shall submit a detailed commissioning plan that shall be approved by the engineer. The plan shall be developed specifically for the control system in this project. Do not merely provide a generic plan not adapted to this project because the engineer will refuse it.

The plan shall be arranged in a logical sequence. It shall include at least the following:

- Listing of all the intended test procedures (grouped by component type), the expected response, and the pass/fail criteria for every component tested
- Description of the testing procedure; the plan shall also indicate where assisting personnel are required
- Description of procedures used to simulate test conditions
- Time table for all testing procedures

The following verification shall be performed:

- Verify the completion of all installation work according to the specifications, submittals and manufacturer's installation and application instructions
- Verify the installation of all DDC controllers, sensors, switches, and actuators
- Verify the installation of all electric wiring
- Verify all wiring, components, and panels are properly labeled
- Verify all control circuits operate at the proper voltage and are free from grounds or faults
- Verify all required surge and overvoltage protection is installed
- Verify all DDC controllers are on-line and that each controller's programming is backed up
- Verify all required points are wired and programmed into devices
- Verify all network devices' tags/identifications match approved drawings
- Verify all network devices' address matches approved drawings
- Verify all network communications function properly using a communication protocol analyzer tool
- Verify all sensor readings are calibrated
- Verify all actuator zero and span adjustments are set properly
- Verify all actuators' rotation direction is correct
- Verify each actuator goes to designed position upon loss of power
- Verify each controller works properly in stand-alone mode
- Verify all electrical interlocks work properly
- Verify all safety controls work properly
- Verify as-built documents are completed

The contractor shall furnish all personnel, equipment, instrumentation and supplies necessary to perform all aspects of the commissioning tests

Any items that do not meet the contract requirements shall be identified

Immediate repairs and re-testing shall be performed if time permits; otherwise, deficiencies shall be investigated, corrected and re-tested later using initial testing procedures

The engineer may require re-testing of any control system components affected by the original failed test

10.1.4 Trial operation

The trial operation shall demonstrate that the control system operation is fit for continuous independent operation. The duration of the trial operation shall be at least two full weeks.

The contractor shall demonstrate that the HVAC system operates properly through the complete sequence of operation

The contractor shall provide the engineer prior to the start of the trial operation with remote access to the building management system (BMS). The access to the BMS shall allow the engineer to supervise the system operation. He shall be able to change set points to observe control loop stability and accuracy and display trend data of all logged points.

Any sudden change of the control variable set point (20% change) shall result in a stable system response without cycling and excessive undershoot and overshoot. Once the new set point is reached, it shall be stable and maintained.

At the end of each 7-day period of the trial operation (within 24h after the end of each 7-day period), the contractor shall transmit all logged data to the engineer for further analysis. Control loop trend data shall have time interval of maximum 30 seconds.

Upon successful completion of the commissioning, the contractor shall submit a report to the engineer. A report shall not be submitted until all observed problems are corrected and successfully re-tested. Where problems were identified, the contractor shall explain each problem and the corrective action taken.

10.1.5 Provisional acceptance

The provisional acceptance takes place after commissioning testing and trial operation have been completed and approved by the engineer.

10.1.6 Follow-up

A follow-up period of at least two years is foreseen following a successful provisional acceptance. During this phase the contractor is responsible for:

- Resolution of faults resulting from system operation
- Maintenance of all parts of the building automation system
- Transfer of measurement data (trends)
- Leading periodic energy use optimization activities

The contractor shall provide the engineer prior to the start of the follow-up phase with remote access to the building management system (BMS). The access to the BMS shall allow the engineer to supervise the system operation.

Faults:

Any discrepancy between the submitted sequence of operation and the witnessed behavior of the control system is considered a fault:

- All faults identified by the owner or the engineer will be reported to the contractor either by telephone or e-mail. The contractor shall put in place a "hotline" (i.e. 24-hour telephonic support). The contractor shall be responsible that such hotline service be always operational and available. The hotline shall ensure that faults relating to system controls are promptly rectified.
- The contractor shall maintain an updated list of all faults. The list shall be made available to the owner and the engineer. The faults in the list shall be organized in a logic manner. For every item in the list, a status shall be indicated (open, closed, resolved, etc.).
- All faults concerning major comfort and air quality problems (not fulfilling min. requirement of EN 16798-1) are considered urgent and shall be resolved immediately. In the absence of immediate response, the owner may contact another specialized contractor to carry out the necessary work at the expense, risk and peril of the contractor. This intervention by third party does not influence in any way the current warranty.
- All other faults shall be resolved at latest 7 days after they had been reported.

If the submitted sequence of operation appears to be incomplete, the contractor shall supplement and re-submit the document:

- If an operation sequence has been programmed but not described in the submitted document
- If a control sequence has been described in the submitted document but not programmed

Maintenance:

The contractor shall provide maintenance of the control system during the entire duration of the follow-up

The objective is to maintain the serviceability of the of the control system infrastructure in a sustainable manner at the lowest operating and maintenance cost while ensuring compliance to contract specification

For each piece of equipment, all work will be carried out to standards as required by the Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) as well as any applicable government law and/or regulations

Where OEM standards differ from those required by this document the more stringent requirements shall apply

All work shall be carried out in accordance with prevailing industry norms and best practice and will always comply with OEM requirements

The contractor shall continuously ensure that all staff is suitable, able and competent for the duties required of them. He shall continuously ensure that all staff is knowledgeable and trustworthy to provide maintenance of controls system services

The contractor will be expected to attend meetings relating to maintenance and operations that may arise from time to time. As far as this is practicable, the contractor will make all required persons available for these meetings. The contractor shall not submit claims for payment for staff attending any of these meetings.

All work shall be performed within the required response times. Any breakdown affecting operations shall be attended-to until restored to good reliable condition. No breakdown may be left unattended or incomplete for the next day or shift.

Response times and service levels:

- System availability of heat pumps, chillers, boilers: ___ %
- Response time during working hours: ___ min
- Response time after working hours: ___ min
- Closure of corrective work orders: all corrective maintenance work orders should be closed within ___ days of issue unless it is because of circumstances beyond the control of the contractor
- Closure of preventive maintenance work orders should be closed within 14 days of issue

All maintenance work shall be scheduled and a roster presented to the owner at the end of the preceding month. Work shall be scheduled in a manner as not to interfere with any normal building operations.

All maintenance of control systems shall be scheduled, at least at minimum, to the following requirements:

- Daily:
 - Check that the control system and BMS are working
 - Check that sequence of operation is functioning according to design
- Monthly:
 - Check that all sensors linked to the control system are working and replace where necessary
 - Check that the heat generator rotation/sequencing is working and adjust where necessary
 - Check and adjust sequence of operation settings where necessary
 - Download and provide historical data and trends
 - Check and test the fire detection signal relay
 - Check and test that all control valves are functioning within specification
 - Check and test all temperature sensors status
 - Test all emergency stop interlocks
 - Check all energy meter readings
 - Check for controller security updates and install them
- Yearly:
 - Re-calibrate all sensors
 - Check the backup of all controllers

Trends:

The contractor shall periodically transfer the recorded data of all measured points to the engineer for analysis.

The transfer shall take place at the end of each month and shall contain data for the entire calendar month. The data shall be sent by e-mail in an attached *.csv file format.

The file name shall contain the start date of logging (YYYY-MM-DD) and the name of the building.

Energy use optimization activities:

The contractor shall take the leading role in managing the energy use optimization activities:

- Analysis of trends
- Periodic meetings with the engineer and owner
- Optimization of operation sequences
- Controller reprogramming

Meetings shall take place:

- Monthly during the first 6 months of the follow-up phase
- Bi-monthly during months 6-12 of the follow-up phase
- Quarterly during months 12-24 of the follow-up phase

The goal of energy optimization meetings is to:

- Verify that the sequences of operation work properly in all seasons of the year
- Compare the measured energy use trends with the anticipated and benchmark values
- Discuss energy use optimization strategies

The trends to be analyzed during meetings and related issues are raised by the engineer and building owner at latest 7 days before the meeting takes place. The contractor may include additional trends if required

During the meeting, the contractor takes notes and sends a meeting report at the latest 7 days after the meeting. The report shall contain the list of discussed points with conclusions and action timeline

In his offer, the contractor shall consider that at least 25% of the control sequences will have to be modified as a result of the optimization meetings

10.1.7 Final acceptance

The final acceptance takes place at the earliest two years after the provision acceptance under the condition that all issues identified during the follow-up have been resolved.

Upon a successful final acceptance, the contractual obligations of the contractor are deemed fulfilled.

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10.2 Rule-based control (RBC)

Note:

Specification templates in this chapter only describe the sequence of control. The specification text for material components (e.g. control valves, sensors, controllers, etc.) is not part of this specification and shall be specified separately or added to the provided specification templates.

There is no standard solution for rule-based control of Ground Source Heat Pump (GSHP) and Thermally Activated Building Systems (TABS). The sequences presented hereafter represent just some of the commonly applied control sequences.

10.2.01 Control of primary ground source heat exchanger pump

Work:

Controller programming
Commissioning
Optimization

Operation:

This sequence of operation concerns the control of the pump in the primary circuit of the ground source heat exchanger (GSHX)

The pump shall enable external control by means of a 0-10 V control signal

The pump in this configuration shall be hydraulically decoupled from the heat pump circuit by means of a pressure equalization bypass

The pump shall be enabled when there is a heating need (heat pump primary pump operational) or cooling need (passive cooling enabled)

The pump speed shall be controlled so that the a constant temperature differential between the supply and return pipe of the GSHX is maintained constant and equal to the design value; this shall be accomplished by means of a PI controller that controls the pump speed

The pump speed shall be limited by a low limit value that corresponds to the minimum flow rate at which a sufficient heat exchange can still be achieved in the GSHX (avoidance of laminar flow)

10.2.02 Control of thermally activated concrete core distribution manifold

Note:

This section contains a proposal for temperature and valve control sequences. It can be applied to individual TABS zones (if the building is divided in TABS zones) or the entire building if no zoning has been foreseen (in this case one can expect poorer comfort conditions if loads vary considerably among zones).

The proposed principle can be further adapted or detailed by the designer on a per project basis in order to suit the exact project needs. For example, one can specify other pump control strategies (e.g. day/night operation, continuous intermittent operation, discontinuous intermittent operation), or other temperature control strategies (e.g. controlling mean TABS water temperature instead of supply or return water temperature).

Work:

Controller programming
Commissioning
Optimization

Operation:

> General

T_{rm} : running mean outdoor temperature (see section 3.14 in EN 16798-1)

Each manifold set (supply and return) is equipped with one [pressure independent] control valve with a servomotor for 0-10 V control signal and a PT1000 [active] temperature sensor in the supply and return pipe

> Control of TABS zone supply temperature

The supply temperature is calculated based on the averaged outside temperature and the operation mode:

- Heating: $T_{supply} = 18\text{ °C} + A (18\text{ °C} - T_{rm})$ where coefficient A equals 0.35
- Cooling: $T_{supply} = 18\text{ °C} + B (18\text{ °C} - T_{rm})$ where coefficient B equals 0.45

Coefficients A and B in the equations above represent default values that need to be corrected during the commissioning phase, taking into account selected thermal comfort performance indicators

The operation mode is defined based on the averaged outside temperature:

- $T_{rm} \leq 10\text{ °C}$: heating
- $T_{rm} > 10\text{ °C}$ and $< 12\text{ °C}$: standby
- $T_{rm} \geq 12\text{ °C}$: cooling

The evaluation of the averaged outside temperature for the switching of the operation mode is performed once per day at midnight

In standby mode, the circuit supplying the manifold zone is isolated from the heat generation side but the pump stays enabled and runs at 50 % of its nominal speed

A direct mode change from heating into cooling shall not be possible; one shall always transfer through the standby mode for a duration of at least 24 hours

A warning shall be generated if the supply temperature exceeds the supply temperature set point by more than 2 K in heating mode; if the temperature is exceeded by more than 4 K the circuit shall be isolated from the primary heat supply

A warning shall be generated if the supply temperature falls below the supply temperature set point by more than 2 K in heating mode; if the temperature drops by more than 4 K below the set point the circuit shall be isolated from the primary heat supply

>> Control of the distribution manifold control valve (option A)

Note:

This option introduces a correction factor as a function of running mean outdoor temperature, which is used to control the flow rate in order to take into account the influence of internal heat gains.

In zones with low internal heat gains, the correction factor shall be higher in heating mode (more TABS output due to low internal gains) and lower in cooling mode (less TABS output to low internal gains). In zones with high internal heat gains, the correction factor shall be low in heating mode (less TABS output needed due to high internal loads) and high in cooling mode (more TABS output needed due to high internal loads).

In each operation mode (heating, cooling, standby) the valve control signal is a function of running mean outdoor temperature

There function shall be individually configurable per manifold control valve

The shape of the function shall be determined during the commissioning phase for each thermal zone controlled by a given control valve, taking into account selected thermal comfort performance indicators

>> Control of the distribution manifold control valve (option B)

Note:

This option introduces a correction factor as a function of running mean outdoor temperature, which is used to control the temperature differential between TABS zone supply and return water temperature. This factor is introduced in order to take into account the influence of internal heat gains. The control valve is controlled to maintain a calculated return water temperature. In order to avoid situations where the calculated return water temperature cannot be practically achieved (e.g. the calculated return temperature is lower than zone air temperature in heating), the max temperature differential is bound by the supply temperature one hand and the zone temperature on the other hand.

In zones with low internal heat gains, the correction factor shall be lower in heating mode (smaller temperature differential and thus more TABS output) and high in cooling mode (larger temperature differential and thus less TABS output). In zones with high internal heat gains, the correction factor shall be high in heating mode (larger temperature differential and thus less TABS output) and low in cooling mode (smaller temperature differential and thus more TABS output).

In heating and cooling mode a PI-controller maintains a set return temperature by controlling the flow rate through a TABS element; the feedback signal comes from a temperature sensor installed in the return pipe from the collecting manifold

The set return temperature is calculated by the controlled according to the following equation:

$T_r = T_s - C (T_v - T_i)$, where:

- T_r : return temperature
- T_s : supply temperature
- T_i : zone air temperature set point
- C : correction factor (a value between greater than zero and smaller than one)⁴

The correction factor C is a function of running mean outdoor temperature

There function shall be individually configurable per manifold control valve

The shape of the function shall be determined during the commissioning phase for each thermal zone controlled by a given control valve, taking into account selected thermal comfort performance indicators

In standby mode, the control valve is fully opened

⁴ Note that a correction factor of 1 will result in the calculated return temperature equal to the zone air temperature set point. Such temperature can be achieved only in limit condition for flow rate equal to zero. The same goes for a factor of 0, which corresponds to the return temperature equal to supply temperature, what can only be achieved in theory if the flow rate is unlimited. Therefore, caution should be used when determining the factor applicable to each zone.

10.3 Model predictive control (MPC)

Note:

This particular description of an MPC system assumes that MPC is implemented on top of Direct Digital Control (DDC) system. In this architecture (most common nowadays), the acquisition of and generation of physical control signals (analog and digital) takes place in DDC controllers installed in proximity of field sensors and actuators. The advantage of using a system of decentralized DDC controllers is that they are capable of rapidly polling sensors and switches for their value because of direct and individual physical connection to each of these elements. Therefore, a DDC controller is capable of producing a real-time⁵ response to changes detected field devices. This is something that is especially convenient when an immediate response of the control system is required. This is typically the case in safety functions (e.g. interlocks related to a frost alarm in an air-handling unit). Moreover, DDC controllers can maintain system in operation even if the communication link with other internetwork devices fails (e.g. by using pre-programmed fallback or most recent values).

In this architecture, the MPC is an additional module that communicates with DDC controllers over a communication network. The communication is performed using a communication protocol. This specification is based on BACnet (EN ISO 16484-5 and ASHRAE 135). Thanks to the use of a communication protocol, the MPC is capable of reading locally measured values and changing set points and operating modes of control programs in DDC controllers. If the communication link between controllers and MPC is interrupted, the system can continue to operate using fallback control algorithms or default values.

Another advantage of MPC as an independent system attached to the underlying control is that the client has the possibility of changing the provider of the MPC in the future, shall he not be satisfied with its performance or the quality of service provided by its supplier. By carefully planning for the integration of the MPC in the building automation and control system from the very beginning, extra cost involved with the integration of MPC into the control system can be minimized to bare minimum. By failing to account for the MPC in advance, various problems can appear during the installation and commissioning of the system, such as:

Missing or unsupported BACnet objects at controllers' interface

Controllers with missing BACnet Interoperability Building Blocs (BIBBs)

Inability to correctly override write variables used by controllers' control program

Etc.

In some cases (e.g. missing BIBBs or unsupported BACnet objects), problems can only be resolved by replacing the hardware. Other problems, e.g. missing BACnet objects or control programs not designed to be overridden by an overlying control system, can be resolved later, but usually for a cost much higher than if they had been accounted for in the design phase.

⁵ Here, real-time means that the longest response time can be determined in advance and does not depend on some unpredictable behaviour of the system.

To avoid problems during the execution and commissioning phase, the designer shall take care of the following tasks and make sure that they are correctly represented in the project:

Describe sequence of operation for all system parts where DDC will be applied

For each sequence of operation, list all the necessary BACnet objects that shall be exposed at the interface of the system

For each DDC controller, list all BACnet BIBBs and object types that it shall support

Work:

Programming

Configuration

Commissioning

Optimization

Specification:

> General

All devices without native BACnet support shall be integrated in the building communication network via BACnet gateways

The MPC controls all system components (air handling units, heat pumps, chillers, boilers, dry coolers, cooling towers, pumps, fans, air volume dampers, valves) by writing in the relevant property fields of concerned BACnet objects in local DDC controllers

The MPC acts on top of the conventional DDC, which is used to control local processes

The MPC shall exert full control over at least the following devices through their direct or indirect BACnet interface:

- Heat pumps, chillers and boilers
- Pumps
- Air dampers
- Control valves
- Fans and variable speed drives

MPC shall have full access to at least the following meters, sensors and switches through their direct or indirect BACnet interface:

- Heat meters
- Electricity meters
- Temperature sensors
- Humidity sensors

- Air quality sensors

All air flow controllers and control valves shall be controllable over their maximal control range

The MPC software shall be installed on a [local workstation](#) delivered by the contractor

The MPC may use an additional cloud-based backend to perform resource-intensive calculations. In this case, it shall be the local MPC controller that always establishes the connection to the cloud-based backend so that no inbound IP connection is necessary and thus no ports in the firewall have to be opened

Every zone for which temperature [and/or CO₂](#) control is required shall be equipped with at least one [temperature or CO₂ sensor](#)

Every fan, pump or a group of (parallel) pumps shall be equipped with equipment for flow measuring

Electricity used by all HVAC equipment shall be metered; all major equipment ([air handling units, pumps, heat pumps, chillers](#)) shall be equipped with individual electricity meters

IP-infrastructure shall be designed and executed for link speeds of at least [100 Mbit/s](#); all structural cabling shall be tested after the installation according to EN 50346; links that do not achieve the demonstrated performance shall be replaced and re-tested

> Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The following system KPIs shall be calculated for every day, week, month and year:

- Heating: kWh_{th}/m² and kWh_{el}/m²
- Cooling: kWh_{th}/m² and kWh_{el}/m²
- Ventilation: kWh_{el}/m²
- Pumps: kWh_{el}/m²
- Discomfort hours: Kh/year and Kh²/year
- Electricity cost (taking into account variable rate): €

The surface used for the calculation of KPIs shall be total net surface area

KPI values shall be logged and archived in a persistent data storage

Visualization of KPI trends shall be performed in the Building Management System (BMS)

> Model

The MPC shall use a mathematical model of building and technical systems to calculate controlled variables; this model shall calculate flows and temperatures of all HVAC system parts that significantly influence building energy use; the calculated values shall be logged and exported for analysis

The model shall adhere to the law of conservation of energy and the law of conservation of mass

Zones with independent temperature, air flow rate or air quality control shall be modelled separately so that the temperature of each individual room is calculated as a separate variable in the model; it is not allowed to simulate separate rooms, each individually cooled and heated, as one zone and to use post-processing to calculate the value for individual rooms

- Room temperature shall be calculated taking into account heat transfer with HVAC, internal heat loads, solar heat loads through transparent construction elements and heat loads through opaque construction elements; the calculation shall be performed for external construction elements that border on outside air and internal construction elements that border on other zones of the same building
- Solar gains shall be calculated using a physical model that takes into account the dimensions of the glazed surfaces and their technical characteristics such as absorption and reflection coefficients, orientation and shading
- Heat transfer between adjacent rooms and outside environment shall be calculated using physical models for heat conduction, convection and radiation, taking into account the material properties of all building fabrics, the order and thickness of material layers and the transient behavior of the heat transfer due to building fabric mass
- The model shall be used to calculate the electricity use of all controlled technical systems; it calculates efficiency of pumps and fans, efficacies of heat exchangers, coefficients of performance (COP) of heat pumps and chillers based on relevant flow rates, pressure and temperature measurements
- The model shall be used to simulate the behavior of the building and its technical systems for the period of at least 48 hours in advance; the simulation shall be performed using weather forecast data
- The MPC shall minimize the total electricity use for the simulated period; it shall take variable electricity rate into account
- The MPC shall respect operational limits for temperature and CO₂:
 - Temperature: [class 2 as per EN 16798-1 \(annex B\)](#)
 - CO₂: [max. 1200 ppm](#)
- A BACnet Schedule object stored in the BMS server controls the above operational limits; MPC shall subscribe via COV mechanism to receive notifications if the schedule is updated

> Control

- MPC shall use priority ____ when writing to BACnet objects in other BACnet devices (local forcing uses priority ____ and DDC controls priority ____). If some other system writes on the same variable at a higher priority, MPC shall interpret this as imposed value for the entire simulation period and try to maintain the imposed comfort level at minimal operational cost using the imposed value
- MPC shall recognize if the input value of physical outputs has been overridden by the BMS; in this case the Out_Of_Service property of the corresponding BACnet object shall be activated by the BMS; MPC shall either subscribe for the COV Out_Of_Service property of each observed object (push) or it shall periodically poll for the change of value (pull)
- Activating the Out_Of_Service property will cause the Present_Value property to be removed from the associated physical output; in this case, the output value used by the MPC remains equal to the last value set until overwritten by the command from the BMS
- When the Out_Of_Service property is reset to the default state, the current value shall be taken over immediately and automatically
- MPC does not have to be BTL-certified if it only acts as BACnet client on the network: this means that MPC is only using BIBBs of type A; if MPC is BTL-certified, it may be used as a BACnet server if necessary (e.g. to store object of type such as Schedule, Trend Log, etc.)

hybrid
GEOTABS

Controlling the power of the ground by integration

10.4 Building automation controllers

Documents:

Data sheet: see specifications

BACnet BTL certificate

BACnet Protocol Implementation Conformance Statement (PICS)

General specifications:

> General requirements

@ Data sheet

Material and construction:

- Polycarbonate, polyamide, ABS or equivalent housing
- All functions and indications are on the front of the device
- Mounting on a 35 mm DIN rail

Protection index: IP20

Conditions of service:

- Temperature: 0 to +50 °C
- Humidity: 10 to 90% (non-condensing)

Power supply:

- 24 V DC voltage, tolerance -15 / + 10%
- Note: If the controller is equipped with an internal rectifier, the power supply can be 24 V AC (50 Hz, tolerance +/-2%)

> Hardware

Microprocessor:

- Capacity and speed are determined by the contractor based on the amount of information to be processed; in any case, the architecture of the microprocessor shall be at least 16 bit
- The duration of a cycle does not exceed 5 seconds (including the request of the values of the measurement points, the execution of the operations and calculations necessary starting from these values, the transmission of the resulting values to the control points and if necessary, data exchange with the control unit or with another system)
- At least one cycle is executed every 5 seconds

Memory and internal storage:

- Memory: min. DDR2 SDRAM
- Internal storage: EEPROM (NOR or SLC NAND flash)
- External storage: space for an SD card (min. SDSC / SCHC) min. 8 GB
- Reserve capacity: min. 30% of the memory capacity occupied
- Note: the reserve can be reduced to 10% if the memory / storage is expandable

Real time clock and 365-day calendar

Battery of capacitor to support the real time clock and RAM for at least 72 h

Integrated Ethernet network switch:

- Application: 10BASE-T, 1000BASE-TX
- Ports: 2x RJ45 which allow to connect several programmable controllers in series like a bus
- Functions: auto-negotiation, auto-MDIX, DHCP, DNS, RTSP

Diagnostic LEDs: power supply, communication, processor status

> BACnet stack

>> General

Native BACnet device according to ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 135

Tested and certified by BACnet Testing Laboratories (BTL)

Data Link Layer:

- BACnet IP, Foreign Device
- MS / TP master, baud rate 9600 to 115200

Supported character set: UTF-8 (length 32 characters)

Support for segmented messages

BBMD (BACnet Broadcast Management Device) function

In the event of a power supply interruption and when the mains voltage returns:

- The properties of dynamic variables shall be kept in the buffer for at least 72 hours; this applies to objects such as Trend Log, Schedule and Calendar
- The Recipient_List properties in the Notification Class object are preserved; clients continue to automatically receive event and alarm information without having to re-subscribe
- Personal COV messages are maintained
- COV subscriptions to other BACnet servers are automatically reestablished

- Connections between controllers are updated (resubscription)

>> BACnet Interoperability Building Blocs (BIBB)

Device profile: B-BC

Additional BIBBs required (not included in the standard B-BC profile):

- Data Sharing: DS-COV-A, DS-COV-B
- Alarm and Event Management: AE-N-E-B, AE-ASUM-B
- Scheduling: SCHED-I-B
- Trending: T-VMT-I-B, T-VMT-E-B, T-ATR-B

>> Objects

The device shall be able to generate and expose at least the following objects:

- Do not have to be created and deleted dynamically:
 - Device (DEV)
 - Analog Input (AI), Binary Input (BI), Multi-state Input (MI)
 - Analog Output (AO), Binary Output (BO), Multi-state Output (MO)
 - Analog Value (AV), Binary Value (BV), Multi-state Value (MV)
 - File (FIL)
 - Loop (LP)
- Shall created and deleted dynamically:
 - Calendar (CAL)
 - Schedule (SCHED)
 - Trend Log (TLOG)
 - Notification Class (NC)
 - Event Enrollment (EE)

Objects shall support all the properties necessary for COV Reporting and Intrinsic Reporting

> Embedded software

>> General

The on-board software and the control program are stored in the non-volatile internal storage

Operating system: multitasking and deterministic

SNTP client: automatic clock synchronization via internet

HTTPS server: device configuration via internal website

The on-board software update and control program shall be able to be carried out remotely from a computer via the local network and without interrupting the operation of the controller

The device shall be able to prevent unauthorized persons from accessing the on-board software (e.g. by means of a password)

A cut of the mains voltage causes an ordered deactivation of the device and, when the mains voltage returns, an automatic and ordered start-up

>> Gateway

The device shall be able to function as master and BACnet/IP gateway for at least the following communication protocols:

- BACnet MS/TP
- KNX (S-mode)
- Modbus RTU
- M-Bus

The integration of the communication protocols mentioned above is carried out either by means of a driver in the software of the device itself (native support); the use of an external gateway, which translates the unknown communication protocol into an intermediate protocol supported by the software of the controller, is not allowed in this case

Update of the embedded software shall be possible via the internet without the need of hardware replacement

>> Events (alarms and notifications)

It shall be possible, regardless of the communication technology or the type of underlying physical point, to define notification conditions for each data point read by the controller

Generated alarms and notifications are recorded in a buffer database in the internal storage of the device

Event records log at least the following information about the event:

- Reference of the source (data point)
- Timestamp
- Value
- Message
- Type (abnormal value, normal value, error)
- Priority level
- State (active, acknowledged, inactive)

There shall exist a possibility of sending alarms and alerts via email and SMS (via SMTP) without the use of additional software, web server or BMS server; messages sent shall be able to be personalized and contain variables configured in the controller

>> Schedules

It shall be possible to generate hourly schedules on a monthly, weekly and daily basis, and to program exceptions (public holidays, vacation periods, etc.)

Schedules are saved in a local database and synchronized with the real time clock

Each schedule shall be able to change the state or value of a data point independently of the communication technology or the type of underlying physical point

Each device shall support schedules in accordance with the following minimum conditions:

- At least 12 switching times per weekday
- At least 6 exceptions (direct entry or reference to a calendar object), each with at least 6 switching times

Each device shall be able to record at least 3 schedules with each a list for at least 10 date entries

>> Data logging and trends

It shall be possible to collect, to process and save current values of any data point as logs in a buffer database in the internal storage of the device

The possibility of registration shall be independent of the communication technology or the type of underlying physical point; this means that it shall be possible to collect external data points, which the device can access via its network interfaces

The recording of each data point shall be possible according to at least the following modes:

- Fixed interval
- Defined change in the value of an observed data point (COV)
- Trigger by a data trigger point

Minimum sampling interval shall be no more than one second

Recorded data shall be able to be exported to an SLC NAND SD card; at least one of the following digital formats is supported: CSV, XML, JSON

> Programming and configuration software

Programming, configuration and management of the controller shall be performed in an integrated development environment (IDE) on the Windows operating system in standardized languages according to IEC 61131-3 (or equivalent)

The IDE has modules for configuring the BACnet, Modbus (TCP/RTU), M-Bus and DALI communication protocols

Everyone shall be able to obtain and use the development environment (IDE) without additional requirements from the supplier (training, certifications, etc.); any form of vendor lock-in is strictly prohibited

The number of licenses for the use of the IDE depends on the total number of machines supplied and installed; one shall provide at least one license per 50 devices

Execution:

> General

DDC controllers shall always be installed in low-voltage switchgear assemblies

All controllers shall come from a single manufacturer and shall be able to be programmed, configured and managed by a single common software

Controllers shall not depend on a connection to a server or a master regulator to be able to execute the regulation program

Automation of a technical node (e.g. local heat production, substation, air-handling unit, etc.) shall be carried out with at most one programmable controller with sufficient hardware and software capacity; distribution of control logic among several controllers is not allowed

> Events

All announcements shall be generated in the controller and not on the side of the BMS

> Control of order execution

In binary and multi-state objects, the Feedback_Value property shall allow the desired state to be defined via Intrinsic Reporting

In case of discrepancy between the actual and desired state, an alert shall be generated after a specific adjustable time

The real state shall be acquired via the physical input

> Integration of meters with bus interface

Meters (fluids, energy) are integrated into the controller via a communication module

Data points from meters shall be made available as BACnet objects of the Analog Value type

> Totalization of operating time

The total operating time is recorded in seconds in binary objects via the Elapsed_Active_Time property

The recorded value in seconds shall be converted into hours by being displayed using an additional object of the Analog Value type; the time shall be available via the Present_Value property; the Units property contains the time as a unit

An additional conversion function is necessary for the conversion of seconds into hours

The user shall be able to reset the totalizer to zero and set the upper limit in order to trigger a maintenance notification

Reset of the operating time shall be carried out via the overwriting of value by value zero of the Elapsed_Active_Time property and saved in the Time_Of_Active_Time_Reset property

Notifications are sent using the Intrinsic Reporting mechanism; the upper limit shall be set in the High_Limit property

> Manual control

In the event of modification of the Present_Value property of outgoing BACnet objects in forcing mode, the Priority parameter shall receive the value of 8; if there are no commands with higher priority (<8), the physical output is set to the value chosen manually

In the event of manual control of incoming BACnet objects, the Out_Of_Service property of the associated object shall be activated; consequently, the value of the Present_Value property can be adjusted as required from the BMS until the cancellation of the manual command

Activating the Out_Of_Service property causes the Present_Value property to be removed from the associated physical output; in this case, the output value remains equal to the last value set until overwritten by the command from the BMS

When the Out_Of_Service property is reset to the default state, the current value shall be taken over immediately and automatically

Manual interventions by means of micro switches on interface modules or multi-pole switches not connected via BACnet shall also be reported; objects of type Binary Input (via physical connection) or Binary Value (via communicative connection) shall be used for this purpose

11 Energy meters

11.01 Ultrasonic energy meters

Products:

Ultrasonic heat meter

Work:

Supply and installation
Commissioning

Documents:

Data sheet: see specifications
Commissioning report

Certification:

CE marking
12 year warranty on the battery

Specifications:

> Ultrasonic heat meter

>> General

Conformity: EN 1434-1/2/4/5

>> Ultrasonic flowmeter

MID class: 2

Max working pressure: 16 bar

Max pressure drop: 0.15 bar (at nominal flow)

Dynamic measurement range (min/nominal flow): 1/100

Protection index: IP68

>> Programmable data logger

Polycarbonate, ABS or equivalent housing

Meter type: hot and cold

Min temperature range (fluid): +5 to +105 ° C

Differential temperature range (fluid): 0.2 to 100 K

Protection index: IP54

Battery: type D (Li-ion), autonomy at +20 ° C: min. 12 years

Memory: EEPROM for min. 2,000 retrieved values

External power supply: 1x230 V, 50 Hz

Communication module: BACnet MS/TP

>> Temperature probes and thermowells

Material:

- Two temperature probes: Pt500 or Pt1000 according to EN 60751
- Thermowells: EN 1.4301 or EN 1.4401
- Connection cable

Execution:

Installation and commissioning in accordance with EN 1434-6

Install temperature sensors in thermowells